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**MULTIPLE STELLAR
POPULATIONS IN ω CENTAURI**

TESI DI DOTTORATO
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Chapter 1

Introduction

This Ph.D. Thesis (*Tesi di Dottorato*) has been carried out in the framework of a large project (The Bologna Key Project on ω Cen, see Ferraro, Pancino, & Bellazzini, 2002b), entirely dedicated to the study of the globular cluster ω Centauri (NGC 5139). The scientific goals of the global project are aimed at understanding the formation and evolution of this anomalous cluster, in an attempt to explain its many peculiar properties (see Chapter 2 for a comprehensive literature review). In particular, the project goals are the following:

- The complete characterization of the complex stellar content of ω Cen, and the complete definition of the photometric properties of its sub-populations;
- The derivation of the detailed chemical abundance patterns of its red giant stars (the brightest and easiest to study), to identify the sources of chemical enrichment for each sub-population;
- The determination of the eventual age differences among the sub-populations, with the aim of deriving the star formation history of the cluster, and confirm or falsify the hypothesis that ω Cen was a self-enriching systems similar to, e.g., the dwarf galaxies in the Local Group;
- The derivation of the structural and kinematical properties of the largest possible number of stars belonging to different sub-populations in ω Cen, to reconstruct the (possibly different) dynamical evolution of each population.

By combining all these observations in an organized way, we hope to give clear-cut answers to some of the long-standing problems in the scenarios of formation and evolution of ω Cen.

1.1 The Bologna Key Project on ω Cen

To reach the above goals, we have started a vast spectro-photometric observational effort, mainly profiting from the extraordinary facilities and new generation instrumentation of the European Southern Observatory (ESO) located in La Silla and Paranal, Chile. The global project consists of different observational sub-projects, to address the fundamental questions posed above. In particular:

Wide Field Multi-band Photometry

A complete multi-wavelength photometric wide field survey to investigate the general morphology and properties of the sub-populations, from the optical to the near infrared. Most of the optical wide field data have been already collected with the Wide Field Imager (WFI) mounted at the ESO/MPI 2.2 m telescope in La Silla, during several observing runs from January 1999 to March 2000. Part of the data have been already published (Pancino et al., 2000), but the whole set of U , B , V , I , H_α and R data, covering an area of $33' \times 33'$, is still under processing. The infrared (IR) wide field survey has also been completely carried out with SOFI (Son Of Isaac) mounted at the ESO NTT (New Technology Telescope) in La Silla, Chile, and the data are presently under analysis. The cluster center has been mapped with nine overlapping pointings in J and K , covering an area of $13' \times 13'$.

Optical and Infrared Spectroscopy of the Red Giants

A vast spectroscopic survey of the red giants, both with optical and infrared high and medium resolution data, has been conducted with SOFI at the NTT and UVES (Ultraviolet Visual Echelle Spectrograph) at the Very Large Telescope (VLT) in Paranal, Chile. ~ 30 red giants in all the sub-populations have been observed with UVES at $R \sim 45,000$ and very high S/N , and another ~ 20 stars have been observed with SOFI. The analysis of the whole dataset has just begun, and will provide not only the detailed chemical abundance patterns, but also a set of precise radial velocities that will enable us to answer many of the open questions on ω Cen.

Relative Ages

A detailed high-resolution spectro-photometric study of the Turn-Off (TO) and Sub Giant Branch (SGB) region of ω Cen, the most sensitive to age variations.

We have already obtained high-resolution photometry of the cluster center in the U , B , V and I bands with FORSat the VLT, under extremely good seeing conditions, to study the sub-structures that will identify the SGB counterparts of the Red Giant Branch (RGB) sub-populations. We also have obtained high-resolution spectra of six SGB stars of different composition, so that we will be able to break the age-metallicity degeneracy and measure accurate age differences among the different sub-populations.

1.2 Thesis Organization

The thesis work presented here concentrates mostly on the definition and the study of the recently discovered (Lee et al., 1999; Pancino et al., 2000) metal-rich population in ω Cen, since its exact nature is still very poorly known. Although most of the work has been devoted to optical wide field photometry and high-resolution spectroscopy, other preliminary results concerning the whole Bologna Key Project on ω Cen will be mentioned and described, when relevant, throughout the following Chapters.

The Thesis is organized as follows. Chapter 2 will briefly summarize the vast literature on ω Cen, concentrating most on the observational evidence that is relevant to the problems treated in the following Chapters.

Chapter 3 describes results obtained on the wide field, multi-wavelength photometric dataset and some published (Pancino et al., 2000) and unpublished results. In particular, the Chapter will focus on the B , V and I WFI and on the J and K IR SOFI photometric datasets. The structure of the RGB will be analyzed, presenting the newly discovered metal-rich population (RGB-a) and some of its properties.

Chapter 4 concentrates on the spectroscopic survey of the red giants in ω Cen, describes the observational campaigns that have been carried out and shows some published (Pancino et al., 2002) and some preliminary results on the extremely metal-rich stars belonging to the RGB-a. The focus of the Chapter is on the UVES results, but part of the IR SOFI results are also mentioned in support of the presented evidence.

Chapter 5 presents an interesting result (Ferraro, Bellazzini, & Pancino, 2002a) concerning the proper motion of the metal-rich RGB-a stars, that opens new questions on the internal structure and dynamical evolution of ω Cen.

Chapter 6 is dedicated to a detailed statistical analysis of the RGB sub-populations spatial distribution and shape. The main results of this analysis

(still unpublished) support partially what found in Chapter 5, and adds more evidence on the very complex spatial structure of this dynamically young cluster.

Chapter 7 shows an application of the huge photometric catalog described in Chapter 3 to the calibration of the RGB-Tip method for determining distances (Bellazzini, Ferraro & Pancino, 2001).

Chapter 8 describes some very preliminary results on the study of the TO and SGB region of the Color Magnitude Diagram (CMD), and its implications for the relative ages of the sub-populations in ω Cen.

Finally, Chapter 9 summarizes the results obtained, and discusses them in the framework of the commonly accepted theories for the formation and evolution of ω Cen. Some answers are given to long-standing questions, while some new questions are risen. The remaining answers could come from the future survey with the multi-fiber spectrograph FLAMES. A brief description of the future projects completes the presentation.

1.3 Published Results

As discussed above, some of the results presented in this Thesis have been already published in refereed journals and conference proceedings. We list them here for ease of consultation, although they are also included in the bibliographic section and pointed out throughout the various Chapters.

- **Pancino, E.**, Ferraro, F.R., Bellazzini, M., Piotto, G. & Zoccali M. “New Evidence on the Complex Structure of the Red Giant Branch of ω Centauri” 2000, ApJL, 534, L83
- Bellazzini, M., Ferraro, F. R. & **Pancino, E.** “A Step Toward the Calibration of the Red Giant Branch Tip as a Standard Candle” 2001, ApJ, 556, 635
- **Pancino, E.** “The Multiple Stellar Populations in ω Cen” 2002, ASP Conf. Ser. 265: Omega Centauri, A Unique Window into Astrophysics, 313
- Ferraro, F. R., **Pancino, E.** & Bellazzini, M. “The bologna Keyu Project on ω Centauri” 2002, ASP Conf. Ser. 265: Omega Centauri, A Unique Window into Astrophysics, 407

- Ferraro, F. R., Bellazzini, M. & **Pancino, E.** “discovery of an Accreted Stellar System Within the Globula Cluster ω Centauri” 2002, *ApJL*, 573, L95
- **Pancino, E.**, Pasquini, L., Hill, V., Ferraro, F. R. & Bellazzini, M. “High-Resolution spectroscopy of Metal-Rich Giants in ω Centauri: First Indication of Type Ia Supernova Enrichment” 2002, *ApJL*, 568, L101
- Origlia, L., Ferraro, F. R., Bellazzini, M. & **Pancino, E.** “A Near-Infrared Spectroscopic Screening of the Red Giant Populations in ω Centauri” 2003, *accepted for publication in ApJ*
- **Pancino, E.**, Seleznev, A., Ferraro, F. R., Bellazzini, M. & Piotto, G. “The multiple stellar population in ω Centauri: spatial distribution and structural properties” 2003, *submitted to MNRAS*

Chapter 2

Literature Review on ω Centauri

ω Centauri (NGC 5139) is the most massive and bright system among the Galactic Globular Clusters (GGC), and it shows also a remarkable flattening, which is attributed to its high degree of rotation. However, its most astonishing characteristic is the chemical inhomogeneity: ω Cen is the only GGC that shows clear and undisputed variations not only in the light elements abundances, but also in its overall metallicity. From this point of view, ω Cen could be considered a “bridge” between the common globulars, which are unable to retain the gas ejected by their former massive stars, and the dwarf galaxies, which are the least massive self-enriching stellar systems known (Meylan & Mayor, 1986; Meylan, 1987). It is interesting to note that those dwarf spheroidal galaxies (dSph) that are less luminous than ω Cen (e.g. Ursa Minor, Draco and Carina) show very modest abundance spreads with respect to this cluster. Table 2.1 shows a qualitative comparison between the typical GGC properties (from Harris, 1996) and the typical dSph (from Irwin & Hatzidimitriou, 1995; Mateo, 1998): ω Cen clearly shows intermediate

Qualitative comparison between GCs and dSph.			
Proprietà	AG	ω Cen	dSph
Integrated Magnitude, M_V	< -9	-10	$-8 \div -13$
Total Mass, in M_\odot	$\sim 10^5 M_\odot$	10^6	$10^6 \div 10^8$
Ellipticity, $\epsilon = (1 - b/a)$	< 0.1	0.12	> 0.13
Abundance Spread, $\Delta[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$, in dex	< 0.1	~ 1	$0.2 \div 1.4$

Table 2.1: Typical characteristics of GGCs (from Harris, 1996) are compared to the corresponding characteristics for ω Cen and for dSphs (from Irwin & Hatzidimitriou, 1995). Although qualitative, this comparison clearly shows that ω Cen, in some of its properties, is more similar to dSphs than to the typical GC in the Milky Way and thus represents a “bridge” between the two classes of objects.

properties, thus possibly representing some kind of conjunction between the two classes of objects.

ω Cen is one of the most studied objects: a search in the NASA ADS (Astrophysics Data System) in march 2003 revealed more than 860 published papers concerning ω Cen, of which 745 published in refereed journals. In this Chapter we will try to briefly review and summarize this vast literature reservoir of observational evidence and different interpretations of its many peculiarities, that culminated in a conference entirely dedicated to ω Cen, held in Cambridge, UK, in august 2001 (van Leeuwen, Hughes & Piotto, 2002). We will concentrate here on a summary of the observational results and only briefly mention the possible explanations. A more detailed and organic discussion on the proposed and more likely scenarios for the formation and evolution of ω Cen will be presented in Chapter 9.

2.1 Photometry and Color Magnitude Diagrams

Table 2.2 summarizes the integrated photometric properties of the cluster, together with some other general properties like the reddening. As shown in Figure 2.1, the total absolute magnitude of ω Cen is by far the brightest ($M_V \sim -10$) in the compilation by Harris (1996), and it corresponds to an equally outstanding total mass of a few $10^6 M_\odot$ (see Section 2.4 for more details on the mass determinations of ω Cen). Moreover, only three GGC (NGC 6715, NGC 6441 and NGC 2419) are more luminous than half of ω Cen, while most of them have much lower luminosities and masses ($M_V \sim -7$ and $M \sim 10^5 M_\odot$).

As far as the reddening of ω Cen is concerned, Lub (2002) reviewed critically the previous literature determinations, concluding that $E(B - V) = 0.11$. Indeed, while the vast majority of the studies reports values very close to $E(B - V) = 0.11 \div 0.12$, the determinations obtained with the COBE maps (Schlegel, Finkbeiner & Davis, 1998) and with far ultraviolet photometry with the Ultraviolet Imaging Telescope (UIT – Whitney et al., 1994) tend to favour a somewhat higher value, $E(B - V) = 0.14 \div 0.15$. Lub (2002) also points out that no significant differential reddening has been detected in ω Cen (see also Section 2.5).

The first comprehensive, pioneering study of ω Cen from photographic plates by Woolley (1966) produced ~ 7000 magnitudes and ~ 4500 proper motions, in the B and V bands, of bright stars lying between $3'$ and $22'$ from the cluster center. Followed by other photometric studies by, e.g., Dickens &

Galactic Globular Clusters from Harris 1996

Figure 2.1: Top panels: the histograms of absolute magnitudes, M_V (left panel), and masses, $\log M/M_\odot$ (right panel), for GGC are shown (from Harris, 1996). The position of ω Cen, at the extreme of the distributions, is marked by an arrow. Bottom panels: the luminosities of GGC (also from Harris, 1996), divided by the luminosity of ω Cen, are plotted as a function of r_h , the half-mass radius. Only three GC in the whole Galaxy are more luminous than half of ω Cen.

Integrated Photometric and General Properties of ω Cen		
Color Excess, $E(B - V)$	0.15	Djorgovski (1993)
Color Excess, $E(B - V)$	0.12	Harris (1996)
Color Excess, $E(B - V)$	0.11	Lub (2002)
Visual Absorption, A_V	0.47	Djorgovski (1993)
Integrated Magnitude, V_t	3.53	Djorgovski (1993)
Integrated Magnitude, V_t	3.68	Harris (1996)
Integrated Luminosity, M_V	-10.07	Djorgovski (1993)
Integrated Color ($U - B$)	0.19	Harris (1996)
Integrated Color ($B - V$)	0.78	Harris (1996)
Integrated Color ($V - R$)	0.51	Harris (1996)
Integrated Color ($V - I$)	1.05	Harris (1996)

Table 2.2: Some general, integrated photometric properties of ω Cen.

Woolley (1967) or Cannon & Stobie (1973) this work showed how the RGB possesses a large spread in color, incompatible with the photometric errors.

The subsequent series of photometric studies were based not only on photographic photometry, but also on photoelectric measurements and on the first CCD photometries. We cite as examples the works by Alcaino & Liller (1987), Dickens & Caldwell (1988) and Noble et al. (1991). The general aim of these studies was to reach fainter and fainter stars, and to extend to the outer regions of the cluster, where crowding was less severe.

It was thus possible to measure some fundamental parameters of ω Cen. The Turn-Off (TO) position, for example, was determined by Alcaino & Liller (1987) and Noble et al. (1991), resulting in both cases at $V = 18.3$. First attempts to determine the cluster age and its distance modulus were also based on these photometries, like the absolute age of 16 ± 3 Gyr and the visual distance modulus of $(m - M)_V = 14.29 \pm 0.18$, determined using the main sequence by Noble et al. (1991). The intrinsic dispersion of the RGB was also estimated to be $\sigma_{B-V} = 0.056 \pm 0.016$ mag, by gaussian fitting to the color distribution.

The first CCD photometry of the cluster center was obtained by Lyngå (1996) in four photometric bands (B , V , R e I) and comprised more than 3500 stars (Figure 2.2). In the same years, the OGLE (Optical Gravitational Lensing Experiment) team observed six fields of $15' \times 15'$, including the cluster center, to look for binary and variable stars (Kaluzny et al., 1996, 1997). The variable stars population in ω Cen is quite large, including RR Lyræ and population II Cepheids (~ 150 in total), 24 SX Phe stars, 7 contact binaries, 5 detached or semi-detached binaries, and 3 likely spotted variables (FK Com

Figure 2.2: The first CCD photometry of ω Cen’s center, obtained by Lyngå (1996). The large spread of the RGB and of the HB, incompatible with the photometric errors, is clearly visible.

or RS CVn type stars). For more information on variable stars in ω Cen, see Rey et al. (2000), and references therein.

HST (Hubble Space Telescope) studies in the V e I bands were also conducted by Elson et al. (1995) and Anderson (1997), followed then by NICMOS infrared observations by Pulone et al. (1998) and de Marchi (1999). These studies reached as faint as $V \simeq 26$ on the small regions of $\sim 2.5' \times 2.5'$ covered by the WFPC2 (Wide Field Planetary Camera). This enabled to obtain precise luminosity functions, down to $V \sim 24$, and mass functions, down to $\sim 0.2M_{\odot}$. By comparing inner and outer fields it was possible to study in detail the effects of mass segregation, confirming that ω Cen is not completely dynamically relaxed. This is further confirmed by the updated work by Anderson (2002), based on extensive HST photometry of the main sequence stars, who found some mass segregation in ω Cen, but not nearly as much as equipartition would predict.

The modern era in the photometric studies of ω Cen was opened with wide field studies like the ones by Lee et al. (1999) and Pancino et al. (2000), further discussed in Chapter 3, that allowed the discovery of a new sub-population in ω Cen. These studies were immediately followed by wide field photometries in the Strömgren system, by Hughes & Wallerstein (2000) and Hilker & Richtler

Figure 2.3: The HB of ω Cen in the $(FUV - 3500, FUV)$ plane, from Whitney et al. (1998). Most of the HB stars are located on the cool (right) side of the clearly visible gap at $T_{eff} \simeq 16,000^{\circ}K$. At higher temperatures the blue tail becomes quite populated again, but the population of these stars is quite dispersed.

(2000), and in the Washington-DDO system (Majewski et al., 2000; Frinchaboy et al., 2002) that were the basis to derive populous photometric Metallicity Distribution Functions (MDF – see Section 2.5).

From these studies, we have also some contradictory information on a possible age spread among the TO stars. Hughes & Wallerstein (2000) and Hilker & Richtler (2000) detect an age spread of approximately 3–5 Gyr, judging from the TO region morphology. Such an age spread is not confirmed by Majewski et al. (2000) or Frinchaboy et al. (2002). Concerning this problem, we would like to recall that, even if the TO region is the most sensitive to age in the whole CMD, to correctly derive ages from the TO region, accurate measurements of the metallicity are needed, since a strong age-metallicity degeneracy still remains. Since no spectroscopic metallicity determination of TO stars in ω Cen exists yet, these preliminary indications on the age spread must be considered with much care. We will discuss more about the relative ages of sub-populations in Chapter 8.

2.1.1 Horizontal Branch Peculiarities

The existence of a quite extended blue Horizontal Branch (HB) in ω Cen, down to the faintest photometric limit, was already known since Cannon & Stobie (1973) and Norris (1974). Bailyn et al. (1992), had found that the extremely

blue HB stars (EHB, see below) in ω Cen were more centrally concentrated than the normal HB stars, and made the hypothesis that they were the result of binary interactions. An extended blue HB tail has been observed in many globular clusters and it is due to a variation of the M_{env}/M_{core} ratio of HB stars, where the core mass is approximately constant ($M_{core} \simeq 0.5M_{\odot}$) while the envelope mass (M_{env}) varies due to different amounts of mass loss in the RGB phase (Rood, 1973; Buonanno, Corsi, & Fusi Pecci, 1985; Fusi Pecci et al., 1993): lower envelope masses correspond to more exposed cores, resulting in hotter – and thus bluer – stars. While metallicity is the fundamental parameter driving the HB morphology, there must be a *second parameter* (or a combination of other parameters, including age, core rotation and environment) that seems to be at work, and that it is needed to explain the very different HB morphologies of twin clusters like, e.g., M 3 and M 13 (see Fusi Pecci et al., 1996; Buonanno et al., 1997, and references therein).

Ultraviolet studies by Whitney et al. (1994) and Whitney et al. (1998), obtained with UIT and complemented by u Strömgren photometry, added more quantitative information on the HB of ω Cen. In particular, they first report on the presence of a large *gap* in the blue tail of the HB, centered around a temperature of $T \simeq 16,000^{\circ}K$ (Figure 2.3). Also, the presence of gaps (i.e., regions in the HB that are underpopulated or devoid of stars) has been identified in many other GGC (Ferraro et al., 1998; Piotto et al., 1999). The gap found by Whitney et al. (1994) could be explained either with the modelization of mass loss along the RGB by D’Cruz, Dorman, Rood, & O’Connell (1996), or with the hypothesis that the metallicity in the HB stars of ω Cen *increases* with the effective temperature (D’Cruz et al., 2000).

But the most interesting characteristic of the HB in ω Cen is the presence of a very large EHB (Extreme Horizontal Branch) population, the largest ever observed in a GGC, that extends well below (i.e., hotter than) the minimum envelope mass limit (Moehler et al., 2002; D’Cruz et al., 2002). A similar population has been observed only in one other GGC: NGC 2808 (Sweigart et al., 2002). The nature of these “blue hook”, extremely hot HB stars ($T_{eff} \geq 35,000^{\circ}K$) is still debated, but the most likely explanation is that they lost too much of their envelope mass during the RGB phase, and ignited Helium much later than usual, when the star was already on the white dwarf cooling sequence (Moehler et al., 2002). Since the HB study is not part of the present Thesis work, we point the interested reader to the above literature for further details.

Position and Distance of ω Cen		
Right ascension, α (J2000)	$13^h26^m45.9^s$	Djorgovski & Meylan (1993)
Declination, δ (J2000)	$-47^\circ28'37.0''$	Djorgovski & Meylan (1993)
Galactic latitude, l_{II}	309.10	Djorgovski & Meylan (1993)
Galactic longitude, b_{II}	14.97	Djorgovski & Meylan (1993)
Turn-Off Magnitude, V_{TO}	18.3	Alcaino & Liller (1987)
HB level, V_{HB}	14.52	Peterson (1993)
HB level, V_{HB}	14.53	Harris (1996)
Distance Modulus, $(m - M)_V$	14.29	Noble et al. (1991)
Distance Modulus, $(m - M)_V$	13.92	Djorgovski (1993)
Distance Modulus, $(m - M)_V$	13.97	Harris (1996)
Distance Modulus, $(m - M)_V$	13.27	van Leeuwen et al. (2000)
Distance Modulus, $(m - M)_V$	14.05	Thompson et al. (2001)
From the Sun	4.9 kpc	Peterson (1993)
From the Sun	5.1 kpc	Harris (1996)
From the Sun	4.5 kpc	van Leeuwen et al. (2000)
From the Sun	5.4 kpc	Thompson et al. (2001)
From the Galactic Plane	1.3 kpc	Djorgovski (1993)
From the Galactic Center	6.3 kpc	Djorgovski (1993)

Table 2.3: Positional data for ω Cen from the literature.

2.2 Position, Distance and Orbit

Let us now review the available data on the position and distance. ω Cen is clearly visible in the southern sky with the naked eye, its equatorial coordinates being ($\alpha_{J2000} = 13^h26^m45.89^s$; $\delta_{J2000} = -47^\circ28'36.7''$). Table 2.3 summarizes the various positional parameters that appeared in the literature.

The distance to ω Cen deserves a short discussion. One of the first modern determinations was the one by Noble et al. (1991), giving one of the largest published values of the visual distance modulus: $(m - M)_V = 14.29 \pm 0.18$. The compilation by Harris (1996) reports instead a much lower value of $(m - M)_V = 13.97$, based on the RR Lyræ study by Butler, Dickens & Epps (1978), which is in close agreement with other values reported, e.g. by Djorgovski (1993). However, two of the most recent determinations give somewhat contradictory answers. Thompson et al. (2001), based on the infrared versus surface brightness of the eclipsing binary OGLE 17, obtained a larger distance modulus of $(m - M)_V = 14.05 \pm 0.11$, corresponding to 5360 ± 300 pc, while van Leeuwen et al. (2000), based on the comparison of radial velocity and proper motion dispersions, obtained a lower value of $(m - M)_V = 13.27$, or 4.5 kpc.

Summarizing, we could (acritically) say that the visual distance modulus of ω Cen goes from a minimum of $(m - M)_V = 13.27$ to a maximum of

$(m - M)_V = 14.29$, or from a minimum linear distance of $d = 4.5$ kpc to a maximum of $d = 5.4$ kpc approximately. The most extreme values however, especially the lowest one by van Leeuwen et al. (2000), appear largely discrepant with the bulk of the other determinations.

Concerning the proper motion of ω Cen, the latest and largest study by van Leeuwen et al. (2000) obtains a value of ($\mu_x = -3.97 \pm 0.4$ mas yr $^{-1}$; $\mu_y = -4.38 \pm 0.4$ mas yr $^{-1}$), in broad agreement with the previous results by Dinescu, Girard & van Altena (1999) of ($\mu_x = -5.0 \pm 0.4$ mas yr $^{-1}$; $\mu_y = -3.5 \pm 0.4$ mas yr $^{-1}$), but not in so good agreement with the oldest (and possibly outdated) determination by Murray, Candy, & Jones (1965) of ($\mu_x = +0.5 \pm 0.6$ mas yr $^{-1}$; $\mu_y = -7.7 \pm 0.5$ mas yr $^{-1}$).

From proper motions studies like the one by Dinescu, Girard & van Altena (1999) and Dinescu et al. (1999), we learn that ω Cen moves in a strongly retrograde orbit, somewhat eccentric ($e = 0.67$), but fundamentally confined to the Galactic plane ($z_{max} = 1$ kpc), with an apocentric radius of 6 kpc. Its orbit is also quite anomalous in its total energy and orbital angular momentum plane if compared to the other GGCs. Thus, ω Cen is presently close to its apogalacticon, being 6.3 kpc away from the Galaxy Center and 4.9 kpc from the sun (Peterson, 1993). According to Dinescu et al. (1999), given its long and complex chemical evolutionary history (Section 2.6), it is difficult to believe that ω Cen originated in its present orbit: with a period of only 120 Myr it would have been swept of all its gas soon after its formation. Thus, ω Cen could be the result of an accretion event where a dwarf galaxy, possibly containing also the clusters NGC 362 and NGC 6779 (M 56), which show similar orbital characteristics, was slowly peeled off its globular cluster and halo population in subsequent interactions with the Galaxy disk (see also Dinescu, 2002, where stars in the local neighborhood are examined in the search for the ω Cen stream).

2.3 Structure and Shape

The parameters describing the morphology and structure of ω Cen are summarized in Table 2.4. All of the reviewed determinations of the core (r_c), half-mass (r_h) and tidal (r_t) radii are generally derived without taking into account the fact that ω Cen is much more flattened than the usual GGC, and thus should be considered as representative values, averaged on the position angle (Merritt, Meylan & Mayor, 1997).

Structure and Shape of ω Cen		
Core radius, r_c , in arcmin	2.58	Trager, King & Djorgovski (1995)
Core radius, r_c , in arcmin	1.40	van Leeuwen et al. (2000)
Core radius, r_c , in pc	3.96	Webbink (1985)
Core radius, r_c , in pc	4.09	Richer et al. (1991)
Core radius, r_c , in pc	3.72	Djorgovski (1993)
Core radius, r_c , in pc	3.75	Pryor & Meylan (1993)
Concentration, $c = \log r_t/r_c$	1.15	Webbink (1985)
Concentration, $c = \log r_t/r_c$	1.33	Richer et al. (1991)
Concentration, $c = \log r_t/r_c$	1.24	Trager, King & Djorgovski (1995)
Concentration, $c = \log r_t/r_c$	1.61	van Leeuwen et al. (2000)
Half-mass radius, r_h , in arcmin	4.80	Mandushev, Spasova & Staneva (1991)
Half-mass radius, r_h , in arcmin	4.18	Harris (1996)
Half-mass radius, r_h , in pc	6.92	Djorgovski (1993)
Half-mass radius, r_h , in pc	8.85	Trager, King & Djorgovski (1995)
Tidal radius, r_t , in arcmin	44.8	Trager, King & Djorgovski (1995)
Tidal radius, r_t , in arcmin	51.0	Meylan et al. (1995)
Tidal radius, r_t , in arcmin	57.0	van Leeuwen et al. (2000)
Tidal radius, r_t , in pc	65.7	Webbink (1985)
Tidal radius, r_t , in pc	87.4	Richer et al. (1991)
Tidal radius, r_t , in pc	64.6	Leon, Meylan & Combes (2000)
Ellipticity ϵ	0.17	White & Shawl (1987)
Average Ellipticity $\langle \epsilon \rangle$	0.12	Geyer, Nelles & Hopp (1983)

Table 2.4: Structural and morphological description of ω Cen. The directly measured quantities (in arcminutes) are presented as well as some derived determinations (in pc) from different sources.

Table 2.4 summarizes many different literature determinations, with different methods and precisions, so we would like to stress here that for r_c and c the literature values agree pretty much on values close to the ones by Djorgovski (1993), Pryor & Meylan (1993) or Trager, King & Djorgovski (1995), while the discrepant values of Richer et al. (1991) and van Leeuwen et al. (2000) have to be considered more like exceptions to the commonly accepted values. As far as r_h and r_t are concerned, the determinations are more uncertain. In fact, while r_t is intrinsically much more difficult to measure, r_h is most cases derived from the half-light radius with semi-empirical formulaes (see Djorgovski, 1993; Harris, 1996) that add some uncertainty. These estimates should simply be taken as indicative values.

Anyway, according to the figures presented in Table 2.4, ω Cen can be described as quite an extended cluster (being also relatively close to us, it appears larger than the full moon) and not much concentrated: its c parameter is $c = 1.24$, an average value if compared with other GGC (Trager, King & Djorgovski, 1995), and thus quite far from core collapse conditions.

As far as the shape of ω Cen is concerned, we already stated that the cluster is among the most flattened GC of the Galaxy. The earliest, visual and non-objective determinations of the ellipticity ($\epsilon = 1 - b/a$ with b and a representing the minor and major axes of the apparent isophotes, respectively) were obtained by Kholopov (1953), Lindsay (1956), Dickens & Woolley (1967) and Frenk & Fall (1982), with very different methods.

A more objective and modern set of measurements was obtained by Geyer, Nelles & Hopp (1983) as a function of radius between $1.4'$ and $28'$ from the cluster center, through photographic photometry. The average resulting value is $\langle \epsilon \rangle = 0.121$, but ϵ actually varies from a minimum very close to zero at the center, to a maximum of $\epsilon_{max} = 0.25$ around $10'$ from the center, and then declines smoothly going outwards. We anticipate here that the behaviour of ϵ is very similar to that of the rotational velocity v_{rot} (Section 2.4). This similarity has led to the interpretation that the flattening of ω Cen is indeed due to its high degree of rotation. To conclude, the position angle of the isophotes does not seem to change significantly with the radius, as stated by Geyer, Nelles & Hopp (1983), with the cluster roughly elongated along the E-W direction. Similar results were later obtained by White & Shawl (1987) in their compilation of axial ratios and orientations for 100 GGC.

The structure and shape of ω Cen will be discussed in detail in Chapters 3 and 6, and some more discussion of its internal kinematics, based on proper motions, can be found in Chapter 5. All of the collected evidence from the literature and from this Thesis work will then be discussed in Chapter 9.

2.4 Kinematics, Dynamics and Mass

From the dynamical point of view, many different studies have been published on ω Cen, starting with the pioneering work by Harding (1965), who first noticed the systemic rotation, one of the most interesting characteristics of ω Cen. Later, the complete dynamical description of the velocity field of ω Cen was obtained through several different studies (Seitzer, 1983; Meylan & Mayor, 1986; Meylan, 1987; Meylan et al., 1995; Merritt, Meylan & Mayor, 1997). In particular, Seitzer (1983) gave the first precise estimates of the rotational velocity, with a maximum of $v_{rot} = 7.7 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ at $\sim 11'$ from the center, of the velocity dispersion, starting from $\sigma_v = 16 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ at the center and decreasing to $\simeq 3 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ in the most external parts, and of the total mass of the cluster, $M = 2.8 \times 10^6 M_{\odot}$ corresponding to a mass-to-light ratio

Dynamics of ω Cen		
Central density, in $M_{\odot} pc^{-3}$	2679	Richer et al. (1991)
Central density, in $M_{\odot} pc^{-3}$	3162	Pryor & Meylan (1993)
Central density, in $M_{\odot} pc^{-3}$	2110	Merritt, Meylan & Mayor (1997)
Max rotation, v_{rot} , in $km s^{-1}$ @ $11'$	7.7	Seitzer (1983)
Max rotation, v_{rot} , in $km s^{-1}$ @ $7'$	7.9	Merritt, Meylan & Mayor (1997)
Central dispersion σ_v , in $km s^{-1}$	16.7	Seitzer (1983)
Central dispersion σ_v , in $km s^{-1}$	22	Meylan et al. (1995)
Central dispersion σ_v , in $km s^{-1}$	17	Merritt, Meylan & Mayor (1997)
Central dispersion σ_{μ} , in $km s^{-1}$	25÷29	van Leeuwen et al. (2000)
Central dispersion σ_{μ} , in $mas yr^{-1}$	1.0÷1.2	van Leeuwen et al. (2000)
External dispersion σ_v , in $km s^{-1}$	3	Seitzer (1983)
External dispersion σ_v , in $km s^{-1}$	5	Merritt, Meylan & Mayor (1997)
External dispersion σ_{μ} , in $km s^{-1}$	7.5	van Leeuwen et al. (2000)
External dispersion σ_{μ} , in $mas yr^{-1}$	0.3	van Leeuwen et al. (2000)
Total mass, M, in $10^6 M_{\odot}$	2.8	Seitzer (1983)
Total mass, M, in $10^6 M_{\odot}$	2.4	Mandushev, Spasova & Staneva (1991)
Total mass, M, in $10^6 M_{\odot}$	7.0	Richer et al. (1991)
Total mass, M, in $10^6 M_{\odot}$	4.0	Pryor & Meylan (1993)
Total mass, M, in $10^6 M_{\odot}$	5.0	Meylan et al. (1995)
Total mass, M, in $10^6 M_{\odot}$	2.9	Merritt, Meylan & Mayor (1997)
Mass-to-light ratio, M/L (solar)	2.6	Seitzer (1983)
Mass-to-light ratio, M/L (solar)	3.6	Pryor & Meylan (1993)
Mass-to-light ratio, M/L (solar)	4	Meylan et al. (1995)
Relaxation Time $\log t_{rc}$, in <i>Gyr</i>	9.58	Webbink (1985)
Relaxation Time $\log t_{rc}$, in <i>Gyr</i>	9.76	Djorgovski (1993)
Relaxation Time $\log t_{rc}$, in <i>Gyr</i>	9.73	Harris (1996)
Relaxation Time $\log t_{rh}$, in <i>Gyr</i>	9.72	Djorgovski (1993)
Relaxation Time $\log t_{rh}$, in <i>Gyr</i>	10.00	Djorgovski (1993)

Table 2.5: Dynamical description of ω Cen.

of $M/L = 2.6$ in solar units.

The following studies added more precision without substantially altering this picture (see Table 2.5). There were claims of a strong mass segregation and strong velocity anisotropy, based on a large and accurate sample of radial velocities by Meylan (1987) and Meylan et al. (1995), and resulting in somewhat larger values of all of the above parameters. However, updated theoretical models, leading to a simpler description of the same dataset based on single-mass models (Merritt, Meylan & Mayor, 1997), showed how no strong radial velocity anisotropy and mass segregation (see also Anderson, 1997, 2002) were needed to explain the velocity field of the cluster, while leaving the conclusions on the rotational velocity and velocity dispersion substantially untouched (updated values are reported in Table 2.5). Unfortunately, the question of the exact amount of needed anisotropy appears not completely settled yet, as discussed by King & Anderson (2002) and Ashurov & van Leeuwen (2002), who reached somewhat conflicting conclusions.

Figure 2.4: The complete characterization of the line-of-sight rotational velocity field (left panels) and of the line-of-sight velocity dispersion (right panels) from Merritt, Meylan & Mayor (1997). Upper panels show the two-dimensional distribution of measured stars (tiny dots) in the sky (East is left and North is up). Overimposed on the upper panels are radial velocity contours, labelled in km s^{-1} (upper left panel) and radial velocity dispersion contours, also labelled in km s^{-1} (upper right panel). The lower panels show the radial velocity as a function of radius (lower left panel) and the radial velocity dispersion as a function of radius (lower right panel).

The most updated results concerning the velocity field of ω Cen are summarized in Figure 2.4 by Merritt, Meylan & Mayor (1997). The rotation is approximately solid-body, up to a maximum of $\sim 8 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ at $\sim 7'$ from the center, while at larger radii the data do not allow stringent constraints. Given the large relaxation times in ω Cen, this rotation most probably reflects the initial conditions of the cluster (as confirmed by Davoust & Prugniel, 1990). In particular, we recall that the ellipticity and rotational velocity behaviour with the distance from the center are quite similar (section 2.3), so that the large flattening of ω Cen can be explained mostly with its high degree of rotation.

However, ω Cen appears still dominated by random motions (Meylan, 2002), since the ratio v_o/σ_o , between the mean rotational velocity and the mean random motions goes from 0.35 to 0.39, depending on the assumptions on the inclination angle i (from 90° to 60° , according to Meylan & Mayor, 1986). More recent estimates of $i \sim 45^\circ$ (van Leeuwen et al., 2000) do not alter this conclusion. All of the above conclusions on rotation and random motions, derived from radial velocity studies, are generally confirmed by the

proper motion study by van Leeuwen et al. (2000).

The relaxation timescales have been estimated by a few different authors like Webbink (1985), Djorgovski (1993), Trager, King & Djorgovski (1995) and Harris (1996). A prescription to estimate $\log t_{rc}$ (the relaxation timescale in the core) and $\log t_{rh}$ (the relaxation timescale at half-mass) can be found in Djorgovski (1993). While the estimates of $\log t_{rc}$ by different authors are generally in good agreement with each other, Harris (1996) has adopted a more updated formula for computing $\log t_{rh}$ that gives more satisfactory (and longer) timescales (see Table 2.5). In any case, in ω Cen both relaxation times are quite large for a globular cluster, confirming the picture emerging from the above literature summary, that ω Cen is a dynamically young cluster, still preserving much of its original characteristics.

Finally, given its orbit close to the Galactic disk, ω Cen is subject even more than other GGC to dynamical interaction with the Galaxy itself. Disk and bulge shocking and tidal interactions are the cause for the loss of most external stars in GGCs, producing the so-called *tidal tails*, i.e., streams of stars that cannot be considered bound to the cluster any more, although they keep relatively close to the cluster in its orbit. An evident pair of tidal tails has been found around ω Cen by Leon, Meylan & Combes (2000), extending to ~ 5 tidal radii or more. It is estimated that $\sim 1\%$ of the total cluster mass has been removed in the last disk-shocking episode. The observed tidal tail is in perfect agreement with the simulations performed by Combes, Leon & Meylan (1999). The presence of tidal-tails around GGC has been used (Moore, 1996) to put stringent constraints to the maximum amount of their dark matter content. In the case of ω Cen, the presence of the tidal tail is consistent with the low mass-to-light ratios found (Table 2.5).

2.5 The Metallicity Distribution

The most studied characteristic of ω Cen is its wide metallicity spread, together with the detailed chemical composition. The typical GGCs have a very small metallicity spread, of about 0.1 dex (Suntzeff, 1993; Stetson, 1993), entirely due to measurement errors, with the possible exception of M 22 (Hesser, Hartwick & McClure, 1977; Norris & Freeman, 1983). ω Cen shows instead a spread of at least 1 dex, i.e., one order of magnitude larger than the typical globular.

The wide RGB shown by the very first photometries of ω Cen was very soon interpreted as due to an intrinsic metallicity spread of the heavy elements

(e.g., Dickens & Woolley, 1967; Cannon & Stobie, 1973). In fact, it was soon clear that no strong differential reddening was present on the field of ω Cen. Cannon (1980) proved that no nebulosity or patchy obscuration was present, reporting on the presence of only a very thin filament ~ 2 deg to the West of ω Cen. Absence of dense interstellar matter in the region of ω Cen is confirmed by reddening maps (Burstein & Heiles, 1982; Schlegel, Finkbeiner & Davis, 1998). A recent ISOCAM study of a few GGC (Origlia et al., 2002b) confirms the absence of interstellar gas within ω Cen, except of course for the very faint emission surrounding stars at the RGB and Asymptotic Giant Branch (AGB) tip.

The first spectroscopic studies confirmed the idea that differential reddening could not be the main source of the color dispersion. Butler, Dickens & Epps (1978) performed a vast survey of the RR Lyræ in ω Cen, obtaining metallicities in the full range $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -2.2 \div -0.6^1$. Similar metallicity dispersions have also been found by Persson et al. (1980), studying the infrared ($V, V - K$) photometry of 82 red giants, and the color dispersion typical of the RGB has also been found at the Main Sequence (MS) level (Cannon & Stewart, 1981).

In particular, the low resolution surveys of a several hundreds of stars conducted by Norris, Freeman & Mighell (1996) and Suntzeff & Kraft (1996), based on the H and K and on the infrared triplet Ca II lines as metallicity indicators, have revealed the following facts concerning the metallicity distribution of ω Cen, confirming earlier findings:

- There are very few stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.8$;
- There is an evident peak in the distribution, at $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \simeq -1.6$;
- There is a secondary peak, which is most probably a real feature of the metallicity distribution, around $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \simeq -1.0 \div -1.2$;
- There is a long, asymmetric tail extending to higher metallicity values, such as $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -0.5$.

The results above are beautifully summarized in the $[\text{Ca}/\text{H}]$ metallicity distribution obtained with more than 500 red giants by Norris, Freeman & Mighell (1996), shown in Figure 2.5. The relative shift of $0.2 \div 0.4$ dex between

¹Throughout the Thesis, we will indicate chemical abundances by using the so-called *bracket notation*, where $[\text{El}/\text{H}] = \log[(\text{El}/\text{H})/(\text{El}/\text{H})_{\odot}]$. With this formalism, for example, $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -1.0$ corresponds to 1/10 of the solar iron abundance.

Figure 2.5: Metallicity distribution in $[Ca/H]$, obtained from the analysis of more than 500 low resolution spectra by Norris, Freeman & Mighell (1996). The metallicity distribution is clearly bimodal with a smaller, secondary peak around $[Ca/H] \simeq -1.0$.

the $[Fe/H]$ and the $[Ca/H]$ distributions has to be expected since normal halo and globular cluster stars do show an α -enhancement of about that value (Norris & Da Costa, 1995a), but we will discuss more about the α -enhancement in ω Cen in Chapters 4 and 9.

A comparison of the metallicity distributions found by Suntzeff & Kraft (1996) with the predictions of the “Simple Model” built by Searle & Sargent (1972) and parametrized according to Hartwick (1976) and Pagel (1992), shows that a good agreement with the data can only be obtained if *two generations of stars* are assumed, with a maximum initial metallicity dispersion of 0.07 dex (i.e., the observational error) in the primordial cloud. In particular, it was impossible to reproduce the metal-rich tail with only *one* generation of stars, while the very sharp cut-off at low metallicities ($[Fe/H] \leq -1.8 \div -2.0$) imposed that the original gas cloud was chemically homogeneous.

This situation was further confirmed by Norris, Freeman & Mighell (1996), who were in particular unable to reproduce their secondary peak unless they used two different stellar populations. They concluded, however, that they were unable to distinguish if the two populations had to be formed in different epochs (Morgan & Lake, 1989) or in different locations in space (Searle, 1977). They just discarded the latter possibility on the basis of the low probability

Figure 2.6: The splitting of the main sequence of ω Cen found by Anderson (2002) with a deep HST photometry. The left panel shows the $V, (V - I)$ CMD of the lower MS. The central panel shows the “straightened” sequence, obtained by plotting the color difference, ΔC , of each star from the mean MS ridge line. The right panel shows histograms of ΔC in selected magnitude slices. A secondary sequence on the *right* side of the main MS is clearly seen.

of merging episodes between globular clusters, and on the fact that anyway the two clusters involved in the merger needed both to originally possess an anomalously large metallicity spread. Suntzeff & Kraft (1996) also noted that the metal-rich component was more centrally concentrated than the metal-poor one, a fact that they considered compatible with a dissipative self-enriching formation scenario.

Recent efforts have been made to derive photometric MDF, based on the fact that the statistics are increased from a few hundreds to a few thousands of stars, although at the expense of some accuracy in the metallicity determinations. Examples of such works are Hilker & Richtler (2000) and Frinchaboy et al. (2002). They generally confirm what obtained by Norris, Freeman & Mighell (1996) and Suntzeff & Kraft (1996), although they show the presence of a very small low metallicity tail (a few % of the total number of stars) extending below $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \simeq -2.0$, that was missing from the spectroscopic samples.

Also, very recent work presented by Anderson (2002), based on deep multi-epoch extensive HST photometry, shows how the MS of ω Cen appears splitted

into two components, implying a metallicity distribution which is very hard to reconcile with the spectroscopic and photometric results presented above. In particular, the secondary sequence, which is much less populated than the main MS, appears to the *right side* of the bulk MS. Isochrone fittings suggest that these stars, if belonging to the cluster, should be more *metal-poor* than the bulk MS of ω Cen, in some contradiction with the above findings.

Although this Thesis does not deal with the study of the MDF of ω Cen, this is a very valuable constraint to the formation and evolution history of ω Cen. The future observations described in Chapter 9 will also attempt to tackle this problem, trying to derive the first MDF for a few hundred RGB, SGB and HB stars in ω Cen with high-resolution ($R \geq 20,000$) spectroscopy.

2.6 Abundance Patterns and Enrichment Timescales

While the above observations alone are enough to state that the history of formation and evolution of ω Cen must have been different from that of the typical GC in the Milky Way, other puzzling evidence concerning the chemical composition was collected with medium and high-resolution studies of RGB and SGB stars in ω Cen during the years. A short summary of the results is presented below, separating the different elements in families, according to their putative production sites.

2.6.1 The Anti-Correlations Phenomenon

Most of the early studies (Bessell & Norris, 1976; Norris & Bessell, 1978; Cohen, 1981; Mallia & Pagel, 1981; Gratton, 1982; François, Spite & Spite, 1988; Paltoglou & Norris, 1989, and many others) concentrated on the attempt to precisely measure the abundance spread and on the so-called abundance anomalies or anti-correlations. While the problem of the abundance spread was solved with the derivation of the first populous MDF described in Section 2.5, the study of the anti-correlations in GGC greatly benefited from these works. ω Cen was infact one of the first clusters in which such anomalies were detected, together with M 22, while nowadays all of the properly observed GGC show some sign of anti-correlation. Such a behaviour is not observed in the field stars, nor in the dwarf galaxies studied with high-resolution spectroscopy so far (Shetrone et al., 2003). The whole problem is described in the reviews by Kraft (1994), Da Costa (1998) and Sneden (1999). In short, the most commonly observed anti-correlations are the one between CH and CN (i.e.,

stars that possess strong CH bands have very weak CN bands and vice versa), the one between Na and O and the one between Al and Mg.

More recent studies (Norris & Da Costa, 1995a; Smith et al., 2000) addressed in some detail the problem of the (very pronounced) anti-correlations found in ω Cen, using a fair number of high-quality spectra of red giants, and with the help of additional stellar mixing indicators like $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C}$. In fact, these puzzling correlations were in the past explained as a sign of mixing episodes inside stellar interiors (Sweigart & Mengel, 1979; Smith & Tout, 1992), dredging up the altered compositions of CNO-cycle and CN-cycle processed material to the stellar surface.

However, more recently, the anti-correlations have been also observed in TO stars in, e.g., 47 Tuc (Cannon et al., 1998) and M 71 (Cohen, 1999): stars at the TO level have not undergone any significant mixing episode yet, since the so-called first dredge-up happens at the beginning of the RGB. Moreover, the anti-correlations between Al and Mg, appear very likely due to the $^{24}\text{Mg}(p,\gamma)^{25}\text{Al}$ reaction, occurring in the hot interiors of AGB stars, and is thus incompatible with the low temperatures of the low mass MS stars under study.

The current explanations thus point more towards a combination of mixing episodes and, possibly, primordial pollution (or accretion on the stars surfaces) from AGB stars ejecta (Bell et al., 1981; Denissenkov, Weiss & Wagenhuber, 1997; Ventura et al., 2001), although a definite and quantitative answer to this problem has not been given yet. More important, it is not clear why the anti-correlations have been found only in GGC and *not* in other environments. The problem of pollution by AGB stars is particularly interesting in the case of ω Cen, as described in Section 2.6.2 and further discussed in Chapters 4 and 9.

Up to now, no star at the TO level has been studied in ω Cen, so the anti-correlation phenomenon has not been observed yet in that region of the CMD. However, we will show some new results concerning this point in Chapter 8.

2.6.2 The Anomalous *s*-process Elements Enhancement

Dickens & Bell (1976) and Lloyd Evans (1983) were among the first to show that some of the reddest stars to the right of the RGB, that appeared to be members of ω Cen, were extremely rich in Ba, ZrO and other heavy elements like Y, Zr, La, Ce, Nd, Rb and so on. These elements are mainly produced by “slow” (hence the *s* in the name) neutron capture reactions, i.e., slower

than the typical β -decay times, as opposed to the “rapid” neutron capture r -processes. The s -processes are known to happen mostly during the mixing episodes that happen between the two burning shells of AGB stars (see Busso, Gallino & Wasserburg, 1999; Busso et al., 2001, and references therein). The stars observed by Lloyd Evans (1983) were not bright enough to be AGB stars, and showed no sign of binarity, so the hypothesis was made, that the s -process enrichment must have been *primordial*, by a previous generation of AGB stars. Another possibility is that the gas from AGB stars has been *accreted* onto the surfaces of forming stars (see Ventura et al., 2001, and references therein).

Later studies (see e.g., Norris & Da Costa, 1995b; Smith, Cunha & Lambert, 1995; Vanture, Wallerstein & Brown, 1994; Smith et al., 2000; Vanture, Wallerstein & Suntzeff, 2002) confirmed that s -process elements are generally 10 times more overabundant with respect to iron in ω Cen than in typical GGCs, and that the $[s/Fe]$ abundance ratios are steeply rising with $[Fe/H]$. In a critical compilation of the highest quality literature data, Smith (2002) showed how the s -process elements overabundance $[s/Fe]$ increases dramatically from $[Fe/H] \simeq -2.0$ to $[Fe/H] \simeq -1.5$ and then possibly flattens out, or at least slows down, exactly where the secondary peak in the MDF (Figure 2.5) appears. This has been interpreted as evidence that, at the lowest metallicity end, the heavy elements were contributed also by the r -process while as metallicity increased, the s -process contribution was increasing rapidly up to a point where it was, by far, the dominating source of heavy elements (see Figure 2 in Smith, 2002, and also Figure 4.10 in Chapter 4).

Concerning the anomalous abundance of heavy elements, it is interesting to note here that only one other system shows similarly high s -process elements abundances: the Sagittarius dSph (Smecker-Hane, McWilliam & Ibata, 1998; Smecker-Hane & McWilliam, 2003), a disrupting system that is being right now accreted by the Milky Way. This striking similarity will be further discussed in Chapter 9, in the framework of one of the theories for the likely formation and evolution of ω Cen.

The identification of the exact type of AGB polluting stars has been obtained by comparisons of the detailed chemical abundances of many different elements of certain s -process origin (Vanture, Wallerstein & Brown, 1994; Smith et al., 2000; Vanture, Wallerstein & Suntzeff, 2002) with theoretical models (e.g. Lambert et al., 1995; Straniero et al., 1997; Gallino et al., 1998; Busso et al., 2001). The higher abundance of heavy s -process elements (hs , i.e., Ba, La, Ce etc.) with respect to the light s -process elements (ls , i.e., Y, Zr etc.)

is indicative of a relatively low neutron exposure. This points more towards the $^{13}\text{C}(\alpha,n)^{16}\text{O}$ as the main source of neutron production, which is operating mostly in lower mass ($1.5\div 3.0 M_{\odot}$) AGB stars, while in higher mass ($\sim 5 M_{\odot}$) AGB stars, neutrons are produced mainly by the $^{22}\text{Ne}(\alpha,n)^{25}\text{Mg}$, that would result in higher neutron densities and quite different $[hs/l_s]$ ratios. A similar indication comes from the $[\text{Rb}/\text{Zr}]$ ratio (Vanture, Wallerstein & Suntzeff, 2002; Smith, 2002), which again points towards a lower neutron exposure and low mass AGB stars as the main contributors.

Retaining the AGB ejecta long enough to pollute a forming generation of stars is not impossible, especially if the disk of the Galaxy at that time was not formed yet, as has been demonstrated by Gnedin et al. (2002). It is instead more difficult to reconcile the different evolutionary timescales resulting from different chemical contributors in ω Cen. For example, the evolutionary times of low mass ($1.5\div 3.0 M_{\odot}$) AGB stars are of about $1\div 2$ Gyr (Castellani, Chieffi, & Straniero, 1990), which constitutes a lower limit to the timescale of s -process enrichment in ω Cen. As we will see below, this is somehow in contradiction with the shorter timescales implied by SNe Type II enrichment.

2.6.3 Enrichment by Supernovae

The firm conclusion that all stars in ω Cen (at least up to $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \leq -0.8$) must have been primarily enriched by SNe type II, i.e., by supernovae with massive progenitors that produce mainly α -elements, comes from the well established fact that the α -enhancement appears approximately constant at $[\alpha/\text{Fe}] \sim +0.3 \div 0.4$ (Paltoglou & Norris, 1989; Brown et al., 1991; Brown & Wallerstein, 1993; Norris & Da Costa, 1995a; Smith, Cunha & Lambert, 1995; Smith et al., 2000) with varying $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$. This fact alone would be enough to conclude that no SNe type Ia have contributed to the enrichment of these stars, at least in the metallicity regimes studied so far, which is approximately $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \leq -0.8$.

Several attempts have been made to estimate the fractions of the fast SNe type II ejecta retained by ω Cen, to produce such an abundance spread, starting with the work of Brown & Wallerstein (1993), who estimated that a total iron mass of $\sim 150 \div 250 M_{\odot}$ must have been retained by the cluster, implying that the ejecta of about ~ 700 SNe II are needed to explain the observed iron spread, if we start from an initial iron abundance of $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -2.3$. Since the total number of SNe II that exploded in ω Cen must have been much higher than that, ω Cen has been *extremely inefficient*

in retaining these ejecta. This was also taken as a supporting evidence to the lack of SNe Ia enrichment, since the ejecta from these stars are even more energetic and generally explode in a lower density medium, already swept by previous generations of supernovae (Recchi, Matteucci, & D’Ercole, 2001). More precise and modern back-of-the-envelope calculation of the same type have been also performed, e.g., by Hilker & Richtler (2000), who estimated that only some $\sim 3\%$ of the SNe type II ejecta needed to be retained to produce the metallicity that we observe today.

The timescale of the pollution due to these massive stars is thought to be extremely short (≤ 1 Gyr), so the hypothesis was made that ω Cen reached $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -0.8$ in such a short time (i.e., a burst). However, as stated in Section 2.6.2, this short enrichment period is in contradiction with the much longer timescales needed to achieve the AGB pollution described above. A possible way out this problem can be represented by the alternative hypothesis of accretion of AGB ejecta directly on the surface of stars (Ventura et al., 2001).

The idea that SNe Ia did not contribute to the enrichment of stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \leq -0.8$ was further reinforced by the abundances of two key elements, Europium and Copper. Europium is the only pure r -process element that can be measured in these cool red giants, through the hyperfine splitted 6645 Å line, which is also quite weak. Since the r -process production site, although still debated, is almost certainly associated with SNe type II (Truran et al., 2002), Eu is the perfect SNe II tracer. Only high-quality datasets allow the precise measurement of this feature, like the ones by Smith, Cunha & Lambert (1995) and Smith et al. (2000), who found a fairly flat $[\text{Eu}/\text{Fe}]$ ratio, which is constant with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$, confirming that SNe II are the main contributors to the iron-peak and α -elements enrichment in ω Cen, at least up to $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \leq -0.8$.

Cu (and Mn) have been studied only recently, since an accurate measurement requires hyperfine structure, and good quality data. The $[\text{Mn}/\text{Fe}]$ (Gratton, 1989; McWilliam et al., 1995) and $[\text{Cu}/\text{Fe}]$ (Snedden, Gratton, & Crocker, 1991; Cunha et al., 2002) trends with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$, for the Galaxy, show a mirror behaviour with respect to that of the α -elements, i.e. they start to rise when the α -elements start to decrease ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -0.1$). This has been interpreted as a signature that their main production sites must reside in SNe type Ia (Matteucci et al., 1993; Cunha et al., 2002), making them promising SNe Ia tracers. However, some debate is still going on concerning the suggestion by Woosley & Weaver (1995) that the yields of Cu and Mn may be metallicity dependent (see Shetrone et al., 2003, for a deeper discussion).

Figure 2.7: The radial velocities from Mayor et al. (1997) have been plotted for red giants with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \leq -1.2$ (top panel) and $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \geq -1.2$ (bottom panel) as a function of the position angle (Norris et al., 1997). While a clear rotation is evident for the metal-poor group, no sign of rotation could be found for the metal-rich group.

In ω Cen, while Mn is not well studied, Cu has been observed by both Smith et al. (2000) and Cunha et al. (2002), resulting in a flat and constant $[\text{Cu}/\text{Fe}] \simeq -0.6$, perfectly consistent with no contribution by SNe Ia for stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \leq -0.8$. Above that metallicity, we will show some new results in Chapter 4 for both the α -elements and Copper, and these results will be discussed in Chapter 9 together with the other results from the literature and the present Thesis.

2.7 Correlations Between Chemical and Kinematical Properties

To further complicate the emerging picture, some puzzling correlations between kinematical and chemical properties have been found in ω Cen. The first such report is from Freeman (1985), who noticed that CN-strong stars showed a velocity dispersion decreasing more rapidly with radius than the CN-weak stars. Also, the CN-weak stars showed a large systemic rotation. Later, Norris et al. (1997) correlated their large sample (Norris & Da Costa, 1995a; Norris, Freeman & Mighell, 1996) of spectroscopic abundance determinations for ω Cen's red giants with the radial velocity catalog by Mayor et al. (1997).

Figure 2.8: The radial velocity dispersion is plotted as a function of $[Ca/H]$ (Norris et al., 1997). Clearly, the dispersion appears to decrease with increasing metallicity.

They obtained two main results. The first one concerns the rotational velocity, v_{rot} , and is illustrated in Figure 2.7. The red giants have been divided into two groups with $[Fe/H] \leq -1.2$ and $[Fe/H] \geq -1.2$. The radial velocities have been plotted as a function of the position angle for the two groups separately, showing quite clearly how the metal-poor group exhibits the well known systemic rotation of about $\sim 8 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, while the metal-rich group shows no sign of it.

The second result from Norris et al. (1997) concerns the radial velocity dispersion, σ_v , and it is illustrated in Figure 2.8. It is evident that stars with higher metallicity tend to have a lower σ_v with respect to stars with lower metallicity. The two pieces of evidence match perfectly the previous findings by Freeman (1985). The velocity dispersion effect is even more puzzling if one considers the fact that the metal-rich stars are mostly concentrated in the central regions of the cluster (Suntzeff & Kraft, 1996; Norris, Freeman & Mighell, 1996), where the system is dynamically hotter² (Meylan & Mayor, 1986; Merritt, Meylan & Mayor, 1997). Possible interpretations of these findings, involving the merging of two separate sub-systems, were proposed by the authors in the framework of the merging within a fragments scenario (Searle, 1977), and will be further discussed in Chapter 9.

To conclude, we cite an even more puzzling observational effect found by Jurcsik (1998). She compiled spectroscopic abundance determinations for RGB

²A possible simple explanation for this particular piece of evidence has been proposed by van den Bosch et al. (1999): the metal-rich stars could be distributed on a disk-like sub-system, seen face-on, that rotates around the line of sight.

Figure 2.9: Spatial distribution of red giants in ω Cen. The two populations lying at the extremes of the metallicity sample collected by Jurcsik (1998) are represented with empty circles ($[Fe/H] > -1.25$) and filled circles ($[Fe/H] < -1.25$). The dashed line represents the minor photometric axis, i.e. the rotation axis of ω Cen. The two populations are clearly segregated to the two sides of the cluster, with a separation of $6.2'$ between the two groups centroids.

stars from the literature, and noticed that the brightest giants belonging to the two extreme metallicity groups ($[Fe/H] \leq -1.75$ and $[Fe/H] \geq -1.25$) showed a weird spatial segregation. Stars of each group occupied preferentially one half of the cluster, with a separation of $6.2'$ between the two group centroids (Figure 2.9). Different interpretations were proposed, but we will further discuss and partially explain the effect in Chapter 6.

Chapter 3

The Complex RGB Structure of ω Cen from High-Quality Color Magnitude Diagrams

In this Chapter we present the wide field optical photometric catalog (partially published in Pancino et al., 2000) and the infrared catalog (Ferraro et al., 2003, in preparation) for ω Cen. These high-quality photometries allow us to study in detail the complex structure of the RGB of ω Cen. The CMD presented here show the presence of multiple, discrete red giant branches, so we propose the photometric definition of three RGB sub-populations: the RGB-MP, the RGB-MInt and the RGB-a (see below). This classification will be used as a basis for the following Chapters.

We also confirm the presence of an additional, anomalous branch (RGB-a – Lee et al., 1999; Pancino et al., 2000), which appears to be well separated from the bulk of the RGB stars. On the basis of the CMDs presented here and from the previous literature, we conclude that (1) these stars, clearly identified as a separate population in our photometries, represent the extreme metal-rich extension ($[\text{Ca}/\text{H}] > -0.3$) of the stellar content of ω Cen, and show anomalous abundances of *s*-process elements (as Ba and Zr) as well; (2) they are physical members of the ω Cen system; (3) they comprise $\sim 5\%$ of the stars of the whole system; (4) this component and the metal-intermediate one ($-0.4 > [\text{Ca}/\text{H}] > -1$) have been found to share the same spatial distribution, both of them differing significantly from the most metal poor one ($[\text{Ca}/\text{H}] < -1$).

Figure 3.1: The X and Y pixel coordinates of the 230,000 stars in the WFI *B*, *V* and *I* catalog. The location of the cluster center (Chip#2) and the gaps between different CCDs in the WFI mosaic are clearly visible. North is up and East is left.

3.1 The Wide Field Optical Photometry

The data have been obtained on January 1999 (Run A) and July 1999 (Run B) at the 2.2m ESO-MPI telescope at La Silla (Chile), using the WFI, which has exceptional imaging capabilities. The imager consists of eight CCD chips, each with a field of view of $\sim 8' \times 16'$, giving a total field of view of $\sim 34' \times 33'$. The cluster was roughly centered on Chip#2 during Run A, and on Chip#3 during Run B. Figure 3.1 shows the spatial distribution of $\sim 230,000$ stars included in the final catalog. The images were taken through the *B* and *V* filters and through I_{853} , a medium band filter (cf. WFI Manual) which avoids the most pronounced atmospheric emission lines.

After applying the standard bias and flat field corrections with the *noao.mscred* package within IRAF¹, we used DAOPHOT II and the psf-fitting algorithm ALLSTAR (Stetson, 1994) to perform accurate stellar photometry. The photometric calibration was performed using 50 photoelectric standard stars in the selected areas SA98 and SA95 (Landolt, 1992). The catalog was

¹Image Reduction and Analysis Facility. IRAF is distributed by the National Optical Astronomy Observatories, which is operated by the association of Universities for Research in Astronomy, Inc., under contract with the National Science Foundation

Figure 3.2: The $B, (B - I)$ CMDs for ω Cen. Eight CMDs are plotted on different panels: one for each of the eight WFI mosaic CCD chips. The cluster center is located on Chip #2. The arrows indicate the anomalous RGB (RGB-a), which is only visible in the central CCD and, to a lesser extent, in the neighboring CCDs.

Figure 3.3: The $V, (B - V)$ CMDs for ω Cen. Eight CMDs are plotted on different panels: one for each of the eight WFI mosaic CCD chips. The cluster center is located on Chip #3. The arrows indicate the anomalous RGB (RGB-a), which is only visible in the central CCD and, to a lesser extent, in the neighboring CCDs.

subsequently astrometrically calibrated using the catalog of accurate positions and proper motions by van Leeuwen et al. (2000) as a reference, and making use of a dedicated software (CataPack) developed at the Bologna Observatory by Paolo Montegriffo.

Figures 3.2 and 3.3 show the resulting B , $(B - I)$ (Pancino et al., 2000) and V , $(B - V)$ (unpublished) CMD containing the $\sim 230,000$ stars that were included into the final catalog. To our knowledge, this is the largest stellar sample ever observed in ω Cen. Most notable is the *complex* structure of the RGB, where an additional sequence, redder than the bulk of the RGB, is marked by arrows. We would also like to point out some complex substructures also at the TO and SGB level, that will be further discussed in Chapter 8. Finally, we would like to note the presence of a large population of HB stars lying below the Zero Age HB level and the unusual width of the HB, that are not further discussed in this Thesis, but will be the subject of the future investigations described at the end of Chapter 9.

3.2 The Infrared Photometric Mapping

The Infrared (IR) data were obtained during two observing runs on January 2000 (Run #1) and December 2001 (Run #2) at the ESO New Technology Telescope (NTT) at La Silla, Chile, equipped with the near-IR imager/spectrometer SOFI. J and K images were observed using a scale of $0.292''/\text{pixel}$, allowing a field of view of $\sim 5' \times 5'$ per exposure. During the two runs, the central regions of ω Cen have been mapped with a total of nine (3×3) overlapping fields, covering a total area of approximately $\sim 13' \times 13'$ (Figure 3.4).

Each of the nine frames, in J and K , was sky-subtracted and flat-field corrected. A set of high S/N flat-fields in each filter have been obtained with a halogen lamp, alternatively switched on and off. Also, a sky-field has been observed (at ~ 10 arcmin from the cluster center) for each scientific exposure, using the same instrumental configuration. Each sky-image was then obtained as the median average of at least 5 frames, shifted by some hundreds of pixel with respect to each other.

All photometric reductions were carried out using ROMAFOT (Buonanno et al., 1983), using a PSF-fitting routine specifically modified to deal with under-sampled stellar images (Buonanno & Iannicola, 1989). The resulting catalog contains a total of $\sim 50,000$ stars.

Figure 3.4: Chart of the spatial distribution of the $\sim 50,000$ stars observed in the IR. The whole area is a mosaic of nine overlapping fields, covering $5' \times 5'$ each.

During Run #2, a set of nine standard stars from the Persson et al. (1998) list have been observed: five measures for each standards have been secured and averaged, per filter. The calibrations linking the aperture photometry to the standard system are:

$$K = k + 22.30 \pm 0.02$$

$$J = j + 23.03 \pm 0.02$$

where j and k are the instrumental magnitudes and J and K the calibrated magnitudes. The existence of a slight residual colour equation (with $a < 0.01$) in both filters cannot be totally excluded. The resulting catalog contains more than 50,000 stars.

Figure 3.5 (left panel) presents the $(K, J - K)$ CMD obtained by plotting the entire IR sample: this is the largest IR data set ever observed for ω Cen. Figure 3.5 (right panel) shows instead one of the optical-IR combined CMDs, obtained by cross-correlating the IR catalog with the WFI catalog presented in section 3.1.

The CMDs sample the entire evolved populations in the cluster, reaching the TO region (approximately at $K \sim 17$). The complex structure of the RGB in ω Cen is fully confirmed by the IR observations. In particular, the

Figure 3.5: The $K, (J - K)$ (top panel) and $K, (B - K)$ (bottom panel) CMDs for ω Cen, covering an area of $\sim 13' \times 13'$ around the cluster center.

presence of the dominant metal poor population it is evident, defining the main RGB (RGB-MP, see Section 3.3 for the sub-populations definitions). Also the anomalous RGB (RGB-a, see below) is clearly seen at the extreme red side of the main population, and an intermediate population (RGB-MInt, see below) which uniformly populates the CMD region between the two components.

The dominant RGB-MP sample is quite well populated and allows a precise measurement of the RGB-Tip, that will be used to extend the calibration of the RGB-Tip method (see Chapter 7) to the IR bands.

3.3 The RGB of ω Cen

The most striking characteristic of the CMDs shown in Figures 3.2 and 3.5 is the presence of a narrow sequence, significantly redder and more bent than the bulk of the “main” RGB stars, which we will call the *anomalous* RGB (hereafter RGB-a). Note that, in the WFI mosaic, the RGB-a is visible only in the CMD where the cluster center is located and to a much lesser extent in the nearby East (left) and possibly West (right) CCDs. (see the arrows in Figure 3.2). We shall come back to the spatial distribution of the RGB stars in Section 3.4 and more extensively in Chapter 6. While we were writing a Letter to ApJ concerning this shocking discovery (Pancino et al., 2000), a $V, (B - V)$ CMD showing the same RGB structure was published by Lee et al. (1999). A few months later than the publication of our ApJ Letter, Strömgren photometries showed the same feature in the RGB of ω Cen: the reality of the RGB-a is thus confirmed by several independent surveys based on different photometric systems.

The morphology of the RGB-a and its position in the CMD strongly suggests that it must be populated by stars much more metal rich than the ω Cen bulk population. We can directly check this hypothesis using the [Ca/H] catalog by Norris, Freeman & Mighell (1996) (kindly provided by J. Norris). We have cross-identified the stars in our catalog and in the Norris, Freeman & Mighell (1996) one, and marked the common stars in Figure 3.6 (top panel) using different symbols for different metallicities (see figure caption).

Six stars belonging to the RGB-a are in common with the Norris, Freeman & Mighell (1996) sample (namely stars ROA 300, ROA 447, ROA 500, ROA 513, ROA 517, ROA 523, adopting the nomenclature of Woolley, 1966): these stars have [Ca/H] = -0.1 ± 0.1 . They are the most metal rich stars in the catalog, though they do not correspond to any of the peaks shown in the

Figure 3.6: *Panel (a)*: Zoom on the upper RGB region. Stars in the RGB-a have been plotted as *small filled triangles*. Large empty symbols show the position of stars with different metallicities (from Norris, Freeman & Mighell, 1996): *open circles* stars with $-1.5 < [\text{Ca}/\text{H}] < -1.3$, *open stars* with $-1.1 < [\text{Ca}/\text{H}] < -0.85$, *open squares* with $-0.65 < [\text{Ca}/\text{H}] < -0.4$, *open triangles* with $[\text{Ca}/\text{H}] > -0.3$. *Panel (b)*: Histogram of the distances from the MP mean ridge line (see text). The mean $[\text{Ca}/\text{H}]$ abundances for the four main RGB components (*panel (a)*) are also marked.

Norris, Freeman & Mighell (1996) [Ca/H] distribution (e.g. their Figure 12). Figure 3.6 suggests that the RGB-a represents an *additional*, very metal rich component, located at the extreme end of the abundance distribution in ω Cen. Moreover, the large color baseline of the present survey allows us to clearly separate the most metal rich component from the remaining ω Cen RGB stars and, thus, to estimate its contribution to the *global* population of the cluster. By comparing the star counts along the RGB, in the same magnitude range ($B < 16$), we find that the RGB-a represents $\sim 5\%$ of the whole stellar content of ω Cen. It is important to note that the six RGB-a stars for which we know the radial velocities from the Mayor et al. (1997) catalog (kindly provided by G. Meylan) have $v_{rad} = 233 \pm 9$ km s $^{-1}$. This value is fully compatible with the mean value $\langle v_{rad} \rangle = 233 \pm 17$ km s $^{-1}$ for the 471 stars in the Mayor et al. (1997) catalog, showing that the RGB-a stars are indeed members of the ω Cen system (Lloyd Evans, 1983).

To further investigate the distribution of the RGB stars in the CMD, we computed the distance of each of them from the Mean Ridge Line (MRL) of the main metal poor component in several magnitude bins. The MRL has been obtained following the procedure described in Ferraro et al. (1999a). A preliminary selection of the stars belonging to the bluest ridge of the RGB (excluding HB, AGB, and the reddest RGB components) has initially been performed by eye. Then we fitted the selected stars with polynomials, and the procedure was iterated, rejecting all stars at $> 2\sigma$ from the best fit line, until the result was considered acceptable. In doing this, we used the $I, (B - I)$ CMD, since in this plane the upper part of the RGB is less bent than in $B, (B - I)$, and a low order polynomial excellently reproduces the RGB shape.

Then we defined the observable δx as the geometrical distance of each star from the adopted MRL. The distribution of δx for the RGB stars in the magnitude range $11.9 < I < 12.5$ is plotted in Figure 3.6 (bottom panel). Positive and negative values of δx are assumed for stars redder and bluer than the MRL, respectively. The distribution is clearly asymmetric; besides the main peak, secondary peaks are well visible. The estimated typical [Ca/H] abundances for the different components are marked. Four different components can be identified in Figure 3.6. They can be grouped in three main samples as follows:

- **RGB-MP** for the most metal poor component, at [Ca/H] ~ -1.4 , comprising $\sim 75\%$ of the whole RGB population;

Figure 3.7: The definition of the three RGB sub-populations in ω Cen, as described in Section 3.3. This catalogation of the sub-populations in ω Cen constitutes the basis of the analysis presented in the following Chapters.

- **RGB-MInt** for the metal intermediate component, comprising $\sim 25\%$ of the whole RGB population: this sample includes the secondary peak ($\delta x \sim 0.08$) in Figure 3.6, which corresponds to $[\text{Ca}/\text{H}] \sim -1.0$, and the metal rich tail ($\delta x \sim 0.2 - 0.3$), extending to $[\text{Ca}/\text{H}] \sim -0.5$;
- **RGB-a** for the extreme metal rich component, at $\delta x \sim 0.4$ in Figure 3.6, i.e. $[\text{Ca}/\text{H}] \sim -0.05$, clearly separated from the other stellar populations, comprising $\sim 5\%$ of the whole RGB population.

The first two components correspond to the peaks visible in Figure 12 by Norris, Freeman & Mighell (1996), while the RGB-a is a third, new component of the stellar population of ω Cen (Lee et al., 1999). The definition of these three RGB sub-populations is further illustrated in Figure 3.7, and will be used throughout the rest of this Thesis as a powerful classification that will enable us to understand more deeply the properties of ω Cen.

To better describe the characteristics of the “multiple” ω Cen RGB in terms of the “classical” abundance parameter $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$, we used a set of 60 giants in our sample which have both $[\text{Ca}/\text{H}]$ (from Norris, Freeman & Mighell, 1996) and $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ abundances (from Suntzeff & Kraft, 1996, kindly provided by N. Suntzeff). From these, we derived an empirical relation linking the calcium abundance to iron, in terms of $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ on the Zinn & West (1984) scale. The procedure yields the following results for the four peaks labeled in Figure 3.6: $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]_{ZW} \sim -1.7, -1.3, -0.8$ and -0.4 , respectively.

It is interesting to note that the spectra of the six metal rich stars quoted above exhibit strong Ba II lines, and the brightest three (namely ROA 300, ROA 447 and ROA 513) show also strong ZrO bands (Lloyd Evans, 1983), a very unusual occurrence for globular cluster giants. The fact that high metallicity giants have strong Ba lines fully agrees with the increase of the *s*-process element to iron ratio with metallicity found by Norris & Da Costa (1995a) and described in Sectionsec-met, and suggests that intermediate mass ($1 - 3 M_{\odot}$) AGB stars may have contributed significantly to the enrichment of the material from which the RGB-a stars formed. This, in turn, implies a significant delay (~ 0.5 Gyr) between the formation of the stellar population that enriched the medium and the one associated with RGB-a (Norris & Da Costa, 1995a; Lee et al., 1999). A deeper discussion on the chemical enrichment timescales in ω Cen can be found in Chapters 2 and 9.

3.4 A Preliminary Study of the Spatial Distribution

The correlation between metal content and kinematics found by Norris et al. (1997), and the spatial asymmetry between metal rich and metal poor bright red giants found by Jurcsik (1998), are a possible evidence of a past merging event, in which a small metal rich object has been captured by a larger system, mainly metal poor. Note that none of the quoted studies have identified the RGB-a as a distinct population, since only a few stars belonging to this branch have been measured by Norris, Freeman & Mighell (1996) and listed by Jurcsik (1998). The discovery of a population so clearly separated from the main branches makes the hypothesis that ω Cen hosts an external population captured in the past more and more appealing, even if it is worth noticing, according to note 3 by Norris et al. (1997), that neither the large metal spread nor the s-process abundances of the RGB-MP and RGB-MInt can be easily explained in terms of a simple merging event between two ordinary globular clusters.

These considerations prompted us to start an preliminary investigation on the spatial distribution of the three RGB components, taking advantage of our photometric sample, which is much larger ($N_{RGB} > 3500$) and more complete than the Norris et al. (1997) and Jurcsik (1998) ones. A more detailed and rigorous statistical investigation of the spatial distribution of the three RGB sub-populations will be conducted in Chapter 6, but a few first, general properties can already be derived with the following analysis.

Sub-populations Centroids.

As a first step, we evaluated the centroid of the stars of the entire sample; by adopting the procedure described in Montegriffo et al. (1995) and Ferraro et al. (1999b), we found it to be at pixel $(700 \pm 20, 1900 \pm 20)$. The centroids of all the RGB components appear to coincide within these large observational errors, but see the more accurate determinations carried out in Chapter 6 and the following discussion.

Radial Distributions.

Then, we investigated the radial distributions; special care has been devoted to avoid contamination by the field population which can affect the radial trend, especially in the lower density external region. To this purpose, we limited our analysis to the most internal region ($r < 10'$), and to the brighter

Figure 3.8: Isodensity contour maps. The map is $\sim 26'$ in size. The distribution of the RGB-a sample (heavy solid line in *panel (a)*) and of the RGB-MInt (heavy solid line in *panel (b)*) is compared with the RGB-MP distribution (light dashed lines in both panels). The step between the isodensity contours is 2 counts for the RGB-a and RGB-MInt maps. For the RGB-MP the step is 1 count for the outer 30 isodensity contours and 10 for the others. The total number of stars comprised in the outer isodensity contour is $N = 116$ for the RGB-a, $N = 236$ for the RGB-MInt and $N > 1000$ for the RGB-MP samples. The difference in the elongation of the spatial distribution between the RGB-MP (along the X-axis) and the RGB-MInt, RGB-a (along the Y-axis) is well visible.

portion ($B < 16$) of the RGB, which is expected to be little contaminated. The comparison of the cumulative radial distributions for the selected RGB samples shows that the RGB-MInt and RGB-a stars have a very similar distribution, and both seem to be more concentrated than the RGB-MP. A KS test gives an 8% probability that the radial distribution of the coadded (RGB-MInt + RGB-a) sample and the RGB-MP sample are drawn from the same parent distribution. Although this evidence is marginal, it is in good agreement with that found by Norris et al. (1997). Still, this simple radial distribution analysis implicitly assumes that the three populations are distributed with the same (spherical) geometry. In view of the strong ellipticity of ω Cen, we decided to follow an alternative approach.

Spatial density distributions.

In order to avoid the sparsely populated outer regions, we divided the central region of the cluster ($r < 13'$ from the center) into a grid of 13×13 square boxes, each 500×500 pixels wide. Inside each box, we counted the number of stars belonging to the different samples (N_{RGB-MP} , $N_{RGB-MInt}$ and N_{RGB-a} , respectively), thus obtaining a density map for each component. The resulting isodensity contour maps, down to a fixed density limit (4 stars per box), are shown in Figure 3.8. The distributions of the RGB-a sample (heavy solid lines in the top panel) and of the RGB-MInt (heavy solid lines in the bottom panel) are compared with the RGB-MP distribution (light dashed lines in both panels). The elongation of the RGB-MP isodensity contours along the X-axis is clearly visible, reflecting the well known elliptical shape of the whole system: our X-axis is approximately oriented along the E-W direction, i.e., the major axis of the cluster. It is worth noticing that the ellipticity of the RGB-MP component turns out to be $\epsilon \sim 0.2$, even in the most internal region of the cluster ($2' - 4'$). On the other hand, both the RGB-a and RGB-MInt isodensity contours show a very different direction of maximum elongation, nearly perpendicular to the RGB-MP one (i.e., along the N-S direction). Furthermore, a very peculiar substructure is visible in the RGB-a contours, resembling the tidal tails which should be expected to form around a disrupting stellar system (e.g. Leon, Meylan & Combes, 2000).

We took advantage of the fact that the major axis of the RGB-MP ellipsoid is nearly oriented along our X-axis, while the RGB-MInt and RGB-a ones are nearly oriented along the Y-axis. We can thus study the distribution along the two main symmetry axes by simply comparing the distributions along our X

and Y coordinates with respect to the the common centroid. The main results of this analysis are:

- the RGB-MP sample is significantly more concentrated in the Y direction than in X (confidence level 99.5%, according to a KS test), as expected for an ellipsoid elongated in the X-axis direction;
- the RGB-MInt and RGB-a do not share the elongation in the X direction of the RGB-MP stars, and look more elongated in Y than the RGB-MP ones (confidence level 99.6%);
- Figure 3.8 suggests that the RGB-MInt stars distribution is strongly asymmetric along the Y-axis, being more elongated towards the North direction.

These results could help to shed some light on previous puzzling evidence. In particular, they could explain the decrease of ellipticity in the inner 5' of the cluster reported by Geyer, Nelles & Hopp (1983), the bizarre spatial asymmetry found by Jurcsik (1998) (see Chapter 6 for more details).

Furthermore, the similarity in the spatial distributions may indicate a physical association between the RGB-a and RGB-MInt, while the differences shown in Figure 3.8 suggest a different origin of these two components with respect to the main metal-poor one (RGB-MP). If this result finds additional support, then the RGB-a and RGB-MInt populations can be interpreted as two successive phases of the self-enrichment history of an independent stellar system (a giant molecular cloud or a gas rich protocluster), now sunk into the center of ω Cen. These ideas will be further explored in Chapters 5, 6 and 9.

Chapter 4

Abundance Analysis of Red Giants in ω Centauri

In this Chapter we present the spectroscopic part of the project, devoted to the study of the detailed abundance patterns of RGB stars in ω Cen and, in particular, to the newly discovered RGB-a population. The project is articulated in several phases: *(i)* an exploratory *pilot project* based on a small sample of RGB-a and RGB-MInt stars, observed with the high-resolution optical echelle spectrograph UVES at the ESO VLT (Section 4.1), that was successfully carried out and published (Pancino et al., 2002); *(ii)* a low resolution survey in the infrared with SOFI at the NTT, aimed at increasing the number of objects and to better study C and O from IR molecular bands (Section 4.2), that has been carried out successfully and is now in course of publication (Origlia et al., 2003); *(iii)* an extended high-resolution campaign with UVES, to derive the complete chemical fingerprint of the RGB-a (Section 4.3) and to use the RGB-MInt and RGB-MP stars as comparison with the previous literature (e.g., Norris & Da Costa, 1995a; Smith et al., 2000, etc.); this part of the project is currently under way and we present here some preliminary results; *(iv)* a vast high and intermediate resolution study of a few hundreds of RGB stars with FLAMES at the VLT, that will start with the Ital-FLAMES Guaranteed Time Observations in May 2003 (Chapter 9).

4.1 The Pilot UVES Project

We selected six targets among the metal-rich giants in ω Cen. Three of them (stars ROA 300, WFI 222068 and WFI 222679) belong to the RGB-a, while the other three (ROA 371, ROA 211 and WFI 618854) belong to the RGB-MInt. Only star ROA 371 (Tables 4.4 and 4.7) has been observed

before with high-resolution spectroscopy ($R \geq 20000$) by Paltoglou & Norris (1989), Brown et al. (1991), Vanture, Wallerstein & Brown (1994) and Norris & Da Costa (1995a), and for this reason represents an ideal comparison object. After publication of the *pilot project* results (Pancino et al., 2002), Vanture, Wallerstein & Suntzeff (2002) published also an abundance analysis of ROA 300 (see Tables 4.4 and 4.7).

The *pilot project* observations (Run A, see Table 4.1 for a diary of the observations) were carried out in June 2000 with UVES at the VLT in Paranal, as a backup programme while the main targets were not visible. All the obtained spectra have very high signal-to-noise ratios, $S/N \sim 100$ per pixel (more details in Table 4.5), where a resolution element covers approximately 5 pixels. The setup chosen allowed us to cover the whole spectral region from $\sim 3500\text{\AA}$ to $\sim 9000\text{\AA}$, with two gaps around 5000\AA and 7000\AA . The spectra were taken through the $1''$ slit, that allows a spectral resolution of $R \sim 45,000$.

The monodimensional spectra were extracted with the UVES pipeline (Ballester et al., 2000), with the optimum extraction method. This includes bias-subtraction, inter-order background light subtraction, optimal extraction with cosmic ray rejection, flat-field correction, wavelength calibration, rebinning and final merging of all overlapping orders. The spectra were then normalized to the continuum and corrected for telluric absorption bands (mostly O_2 and H_2O vapours) using standard tasks within the IRAF package *noao.onedspec*. To this aim, a telluric calibration standard (HR 6215/HD 150745 from the *Bright Star Catalog* – Hoffleit & Jaschek, 1991) was observed at least once each night, at an airmass similar to that of the targets. An example of the high-quality resulting spectra is shown in Figures 4.1 and 4.2. All of the Run A program stars in Table 4.1 are radial velocity members of ω Cen.

4.1.1 Equivalent Widths and Atomic Data

A set of reliable and unblended lines were selected, spanning a wide range in strength, excitation potential and wavelength. For the *pilot project*, we selected only lines of Fe I, Fe II, Ca I and Si I (~ 130 lines in total), plus the hyperfine splitted 5782\AA Cu I line. We only explored the region with the highest S/N , between ~ 5300 and $\sim 6800\text{\AA}$. The atomic data for these lines were taken from the NIST¹ database, and from Nave et al. (1994) for Iron.

¹NIST (National Institute of Standards and Technology) Atomic Spectra Database, Version 2.0 (March 22, 1999), <http://physics.nist.gov/cgi-bin/AtData/main.asd>.

Figure 4.1: A sample of UVES spectra in the region of the 5853Å Ba II line and of the 5857Å Ca I line. Spectra of stars with increasing metallicity, from top to bottom, are shown.

Figure 4.2: A sample of UVES spectra in the region of the 6300Å forbidden O I line. Spectra of stars with increasing metallicity, from top to bottom, are shown.

Target Information and Adopted Stellar Parameters										
WFI	Leiden	ROA	V	$(B-V)_o$	$(V-I)_o$	$(V-K)_o$	T_{eff}	$\log g$	v_t	[Fe/H]
221132	48099	300	12.71	-1.21	1.48	4.0	3900	0.7	1.4	-0.77
222068	48116	—	12.95	-0.97	1.42	3.4	4000	1.1	1.3	-0.49
222679	47145	—	13.26	-0.66	1.26	3.2	4100	1.2	1.4	-0.54
619210	60073	211	12.43	-1.49	1.37	—	4000	0.8	1.9	-1.02
617829	61067	371	12.71	-1.21	1.34	—	4000	0.7	1.5	-0.95
618854	—	—	13.26	-0.66	1.00	—	4600	1.2	1.5	-1.20

Table 4.1: Columns one to three report the stars names according to Pancino et al. (2000), van Leeuwen et al. (2000) and Woolley (1966), respectively. Columns four to seven report the V magnitude and dereddened colors from the photometry presented in Chapter 3. The four last columns report the adopted stellar parameters of the best model obtained as described in the text.

For the Copper line, that has a non negligible hyperfine structure, we used the hyperfine line list from the Kurucz database (Bielski, 1975).

Equivalent Widths (EW) for the *pilot sample* were measured with IRAF by gaussian fitting of the line profile on the local continuum. For the coolest stars we chose *not* to measure any atomic line inside the prominent TiO bands. The comparison of our EW measurements for ROA 371 with Norris, Da Costa, & Tingay (1995) shows a modest ($\sim 2\%$) systematic difference that has a negligible impact on the final abundance determination: the results for ROA 371 are, in fact, in good agreement with other literature values (Table 4.7).

4.1.2 Initial Estimates of the Stellar Parameters

The first step of the abundance analysis involves the search for the *best model* describing each star, starting from *initial estimates* of the four key parameters: effective temperature T_{eff} (in $^{\circ}K$), surface gravity $\log g$, microturbulent velocity v_t (in km s^{-1}) and global metallicity [M/H]. Two of them, T_{eff} and $\log g$ can be derived from our multiband photometry (Chapter 3), provided that we first produce the absolute M_V magnitude and the dereddened colors, assuming $(m - M)_V = 13.97$ (Harris, 1996) and $E(B - V) = 0.11$ (Lub, 2002). $E(V - I)$ and $E(V - K)$ are computed with the reddening laws by Dean, Warren & Cousins (1978) and Cardelli, Clayton & Mathis (1989), respectively.

We then make use of two different color-temperature calibrations. In particular, Table 3 by Montegriffo et al. (1998) and formulas 4, 6 and 9 from Table 2 by Alonso, Arribas & Martínez-Roger (1999), where the $(V - I)$ color had to be converted from the Johnson’s system to the Kron-Cousins’s system with the prescription by Bessell (1979). With the derived T_{eff} and BC_V we

were able to obtain $\log g$ from the fundamental relations

$$\log \frac{g_*}{g_\odot} = \log \frac{M_*}{M_\odot} + 2 \log \frac{R_\odot}{R_*}$$

$$0.4(M_{bol,*} - M_{bol,\odot}) = -4 \log \frac{T_{eff,*}}{T_{eff,\odot}} + 2 \log \frac{R_\odot}{R_*}$$

Assuming $M_* = 0.8 M_\odot$ (Bergbusch & Vandenberg, 2001), $\log g_\odot = 4.437$, $T_{eff,\odot} = 5770^\circ K$ and $M_{bol,\odot} = 4.75$, in conformity with the IAU recommendations (Andersen, 1999), we derived

$$\log g_* = 0.4(M_V + BC_V) + 4 \log T_{eff,*} - 12.61$$

We thus derived the estimated T_{eff} and $\log g$, from both the above color-temperature calibrations and for the three colors $(B - V)_o$, $(V - I)_o$ and $(V - K)_o$ for each of the programme star. First estimates of the microturbulent velocity v_t and of $[M/H]$ were instead derived from the curves of growth of Fe I and Fe II, and with the help of past literature estimates, when available.

4.1.3 Search for the Best Model

The abundance calculations for the *pilot project* were performed using an extension of the OSMARCS grid of plane parallel, LTE model atmospheres for M giants and supergiants calculated by Plez (1992) and Plez (1995, private communication). We used the most recent version of the LTE synthetic spectrum and abundance calculation code originally described by Spite (1967).

We used the above estimates of the four parameters T_{eff} , $\log g$, v_t and $[M/H]$ to decide which range of the parameters space we intended to explore. Then we computed abundances of Fe I and Fe II from our input line list of measured EW for a grid of interpolated models in the chosen parameters range for each star. Generally, we allowed T_{eff} to vary in steps of $100^\circ K$ for approximately $700 \div 900^\circ K$, depending on the star. For $\log g$ we explored a vast range of ~ 1 dex in steps of 0.1 dex. For the microturbulence we also explored a wide range of about 1 km s^{-1} in steps of 0.1 km s^{-1} , while for the metallicity we tried only one or two (exceptionally three) values close to the photometric metallicity, without interpolating on the original model grids.

Abundances for each of the Fe I and Fe II lines were produced for each star and for each trial model. The best model for each star was chosen by imposing the following four conditions:

- Excitation equilibrium: the abundance of the Fe I (and Fe II) lines should not vary with the excitation potential χ_{ex} — refining the T_{eff} estimate;
- The abundance of the Fe I (and Fe II) lines should not vary with the measured EW, i.e., strong and weak lines should give the same abundance — refining the estimate of v_t ;
- Ionization equilibrium: the abundance of the Fe I lines should not differ by more than the estimated uncertainty (~ 0.1 dex) from the abundance of the Fe II lines — refining the estimate of $\log g$;
- The abundance of the Fe I (and Fe II) lines should not vary with the wavelength, λ , as a global sanity check of the chosen model.

When the best model was found for each star, lines that gave systematically discrepant abundances in a significant number of stars were rejected, and the whole procedure iterated a few times. The resulting best model parameters for the programme stars are summarized in Table 4.1 (see also Section 4.3 and Pancino et al., 2002).

4.1.4 Error Analysis

Once the best model has been chosen, abundances are computed for all of the elements in the original line list. The abundance for each species is obtained by averaging the abundances resulting from all the measured lines, and the *random error* of that measurement is easily computed as the error on the average, σ/\sqrt{N} , where N is the number of lines. For the 5782Å Copper line, that has hyperfine structure, the abundance has been derived through spectral synthesis of the blended line profile. The *random error* in this case has been derived from the residuals of the fitting procedure.

The sensitivity of the models to the adopted stellar parameter was extensively tested, by altering the parameters by their estimated uncertainty ($\Delta T_{eff} = \pm 100^\circ K$; $\Delta \log g = \pm 0.2$ dex and $\Delta v_t = \pm 0.2$ km s⁻¹) and by propagating the global impact that each of such changes has on the final abundance of each element ([El/H]) and on each element ratio [El/Fe]. The resulting abundances, with their random and systematic errors are shown in Table 4.2.

To give an idea of the (external) systematic uncertainties, we analyzed the spectrum of Arcturus (α Boo), taken with UCLES at the Anglo Australian Telescope (Bessell, private communication), with the same procedure used for

Element Abundances for the Pilot Project (Run A)				
RGB-MInt Stars				
Star	[Fe/H]	[Ca/Fe]	[Si/Fe]	[Cu/Fe]
ROA 211	-1.02±0.01 (±0.08)	+0.28±0.04 (±0.14)	+0.28±0.07 (±0.10)	-0.45±0.09 (±0.12)
ROA 371	-0.95±0.01 (±0.09)	+0.30±0.03 (±0.14)	+0.26±0.11 (±0.11)	-0.33±0.07 (±0.04)
WFI 618854	-1.20±0.01 (±0.12)	+0.28±0.04 (±0.05)	+0.30±0.06 (±0.10)	-0.41±0.04 (±0.07)
RGB-a Stars				
Star	[Fe/H]	[Ca/Fe]	[Si/Fe]	[Cu/Fe]
ROA 300	-0.77±0.02 (±0.10)	+0.12±0.07 (±0.15)	+0.01±0.11 (±0.11)	-0.32±0.13 (±0.04)
WFI 222068	-0.49±0.02 (±0.12)	+0.15±0.06 (±0.16)	+0.11±0.10 (±0.11)	-0.15±0.12 (±0.05)
WFI 222679	-0.54±0.02 (±0.11)	+0.06±0.05 (±0.14)	+0.08±0.10 (±0.11)	-0.33±0.11 (±0.08)

Table 4.2: Resulting element abundances and element ratios for the pilot analysis of the six stars observed in Run A (Pancino et al., 2002). The first column reports the star name, the following columns show the abundances of [Fe/H], [Ca/Fe], [Si/Fe] and [Cu/Fe], with their estimated uncertainties. The first uncertainty number is the *random error*, while the second number in parenthesis represents the impact of errors on the assumed model parameters, which is systematic in nature (Section 4.1.4).

the programme stars, obtaining: $T_{eff} = 4300 K$, $\log g = 1.6$, $v_t = 1.4 km s^{-1}$ and $[Fe/H] = -0.43$. This can be used, together with the literature analysis of ROA 371 and ROA 300 (Table 4.7) to place the derived abundances in a more general context.

4.1.5 Results from the Pilot Project

The three RGB-a stars studied in the *pilot project* (ROA 300, WFI 222068 and WFI 222679) are the first members of this population ever analyzed with high-resolution spectroscopy. By taking a straight average of their abundances (from Table 4.2) we found $[Fe/H] = -0.60 \pm 0.15$ and $[Ca/H] = -0.49 \pm 0.16$, confirming that the RGB-a population is the most metal rich component of the ω Cen stellar mix. The RGB-a abundance obtained here is lower than the previous estimate ($[Ca/H] \sim -0.1$) based on Calcium triplet surveys (see Section 2.5). However, Calcium triplet calibrations are usually rather uncertain in the high metallicity regime (see Norris, Freeman & Mighell, 1996).

The most interesting and surprising result, however, is the different α -elements enhancement found for the two sub-populations. We obtained $[Ca/Fe] = +0.29 \pm 0.01$ and $[Si/Fe] = +0.28 \pm 0.02$ for the three RGB-MInt stars, which is the expected value of the α -enhancement in halo and globular cluster stars. Instead, the three RGB-a stars have only $[Ca/Fe] = +0.11 \pm 0.05$ and $[Si/Fe] = +0.07 \pm 0.05$. If we compute the $[\alpha/Fe]$ abundance ratio for each star with a weighted average of their Ca and Si abundances, the α -enhancements of the RGB-MInt and RGB-a populations turn out to be $[\alpha/Fe] = +0.29 \pm 0.01$ and $[\alpha/Fe] = +0.10 \pm 0.04$, respectively. This is the first indication that a

Figure 4.3: Abundance ratios for $[\text{Ca}/\text{Fe}]$ (a), $[\text{Si}/\text{Fe}]$ (b) and $[\text{Cu}/\text{Fe}]$ (c) plotted versus $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$. Results for the six stars of the *pilot project* are plotted as large filled dots, with attached errorbars according to Section 4.1.4 and Table 4.2. The shaded areas mark the region where previous, high resolution measurements for ω Cen giants lie (Norris & Da Costa, 1995a; Smith et al., 2000) and the solid lines represent the corresponding α -enhancement trends in our Galaxy (Edvardsson et al., 1993; Gratton, 1999).

population of stars with a significantly lower α -enhancement exists in ω Cen: both Norris & Da Costa (1995a) and Smith et al. (2000), who analyzed giants in ω Cen with metallicities up to $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -0.78$ and $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -0.95$ respectively, found *no evidence* of a decrease in Calcium, Silicon or in any other α -element enhancement (see Section 2.6).

The effect is illustrated in Figure 4.3 (Panels *a*) and *b*), where the Calcium and Silicon enhancements are plotted as a function of $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$. The shaded areas mark the region where the measurements by Norris & Da Costa (1995a) and Smith et al. (2000) lie, while the solid lines represent the Galactic $[\alpha/\text{Fe}]$ relation as can be derived from Edvardsson et al. (1993) and Gratton (1999). The six stars analyzed here are plotted as filled dots: as can be seen, the three RGB-MInt stars show enhancements that are in good agreement with previous determinations for ω Cen, while the three RGB-a stars are clearly less overabundant in both elements. We would like to note at this point that even if some small systematic differences may be present among the various studies (most probably due to a different choice of the $\log gf$ data, see also Section 4.3) the trends in the abundance ratios are particularly robust since they are based on relative, differential measurements.

Panel *c*) of Figure 4.3 shows the results for $[\text{Cu}/\text{Fe}]$. The six *pilot project* stars are plotted as filled dots, the shaded area covers the region where Smith et al. (2000) and Cunha et al. (2002) measurements for ω Cen lie, and the solid line represents the trend found by Sneden, Gratton, & Crocker (1991) for field stars. The trend shown by our data is more compatible with the results by Sneden, Gratton, & Crocker (1991) than with the behaviour of the metal poor stars in ω Cen.

As discussed by Smith et al. (2000), Copper is thought to be produced mainly by SNe type Ia, and only marginally by SNe type II (see also Matteucci et al., 1993), as required to explain the trend observed in the Galaxy. For the metal poor and intermediate stars in ω Cen, Smith et al. (2000) and Cunha et al. (2002) found a very low and constant value of $[\text{Cu}/\text{Fe}] = -0.6$, in agreement with the idea that SNe Ia have *not* contributed to the enrichment of these two populations.

Thus, if ω Cen is the product of self-enrichment, and if the RGB-a sub-population is the result of the last burst of star formation in ω Cen, the only way to decrease its α -enhancement with respect to the RGB-MInt would be a significant enrichment in iron. Since the main iron producers are SNe type Ia, if the results shown in Figure 4.3 are confirmed by larger samples of metal

rich stars, then *we have found the first evidence that Supernovae type Ia ejecta have contaminated the medium from which the RGB-a stars have formed.*

This interpretation would be further reinforced if the rising trend of Cu with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ will be also confirmed. However, since the exact production sites of Cu are still debated, another way to disentangle the relative contributions of SNe type II and type Ia would be to combine the study of Cu (and possibly Mn, which seems to have a similar origin – McWilliam, 1997) *together with Europium*. Europium is infact the only measureable element in cool giants that is a pure r -process result (see Section 2.6 and Norris & Da Costa, 1995a; Smith et al., 2000, and references therein), so its abundance traces very closely the purest contribution of SNe type II.

4.2 The Infrared Spectroscopic Survey

The observed sample consists of 21 stars belonging to both the metal-rich RGB-a and to the metal-poorer sub-populations (RGB-MInt and RGB-MP) of ω Cen. One intermediate-metallicity star, WFI 228136, could be in the AGB evolutionary phase, according to its position in the CMD (see Table 4.3). Figure 4.4 shows the targets location in the $I_0, (B - I)_0$ color-magnitude diagram, according to the photometric catalog presented in Chapter 3, dereddened assuming $E(B - V) = 0.12$ (Harris, 1996).

The targets have been observed at the ESO NTT 3.5 m telescope at La Silla, Chile, using the near-IR imager and spectrometer SOFI, on January 2000 and December 2001. The stars were observed through a $0.6''$ slit, with both the low resolution JH blue grism ($R \simeq 900$ at $1.2 \mu\text{m}$) and the medium resolution H band grism ($R \simeq 2300$ at $1.6 \mu\text{m}$). The spectra have been sky-subtracted, flat-fielded and corrected for atmospheric absorption using an O-star spectrum as reference. The overall signal to noise ratio of the final spectra is ≥ 30 , and an example of their quality can be seen in Figure 4.5 (empty circles). All of the observed stars are radial velocity members of ω Cen.

The stellar parameters have been established as follows: the temperature, T_{eff} , from optical colors (Figure 4.4), using the color-temperature transformation of Montegriffo et al. (1998), gravity, $\log g$, from theoretical evolutionary tracks according to the location on the RGB, while for the microturbulent velocity, v_t , an average value of 1.5 km s^{-1} has been adopted (see Origlia, Ferraro, Fusi Pecci, & Oliva, 1997). The full sample of observed stars and their adopted photospheric parameters are listed in Table 4.3.

Figure 4.4: The targets observed during the IR runs with SOFI are marked on the zoomed RGB region of ω Cen. Large filled circles mark the RGB-a stars, while large empty circles mark instead the comparison objects, belonging to the RGB-MP and RGB-MInt.

4.2.1 Abundance Analysis

The near-IR (1-2.5 μm) spectra of cool stars show many absorption lines due to neutral metals and molecules. Most of the molecular lines in the H band are not saturated and can be safely treated under the LTE approximation, being roto-vibrational transitions in the ground electronic state, providing accurate C and O abundances. The accessible neutral, atomic lines in the J and H bands are heavily saturated and somewhat less sensitive to element abundance variations, with respect to the molecular lines, but they are not affected by severe blending so they can be safely measured even from low resolution spectra. Three main compilations of atomic oscillator strengths are used: the Kurucz's database, Biemont & Grevesse (1973) and Meléndez & Barbuy (1999). The dissociation energies of the molecules are from Table 2 in Johnson, Bernat & Krupp (1980).

Performing abundance analysis from low resolution spectra is not an easy task. It requires a full spectral synthesis technique to account for line blending and eventually cross-check calibrations with high resolution spectra to select the most sensitive and less contaminated lines (Origlia, Rich & Castro, 2002a). Synthetic spectra of giant stars for different input atmospheric parameters have

Figure 4.5: The normalized spectrum of WFI 246325 is plotted as empty dots in three different windows, showing some of the lines and bands used for the analysis. The best model and two additional models with ± 0.2 dex variations with respect to the best fit abundance are plotted as thin solid lines.

been computed using an updated version of the code described in Origlia, Moorwood & Oliva (1993), that allows the abundance derivation both from full spectral synthesis and from EW measurements of single lines. The code uses the LTE approximation and is based on the molecular blanketed model atmospheres of Johnson, Bernat & Krupp (1980). For temperatures higher than $4000^{\circ}K$ the ATLAS 9 models are used.

The EW of the atomic lines have been measured by gaussian fitting of the line profile, typical values ranging between 100 and 1000 mÅ, with a conservative error of ± 150 mÅ, implying an average uncertainty in the resulting abundances of $\sim 0.2-0.3$ dex.

Different assumptions in the input stellar parameters can also influence the derived abundances. By varying the parameters of reasonable amounts ($\Delta T_{eff} \pm 200^{\circ}K$, $\Delta \log g = \pm 0.5$ and $\Delta v_t = \pm 0.5$ km s $^{-1}$), the change in the inferred element abundances is always ≤ 0.2 dex. As shown in Figure 4.5, models with ± 0.2 dex variation of the elemental abundances with respect to the best-fit solution generate quite different line profiles, particularly in the case of the molecular lines which are not saturated and hence more sensitive to the element abundance. Propagating all of the above sources of error, we assume a global average uncertainty of $\sim 0.2 \div 0.3$ dex on the abundance ratios (Table 4.3 and Figure 4.6).

Abundance Results for the IR Sample									
RGB-a Stars									
WFI	ROA	T_{eff}	$\log g$	[Fe/H]	[O/Fe]	[Ca/Fe]	[Mg/Fe]	[Si/Fe]	[C/Fe]
222068	-	4250	1.5	-0.55	-0.10	-0.05	-0.02	+0.05	-0.43
227309	-	5000	2.0	-0.55	-0.05	+0.05	+0.02	-0.05	-0.03
222679	-	4250	1.5	-0.60	+0.00	-0.10	+0.05	+0.00	-0.30
226951	-	4250	1.5	-0.70	+0.13	+0.00	+0.12	+0.10	-0.08
221132	300	4000	1.0	-0.77	+0.10	-0.03	+0.11	+0.12	-0.43
224245	-	4250	1.5	-0.80	+0.13	+0.10	+0.10	+0.20	+0.00
246325	513	4000	1.0	-0.90	+0.15	+0.20	+0.17	+0.20	-0.20
RGB-MInt Stars									
WFI	ROA	T_{eff}	$\log g$	[Fe/H]	[O/Fe]	[Ca/Fe]	[Mg/Fe]	[Si/Fe]	[C/Fe]
225687	-	5000	2.0	-1.00	+0.30	+0.30	+0.25	+0.20	-0.22
232173	-	4250	1.0	-1.10	+0.20	+0.30	+0.30	+0.20	-0.38
229257	-	4500	1.5	-1.10	+0.30	+0.20	+0.40	+0.20	-0.28
228136*	-	5000	2.0	-1.15	+0.35	+0.45	+0.25	+0.45	-0.07
236094	-	4250	1.0	-1.20	+0.25	+0.20	+0.30	+0.30	-0.25
224886	-	4500	1.5	-1.20	+0.30	+0.20	+0.35	+0.30	-0.25
230340	-	4250	1.0	-1.23	+0.33	+0.43	+0.23	+0.23	-0.29
RGB-MP Stars									
WFI	ROA	T_{eff}	$\log g$	[Fe/H]	[O/Fe]	[Ca/Fe]	[Mg/Fe]	[Si/Fe]	[C/Fe]
217134	167	4250	1.0	-1.53	+0.33	+0.43	+0.23	+0.23	-0.09
236826	9008	4500	1.5	-1.55	+0.32	+0.45	+0.25	+0.25	-0.07
237727	-	4250	1.0	-1.55	+0.35	+0.35	+0.27	+0.35	-0.23
222741	8161	4500	1.5	-1.57	+0.27	+0.47	+0.33	+0.17	-0.05
225201	8141	4500	1.5	-1.60	+0.37	+0.40	+0.10	+0.30	-0.25
239137	-	4500	1.5	-1.60	+0.30	+0.30	+0.30	+0.40	-0.38
235385	-	4250	1.0	-1.65	+0.45	+0.35	+0.25	+0.30	+0.03

Table 4.3: The first two columns report the star names according to Pancino et al. (2000) and Woolley (1966), respectively. Columns three and four report the adopted model parameters (v_t is 1.5 km s^{-1} for all stars). The last columns report the derived abundance ratios. WFI 228136 is most probably an AGB star.

4.2.2 Results for the Infrared Survey

We present here results concerning the abundances of key metals like Fe, C, O and other α -elements in the full range of metallicities (see Table 4.3). A detailed study of the $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C}$ ratio, a valuable indicator of mixing episodes in the stellar interior, has also been undertaken and will soon be published (Origlia et al., 2003). Carbon and Oxygen abundances are inferred from the CO ($\Delta v = 3$) and OH ($\Delta v = 2$) molecular lines in the H (1.5-1.8 μm) band, while Fe, Mg, Si and Ca abundances are derived from a few major neutral lines both in the J and H bands.

Figure 4.6 shows the inferred O, Ca, Si, and Mg abundances relative to iron as a function of [Fe/H] for the observed 21 giant stars in ω Centauri (see also Table 4.3). All these α -elements behave in a similar fashion,

Figure 4.6: The results for the α -elements are presented. Abundance ratios for $[\text{O}/\text{Fe}]$, $[\text{Si}/\text{Fe}]$, $[\text{Mg}/\text{Fe}]$ and $[\text{Ca}/\text{Fe}]$ (from top to bottom) are plotted against $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$. Empty symbols refer to the control samples of RGB-MP and RGB-MInt stars, while filled circles refer to the RGB-a population. The continuous lines are the least-square fitting to the two groups of stars, while the large crosses in the lower left corner of each plot are the uncertainty estimates described in Section 4.2.1.

Figure 4.7: The targets observed during Run A, B and C with UVES are marked on the zoomed RGB region of ω Cen. Large filled circles mark those RGB-a and RGB-MInt stars that belong to the *extended sample*, for which we present preliminary abundance results. The empty large circles mark instead those comparison objects, belonging to the RGB-MP and RGB-MInt, that will be used to calibrate all the literature data in the same framework.

confirming their common origin as by-products from SNe type II enrichment. Only the RGB-MP and RGB-MInt giants appear significantly α -enhanced ($[\alpha/\text{Fe}] = +0.30 \pm 0.03$ dex), while the RGB-a component shows almost no enhancement, confirming the suggestion made in Section 4.1.5 (and in Pancino et al., 2002) that they must have been enriched by SNe type Ia as well.

The three RGB-a stars observed in the *pilot project* have also been re-observed here and there is full consistency, within the quoted uncertainties, between the two sets of abundance measurements (cf. Tables 4.3 and 4.7). Other six giants (ROA 8141, ROA 8161, ROA 9008, ROA 167, ROA 300 and ROA 513) have been previously studied by Norris, Freeman & Mighell (1996) with low resolution optical spectroscopy. While the agreement is satisfactory for the RGB-MP and RGB-MInt stars, the two RGB-a stars (ROA 300 and ROA 513) show systematically lower metallicities than what determined by Norris, Freeman & Mighell (1996). This is exactly the same effect reported in Section 4.1 and is most probably due to problems in the Ca II triplet calibration, as reported by Norris, Freeman & Mighell (1996) themselves. These two stars have been also previously classified as S-stars by Lloyd Evans

Literature Cross-References				
ROA	Leiden	WFI	LR Refs	HR Refs
-	48116	222068	-	15
-	47145	222679	-	15
-	-	618854	-	15
92	46092	225207	13	-
159	33011	411069	2,12,13	11,17
179	41476	126361	5,12,13	8,11,17
211	60073	619210	13	15
213	16015	-	1,2,13	3,4,8,9,11,14,17
238	37247	243123	12,13	14,17
243	34029	332564	12,13	-
256	41039	322398	12,13	6,11
300	48099	221132	5,12,13	15,16
321	44462	122875	12,13	-
371	61067	617829	1,5,12,13	7,8,10,11,15,17
447	37024	329557	5,13	-
500	48323	221376	5,13	-
517	34180	249639	5,13	-
523	48321	221647	5,13	-

Table 4.4: The columns contain: (1) The star name from Woolley (1966); (2) the star name from van Leeuwen et al. (2000); (3) the star name from Pancino et al. (2000); (4) literature references for low resolution spectroscopy ($R < 15000$) and (5) literature references for high resolution spectroscopy ($R > 15000$). Meaning of the literature reference numbers: 1. Dickens & Bell (1976); 2. Bessell & Norris (1976); 3. Cohen (1981); 4. Gratton (1982); 5. Lloyd Evans (1983); 6. François, Spite & Spite (1988); 7. Paltoglou & Norris (1989); 8. Brown et al. (1991); 9. Brown & Wallerstein (1993); 10. Vanture, Wallerstein & Brown (1994); 11. Norris & Da Costa (1995a); 12. Suntzeff & Kraft (1996); 13. Norris, Freeman & Mighell (1996); 14. Smith et al. (2000); 15. Pancino et al. (2002); 16. Vanture, Wallerstein & Suntzeff (2002); 17. Cunha et al. (2002).

(1983), showing strong Ba II absorption lines. Star ROA 300 has very recently been studied also by Vanture, Wallerstein & Suntzeff (2002), who found even lower abundances.

4.3 Preliminary Analysis of the Extended UVES Survey

We present in this Section some preliminary results of the UVES campaign on ω Cen RGB stars. The principal aim of the survey was to cover the RGB along its full extension in a homogeneous way, while having, at the same time, a good number of RGB-MInt and RGB-MP giants in common with previous high-resolution abundance studies on ω Cen. The complete literature cross-references can be found in Table 4.4, where the previous spectroscopic

Observing Logs									
WFI	Leid	ROA	V	(B-V) _o	(V-I) _o	(V-K) _o	Run	S/N	Pop
—	16015	213	(12.03)	(1.00)	—	—	C	30/100	MP
122875	44462	321	12.59	1.27	1.35	3.30	B	30/130	MInt
126361	41476	179	12.10	1.46	1.72	—	C	20/110	MInt
139267	33164	—	13.09	1.17	1.10	—	B	20/90	MInt
140419	32149	—	13.49	1.22	1.19	3.12	B	25/100	RGB-a
221132	48099	300	12.71	1.48	1.63	4.04	A	30/130	RGB-a
221376	48323	500	13.12	1.30	1.36	3.51	B	30/110	RGB-a
221647	48321	523	13.39	1.13	1.27	3.30	B	30/110	RGB-a
222068	48116	—	12.95	1.42	1.32	3.45	A	30/110	RGB-a
222679	47145	—	13.26	1.26	1.25	3.21	A	25/90	RGB-a
225207	46092	92	11.86	1.40	1.39	3.35	B	30/130	MInt
243123	37247	238	12.44	1.05	1.10	2.72	B	25/90	MP
249639	34180	517	13.10	1.19	1.35	3.47	B	25/110	RGB-a
263340	26067	—	13.62	1.13	1.05	—	B	25/100	RGB-a
305654	54022	—	13.38	1.29	1.18	—	B	40/110	RGB-a
321293	42042	—	13.69	1.15	1.09	—	B	30/100	RGB-a
322398	41039	256	12.28	1.13	1.12	—	B	25/100	MP
329557	37024	447	12.85	1.35	1.79	—	B	30/150	RGB-a
332564	34029	243	12.19	1.29	1.29	—	B	30/130	MInt
411069	33011	159	(12.85)	(0.60)	—	—	B	30/110	MP
617829	61067	371	12.71	1.34	1.36	—	A	40/120	MInt
618774	—	—	13.22	1.24	1.22	—	B	25/90	RGB-a
618854	—	—	13.26	1.00	0.97	—	A	40/90	MInt
619210	60073	211	12.43	1.37	1.40	—	A	30/140	MInt

Table 4.5: The columns contain: (1) the ROA star number from Woolley (1966); (2) the Leiden number from van Leeuwen et al. (2000); (3) the WFI star number from Pancino et al. (2000); (4)-(8) assumed magnitudes and dereddened colors from the photometry presented in Chapter 3, except for ROA 213 and ROA 159, where they are from van Leeuwen et al. (2000); (9) observing run during which the star was observed, see text for a description; (10) the S/N ratio measured on the blue and red parts of the spectrum; (12) RGB sub-population to which the star belongs, according to Pancino et al. (2000) and Figure 3.7 in Chapter 3.

works have been separated in HR (high-resolution, $R \geq 15,000$) and LR (low-resolution, $R \leq 15,000$). In particular, we concentrate here our attention on the most metal-rich stars in the whole sample, mostly belonging to the RGB-a and RGB-MInt populations (filled circles in Figure 4.7).

Observations were carried out during two further observing runs with the UVES in April 2001 (Run B) where most of the stars were observed, and in March 2002 (Run C), when two more stars were added to the sample as backup targets when the main targets were not visible. The complete diary of the observations, including the *pilot project* stars (Run A), can be found in Table 4.5.

All the observed spectra have very high signal-to-noise ratios, $S/N \sim 100$ per pixel, where a resolution element covers from 5 to 7 pixels depending on

Adopted Stellar Model Parameters							
WFI	Leid	ROA	T_{eff}	$\log g$	v_t	[M/H]	[Fe/H]
126361	41476	179	3900	0.6	1.8	-1.0	-1.34
139267	33164	-	4300	1.4	1.5	-0.6	-0.79
140419	32149	-	4200	1.5	1.4	-0.6	-0.68
221132	48099	300	4000	0.7	1.7	-0.6	-0.90
221376	48323	500	4100	1.5	1.2	-0.6	-0.52
221647	48321	523	4200	1.6	1.4	-0.6	-0.65
222068	48116	-	4000	1.1	1.3	-0.6	-0.64
222679	47145	-	4200	1.6	1.3	-0.6	-0.53
249639	34180	517	4100	1.3	1.2	-0.6	-0.53
263340	26067	-	4400	1.9	1.2	-0.6	-0.63
305654	54022	-	4200	1.6	1.4	-0.6	-0.65
321293	42042	-	4300	1.6	1.4	-0.6	-0.71
329557	37024	447	4000	0.9	1.6	-0.6	-0.91
617829	61067	371	4000	0.8	1.7	-0.6	-0.93
618774	-	-	4200	1.6	1.5	-0.6	-0.64
618854	-	-	4600	1.2	1.5	-1.0	-1.17
619210	60073	211	4000	0.7	2.1	-1.0	-1.08

Table 4.6: Best models for the stars analyzed so far. The first three columns report the star’s names according to Pancino et al. (2000), van Leeuwen et al. (2000) and Woolley (1966), respectively. Columns four to seven report the four parameters for the adopted best model. For the six stars in Run A, these are the parameters resulting from the re-analysis described in the text, and not to the original analysis performed in Pancino et al. (2002). The last column reports the resulting the iron metallicity based on the Fe I lines.

the setup. While during Run A the setup chosen allowed us to cover the whole spectral region from $\sim 3500\text{\AA}$ to $\sim 9000\text{\AA}$, with two gaps, during Runs B and C instead, the range covered was $\sim 3500\text{\AA}$ to $\sim 7000\text{\AA}$, with two gaps around 4600\AA and 5800\AA . Spectra in all of the three runs were taken with the $1''$ slit, that allows a spectral resolution of $R \sim 45,000$. The telluric standard used for Runs B and C was HR 5206/HD 120640 from the *Bright Star Catalog* (Hoffleit & Jaschek, 1991). The reduction procedure is exactly the same as for the *pilot project* (Section 4.1), and an example of the high quality of these spectra is shown in Figures 4.1 and 4.2. All the program stars in Table 4.5 are radial velocity members of ω Cen.

4.3.1 Abundance Analysis

The abundance analysis has been performed similarly to the *pilot project*, but with more updated software, atomic data and models. Since we wanted to have all measurements in a common scale, we re-analyzed the six stars of the

pilot project together with the stars from Runs B and C. The main updates of the method are described below, along with some comment on the impact of these changes.

After the publication of the *pilot project* results, we designed and developed an automatic software (DAOSPEC) to measure EW on high-resolution, high S/N spectra, in a collaboration with P. B. Stetson of the Dominion Astrophysical Observatory, Canada (Stetson & Pancino 2003, in preparation). DAOSPEC enables us to find, measure (with gaussian fitting) and identify (with a laboratory line list) thousands of lines in one spectrum in a matter of minutes. The average difference in the measured EW for the six Run A stars between DAOSPEC and the IRAF manual measurements is less than 1%, with no apparent trend with EW or wavelength.

We thus extended the input line list with respect to the *pilot project*, not only to include more lines of the above elements, but also to start including additional elements: (i) other α -elements like Mg, Ti and O; (ii) more iron-peak elements like V, Sc, Zn, Cr, Co, Ni; (iii) some of the best studied *s*-process elements like Yr, Zr, Ba, Ce, for a total of ~ 500 lines. We also changed our reference database to VALD (Vienna Atomic Lines Database – Kupka et al., 1999), mainly because of the more frequent updates and the more extended section on laboratory atomic data for heavy elements.

The impact of the atomic data changes on the final abundances (see Table 4.7) is generally very small, and generally results in a simple offset of the abundance zeropoint, proportional to the average difference in $\log gf$ between the two atomic line datasets. For example, the Calcium abundance derived in Pancino et al. (2002) is 0.13 dex lower than the one re-derived here, and it is entirely due to the change in $\log gf$. Relative abundances among different stars are, of course, unchanged.

Finally, we used the most updated, expanded grid from Plez (1997, private communication), that spans a wider range in gravities, α -enhancements, temperatures and metallicities. No detailed error analysis has been performed yet for the new analysis, so we attached representative errorbars of 0.15 dex to all of the derived abundance ratios. Table 4.7 reports a full comparison of the results derived here with all previous literature determinations, both from high and low resolution spectroscopic studies.

Literature Comparisons for the Extended Sample								
ROA	WFI	T_{eff}	$\log g$	v_t	[Fe/H]	R	S/N	Reference
-	222068	4000	1.1	1.3	-0.65	45000	100	<i>this Thesis</i>
		4000	1.1	1.3	-0.49	45000	100	Pancino et al. (2002)
-	222679	4200	1.6	1.3	-0.53	45000	100	<i>this Thesis</i>
		4100	1.2	1.4	-0.54	45000	100	Pancino et al. (2002)
-	618854	4600	1.2	1.5	-1.17	45000	100	<i>this Thesis</i>
		4600	1.2	1.5	-1.20	45000	100	Pancino et al. (2002)
179	126361	3900	0.6	1.8	-1.34	45000	100	<i>this Thesis</i>
		3850	0.5	1.5	-1.10	38000	50	Norris & Da Costa (1995a)
		3850	0.5	1.0	-1.62	17000	100	Brown et al. (1991)
		-	-	-	(-0.52)	5000	50	Norris, Freeman & Mighell (1996)
		-	-	-	-0.80	3000	100	Suntzeff & Kraft (1996)
211	619210	4000	0.7	2.1	-1.08	45000	100	<i>this Thesis</i>
		4000	0.8	1.9	-1.02	45000	100	Pancino et al. (2002)
		-	-	-	(-0.38)	5000	50	Norris, Freeman & Mighell (1996)
300	221132	3900	0.7	1.7	-0.90	45000	100	<i>this Thesis</i>
		3900	0.7	1.4	-0.77	45000	100	Pancino et al. (2002)
		4000	0.8	2.2	-1.20	30000	100	Vanture, Wallerstein & Suntzeff (2002)
		-	-	-	(-0.06)	5000	50	Norris, Freeman & Mighell (1996)
		-	-	-	-0.23	3000	100	Suntzeff & Kraft (1996)
371	617829	4000	0.8	1.7	-0.93	45000	100	<i>this Thesis</i>
		4000	0.7	1.5	-0.95	45000	100	Pancino et al. (2002)
		4000	0.9	1.6	-0.79	38000	50	Norris & Da Costa (1995a)
		4000	0.9	2.2	-1.00	20000	100	Vanture, Wallerstein & Brown (1994)
		4000	0.9	1.5	-0.90	17000	100	Brown et al. (1991)
		4000	0.9	2.5	-1.37	17000	50	Paltoglou & Norris (1989)
		-	-	-	(-0.42)	5000	50	Norris, Freeman & Mighell (1996)
		-	-	-	-0.33	3000	100	Suntzeff & Kraft (1996)
447	329557	4000	0.9	1.6	-0.91	45000	100	<i>this Thesis</i>
		-	-	-	(-0.15)	5000	50	Norris, Freeman & Mighell (1996)
		-	-	-	-0.25	3000	100	Suntzeff & Kraft (1996)
500	221376	4100	1.5	1.2	-0.52	45000	100	<i>this Thesis</i>
		-	-	-	(+0.03)	5000	50	Norris, Freeman & Mighell (1996)
517	249639	4100	1.3	1.2	-0.53	45000	100	<i>this Thesis</i>
		-	-	-	(+0.02)	5000	50	Norris, Freeman & Mighell (1996)
523	221647	4200	1.6	1.4	-0.65	45000	100	<i>this Thesis</i>
		-	-	-	(-0.24)	5000	50	Norris, Freeman & Mighell (1996)

Table 4.7: Comparison of the results obtained here, for the stars analyzed so far, with previously published results, both from high and low resolution. The first two columns report the stars names from Woolley (1966) and Pancino et al. (2000), respectively. Columns three to five report the adopted model parameters, T_{eff} , $\log g$ and v_t . Column six reports the iron abundance [Fe/H] except when the data are from the low resolution calcium triplet survey by Norris, Freeman & Mighell (1996), who gave only [Ca/H] (these results are reported in parenthesis). Columns seven and eight report the resolution $R = \lambda/\Delta\lambda$ and the S/N . The last column reports the literature reference.

Iron-Peak Elements for the Extended Sample						
WFI	ROA	[Sc/H]	[V/H]	[Cr/H]	[Fe/H]	[Ni/H]
126361	179	-1.29	-1.01	-1.26	-1.34	-1.30
139267	-	-0.49	-0.58	-0.74	-0.79	-0.82
140419	-	-0.52	-0.21	-0.59	-0.68	-0.63
221132	300	-0.77	-0.39	-0.72	-0.90	-0.95
221376	500	-0.28	0.07	-0.44	-0.53	-0.47
221647	523	-0.37	-0.03	-0.56	-0.65	-0.60
222068	-	-0.44	-0.10	-0.54	-0.64	-0.69
222679	-	-0.29	-0.32	-0.55	-0.54	-0.62
249639	517	-0.28	-0.11	-0.46	-0.54	-0.52
263340	-	-0.47	-0.29	-0.60	-0.63	-0.61
305654	-	-0.37	-0.07	-0.49	-0.65	-0.54
321293	-	-0.56	-0.44	-0.75	-0.72	-0.67
329557	447	-0.83	-0.31	-0.67	-0.92	-0.83
617829	371	-0.72	-0.65	-0.97	-0.94	-0.99
618854	-	-1.12	-1.24	-0.89	-1.16	-1.25
618774	-	-0.37	0.05	-0.51	-0.64	-0.47
619210	211	-0.94	-0.71	-0.97	-1.08	-1.19

Table 4.8: Iron-peak element abundances for the stars analyzed so far. The typical uncertainty on each measurement is ~ 0.15 dex.

4.3.2 Preliminary UVES Results

We present here the first, preliminary results for the metal-rich part of the UVES sample. The results are preliminary in the sense that they concern a sub-sample of the stars observed, of the measurable lines of each species, of the available atomic species, and of the observed spectral range. A complete analysis of the dataset should thus add more information and statistics, but we do not expect it to alter significantly the results obtained up to now.

First, given the higher number of RGB-a stars analyzed with respect to the *pilot project*, we can re-derive the average metallicity of the RGB-a. We obtain an average $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -0.62 \pm 0.06$, which is perfectly compatible with the result obtained in Section 4.2, with of course a lower σ . The detailed chemical abundance patterns of some iron-peak elements are reported in Table 4.8. For some of them, like V and Sc (Smith, 2002), a detailed spectral synthesis including hyperfine structure information may slightly lower the presented values. Qualitatively speaking, all the iron-peak element ratios measured so far show solar ratios with no evident trend with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$.

Figure 4.8: The α -element abundance ratio, obtained averaging of $[\text{Mg}/\text{Fe}]$, $[\text{Si}/\text{Fe}]$, $[\text{Ca}/\text{Fe}]$ and $[\text{Ti}/\text{Fe}]$, is plotted as a function of $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$. The horizontal dotted lines represent the solar (zero) and halo (+0.35) α -enhancements. The vertical dotted line marks the separation between the RGB-a ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] > -0.75$), where no previous high-resolution measurement exist, from the RGB-MInt/RGB-MP. The literature measurements by Norris & Da Costa (1995a) and Smith et al. (2000) are plotted as empty circles, while the *extended sample* measurements are represented by filled circles.

The α -elements

More interesting is the situation of the α -elements. The measurements obtained for O, Mg, Si, Ca and Ti are shown in Table 4.9. While Si, Ca and Ti are quite safe and robust since they are based on a few tens of lines each, the measurements of Mg are slightly more uncertain being based on less than ten lines. For Oxygen, the situation is even more delicate since the only available lines are the forbidden $[\text{O I}]$ lines at 6300 Å and 6363 Å, both falling inside one TiO band that is most disturbing for the coolest stars ($T_{\text{eff}} < 4000\text{K}$). The ~ 6300 Å O_2 telluric band falls also in that region since the radial velocity of ω Cen stars is around $\sim 250 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. As a result, only a sub-sample of the stars analyzed so far has reliable O abundances. A full spectral synthesis, including TiO molecules, could alleviate the problem and some stars have also a measurable 5577 Å O I line.

Due to these problems, we decided to exclude Oxygen from the estimate of the overall α -enhancement presented in Figure 4.8. Our measurements – filled circles – are compared with the results published by Norris & Da Costa (1995a) and Smith et al. (2000) – small empty circles. The first thing to be

α -elements for the Extended Sample							
WFI	ROA	[Fe/H]	[O/H]	[Mg/H]	[Si/H]	[Ca/H]	[Ti/H]
126361	179	-1.34	-0.78	-0.84	-1.02	-1.07	-0.78
139267	-	-0.79	-0.73	-0.47	-0.62	-0.38	-0.49
140419	-	-0.68	-0.38	-0.42	-0.48	-0.34	-0.23
221132	300	-0.90	—	-0.49	-0.59	-0.42	-0.36
221376	500	-0.53	-0.50	-0.31	-0.31	-0.28	-0.03
221647	523	-0.65	-0.31	-0.53	-0.36	-0.25	-0.13
222068	-	-0.64	-0.56	-0.35	-0.44	-0.33	-0.04
222679	-	-0.54	-0.24	-0.38	-0.42	-0.37	-0.47
249639	517	-0.54	-0.66	-0.31	-0.37	-0.29	-0.10
263340	-	-0.63	—	-0.39	-0.72	-0.33	-0.24
305654	-	-0.65	-0.52	-0.22	-0.34	-0.28	-0.16
321293	-	-0.72	-0.81	-0.34	-0.55	-0.35	-0.35
329557	447	-0.92	-0.75	-0.52	-0.47	-0.47	-0.29
617829	371	-0.94	-0.78	-0.45	-0.57	-0.51	-0.61
618854	-	-1.16	-1.47	-0.87	-0.87	-0.81	-0.96
618774	-	-0.64	-0.25	-0.23	-0.31	-0.28	-0.12
619210	211	-1.08	1.97	-0.60	-0.74	-0.70	-0.63

Table 4.9: Detailed α -element abundances calculations for the stars analyzed so far. The typical uncertainty on each measurement is ~ 0.15 dex.

noted is that, even if we did not perform a detailed set of comparisons, our measurements in the region $-1.5 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -0.8$ (the RGB-MInt) appear in reasonable agreement with the literature values.

The second thing to note concerns mainly the RGB-MP stars with $-2.0 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.5$, which appear to have a slightly lower α -enhancement with respect to the RGB-MInt stars *measured from the same authors*. A more detailed study of a large sample of RGB-MP stars is thus needed to further confirm this apparent trend. As recently discussed by Shetrone et al. (2003), a low and constant α -enhancement, in a metallicity regime where SNe Ia did not play any rôle, indicates that the enriching SNe II were preferentially of low mass ($< 20_{\odot}$, see Woosley & Weaver, 1995). A more detailed study of the single α -elements, on a large sample of giants of all metallicities, is thus urgently needed (see Chapter 9).

But the most evident result is that the RGB-a stars have, on average, a lower enhancement with respect to the RGB-MInt counterparts, fully confirming the results of the *pilot project* (Pancino et al., 2002) and of the IR survey (Origlia et al., 2003). So, as was pointed out in Section 4.1.5, if these stars formed from the α -enriched ejecta of the previous generations of stars in ω Cen (like the RGB-MInt, for example) then the only way to lower

Figure 4.9: The s -element abundance ratio, represented by the average of $[Y/Fe]$, $[Zr/Fe]$, $[Ba/Fe]$ and $[Nd/Fe]$, as a function of $[Fe/H]$. Horizontal dotted lines represent the solar and ten time solar ratios. The vertical dotted line separates the RGB-a ($[Fe/H] > -0.75$), where no previous high-resolution measurement exist, from the RGB-MInt/RGB-MP. Literature measurements by Norris & Da Costa (1995a), Smith et al. (2000) and Vanture, Wallerstein & Suntzeff (2002) are plotted as empty circles, while UVES measurements are represented by filled circles.

the α -enhancement would be a further enrichment by SNe type Ia.

As we will see in the following Chapters, however, there are reasons to believe that the RGB-a formed in a different environment and was later accreted by the main body of ω Cen. If this is really the case, the lower α -enhancement could simply be due to a different chemical evolution, where only low mass SNe II could contribute to its enrichment (see above).

We note that the only way to firmly disentangle contributions from SNe of type II and Ia is to find appropriate *tracers*, i.e. elements that, unlike the α -elements and the iron-peak elements, are produced *exclusively* (i.e., 100%) by one or the other type of supernovae. While Eu is a perfect tracer of SNe type II enrichment, Cu and Mn appear as promising tracers of SNe type Ia, although their effective production sites are still quite debated (Cunha et al., 2002). Eu, Cu and Mn require full spectral analysis of the line profile, since they possess hyperfine structure. Lines of these elements are present in the UVES spectra observed so far, so their analysis is one of the most urgent tasks for this part of the project.

<i>s</i>-process Elements for the Extended Sample								
WFI	ROA	[Fe/H]	[Y/H]	[Zr/H]	[Ba/H]	[La/H]	[Ce/H]	[Nd/H]
126361	179	-1.34	-0.65	-0.57	-0.23	-0.51	0.27	-0.30
139267	-	-0.79	0.04	-0.34	0.38	0.12	0.68	0.06
140419	-	-0.68	0.20	0.10	0.49	0.46	0.84	0.34
221132	300	-0.90	0.18	0.19	0.19	0.51	0.78	0.00
221376	500	-0.53	0.36	0.38	0.76	0.77	1.02	0.73
221647	523	-0.65	0.37	0.48	0.84	—	—	0.77
222068	-	-0.64	0.07	0.35	0.32	0.74	0.87	0.16
222679	-	-0.54	-0.32	0.02	0.52	0.81	1.00	0.49
249639	517	-0.54	0.12	0.06	0.65	0.74	0.84	0.54
263340	-	-0.63	0.13	0.12	0.53	0.46	0.95	0.39
305654	-	-0.65	0.36	0.53	0.56	—	—	0.78
321293	-	-0.72	-0.34	0.07	0.47	0.56	0.88	0.26
329557	447	-0.92	0.23	0.26	0.49	0.64	0.94	0.21
617829	371	-0.94	-0.24	-0.08	0.47	0.99	—	0.56
618854	-	-1.16	-0.43	-0.27	-0.10	-0.24	0.48	-0.03
618774	-	-0.64	0.61	0.86	0.64	—	—	0.74
619210	211	-1.08	-0.52	-0.31	-0.10	-0.22	0.30	-0.17

Table 4.10: Detailed *s*-elements abundance calculations for the stars analyzed so far. The typical uncertainty on each measurement is of about ~ 0.15 dex.

The *s*-process Elements

The next set of derived abundance ratios concerns the *s*-process elements Y, Zr, Ba, La, Ce and Nd (Table 4.10), which are mainly produced in AGB stars (Busso, Gallino & Wasserburg, 1999). These are some of the best studied *s*-process elements although their measurements for red giants are often based on a handful of lines, and most of the atomic data, particularly $\log gf$ values, are still uncertain. This is especially true, in the present case, for Ce and La, that could be measured only in some of the stars, and anyway resulted in scattered abundance trends.

To try to compensate for these drawbacks we averaged the four most reliable elements, Y, Zr, Ba and Nd to produce an average $[s/Fe]$ ratio (Figure 4.9). The UVES determinations are plotted as filled circles, while literature results by Norris & Da Costa (1995a), Smith et al. (2000) and Vanture, Wallerstein & Suntzeff (2002) are plotted as small empty circles. While the last two studies, based on more updated atomic data, appear in good agreement with our determinations, the data by Norris & Da Costa (1995a) had to be shifted by ~ 0.5 dex (a value determined using the only star in common, ROA 371) to produce a satisfactory agreement.

Figure 4.10: Different *s*-process elements ratios are used as indicators of the *s*-process efficiency. In all panels, the horizontal dotted lines represent the solar and ten times solar ratios, while the vertical dotted line separates the RGB-a metallicity regime ($[Fe/H] > -0.8$) from the RGB-MInt/RGB-MP one. Literature measurements by Norris & Da Costa (1995a), Smith et al. (2000) and Vanture, Wallerstein & Suntzeff (2002) are plotted as small empty circles while UVES measurements are represented by large filled circles. The ratio of heavy *s*-process elements to iron, $[hs/Fe]$, obtained by averaging Ba and Nd, is plotted versus $[Fe/H]$ in the top panel. The ratio of light *s*-process elements with iron, $[ls/Fe]$, obtained by averaging Y and Zr, is plotted versus $[Fe/H]$ in the middle panel. The bottom panel displays the ratio of heavy *s*-process to the light ones, $[hs/ls]$, versus $[Fe/H]$. The *hs* elements appear more abundant than the *ls* ones, pointing towards low mass AGB stars as the source of *s*-process enrichment.

Figure 4.9 confirms what already found in the past (see Chapter 2) for the RGB-MP and RGB-MInt populations. In particular, a dramatic increase of the s -process overabundance is clearly seen for RGB-MP stars up to approximately $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \simeq -1.5$, followed by a flattening out, or at least a break in the slope, for the RGB-MInt stars. Smith (2002) noticed that this break in slope, if true, appears exactly at the metallicity that separates the RGB-MP from the RGB-MInt.

Concerning the RGB-a, we see that it shows the same enrichment level of the RGB-MInt, i.e., ten times higher than the solar value observed for other GGC (Norris & Da Costa, 1995a). This result is very clear, and we do not expect that a finer analysis, possibly putting all of the published results in a common framework, will change it. The likely interpretation is that the RGB-MInt and the RGB-a were formed with similarly enriched gas. This continuity of properties is somehow in contrast with the clear difference detected in the α -enhancement between the two populations.

To further investigate on the source of s -process enrichment, we used a popular indicator of the neutron exposure, or efficiency of the s -process: the ratio $[\text{hs}/\text{ls}]$ between heavy and light s -process elements. We computed these ratios with the available measurements, i.e., averaging Ba with Nd for the heavy component and Y with Zr for the light component. The result is shown in Figure 4.10, where UVES measurements – filled circles – are plotted together with literature measurements – empty circles – by Norris & Da Costa (1995a), Smith et al. (2000) and Vanture, Wallerstein & Suntzeff (2002).

The clear overabundance of heavy s -process elements with respect to the light ones points towards low mass ($1.5 \div 3 M_{\odot}$) AGB stars as the main enriching source for ω Cen, through the $^{13}\text{C}(\alpha, n)^{16}\text{O}$ reaction that takes place in the interpulse period (Lambert et al., 1995; Busso, Gallino & Wasserburg, 1999; Busso et al., 2001). The RGB-a makes no exception, showing again a perfect continuity of properties with the RGB-MInt.

The enrichment by the slow winds of AGB stars poses also a problem concerning the enrichment timescales, as already discussed in Chapter 2, and further discussed in more detail in Chapter 9.

Chapter 5

A New Piece in the Puzzle: the Proper Motion of the RGB-a

As discussed in the previous Chapters, the discovery of the anomalous RGB (RGB-a) and of its peculiar chemical composition have added new pieces to the already complex jigsaw puzzle of the formation history of ω Cen. In this Chapter we use the B and I photometric catalog presented in Chapter 3, combined with the large proper motion study by van Leeuwen et al. (2000), to show that stars belonging to the RGB-a have a coherent bulk motion with respect to the other cluster stars. Statistical and photometric tests prove the reality of the observed effect, demonstrating that the RGB-a stars belong to an independent self-gravitating stellar system, still locked in the gravitational potential of ω Cen. This points towards a different dynamical origin of the RGB-a with respect to the other populations in ω Cen, further complicating the global picture.

5.1 Sample Definition and Proper Motion Centroids

The B and I catalog presented in Chapter 3 has been cross-correlated with the proper motion catalog of $\sim 10,000$ red giants in ω Cen published by van Leeuwen et al. (2000). They obtained accurate positions and proper motions of stars with $B < 16$, from photographic plates observed during more than 50 years with the Columbia 26-Inch refractor.

Red giants in our WFI photometry, having proper motion determinations from the van Leeuwen et al. (2000) catalog, have been divided in three samples according to the RGB sub-populations defined in Chapter 3 (see Figure 3.7). To minimize all the effects due to uncertain measures, only stars having good quality proper motions were selected, i.e., stars with both μ_x and μ_y measured to $\sigma_\mu < 0.5 \text{ mas yr}^{-1}$, and with quality flag < 4 (see van Leeuwen et al.,

Figure 5.1: Proper motion plane (μ_{RA}, μ_{Dec}) for stars in ω Cen. Stars in the Van Leeuwen’s catalog with accurate proper motion measures have been plotted as tiny dots in all panels for reference. Only stars with accurate measures ($\sigma_{\mu} < 0.5 \text{ mas yr}^{-1}$) and quality flag < 4 have been considered. The dashed circle highlights in all panels the center of symmetry for the whole cluster population. Stars belonging to the three RGB sub-samples are marked with solid dots: RGB-MP in panel (b), RGB-MInt in panel (c) and RGB-a in panel (d). As can be seen, while the RGB-MP and RGB-MInt proper motion centroids appear to coincide well with the centroid of the whole cluster, the RGB-a proper motion centroid is significantly displaced.

Figure 5.2: The proper motion components μ_x (top panel) and μ_y (bottom panel) are plotted versus the $(B - I)$ color for all of the stars in the WFI catalog that had a good quality ($\sigma_\mu < 0.5 \text{ mas yr}^{-1}$ and quality flag < 4) proper motion measurements. The HB stars, that appear clearly distinct from the RGB (and MS) stars, are labelled. The solid line represents a linear fit to the 3σ clipped data, and the resulting (negligible) slopes are also indicated in mas yr^{-1} per magnitude in $(B - I)$.

2000, for a full description of the catalog). The resulting sub-samples contain 2000 stars for the RGB-MP, 684 stars for the RGB-MInt and 105 stars for the RGB-a.

Figure 5.1 shows the proper motion distributions for the three different RGB sub-samples. For sake of comparison, all the stars satisfying the adopted selection criteria have been plotted on each panel as *tiny dots*. The most striking result is that the proper motion centroid of the RGB-a group is quite different from that of the RGB-MP population.

This means that the RGB-a stars have a coherent residual proper motion with respect to the dominant cluster population. The systematic residual motion turns out to be $\delta\mu_{RA} = +0.4$ and $\delta\mu_{DEC} = +0.7 \text{ mas yr}^{-1}$, which correspond to a total proper motion modulus of $|\delta\mu| = 0.8 \text{ mas yr}^{-1}$ with respect to the centroid of the RGB-MP population.

It is also worth mentioning that also the RGB-MInt population shows a different proper motion distribution with respect to the RGB-MP population. Although the effect is much smaller than the one shown by the RGB-a population (see Figure 5.1), the tests in Table 5.1 and Figure 5.5 prove that the difference is still significant.

Before discussing the implications of these results (Section 5.4), we show that the different proper motion found is not due to residual instrumental effects depending on color or magnitude (Section 5.2) and that the systematic difference is statistically significant (Section 5.3).

5.2 Dependence on Color or Magnitude

As discussed by van Leeuwen et al. (2000) in their Section 8, the Columbia 26-inch refractor, used for the proper motion measurements, suffered from some slight misalignment of the objective elements, during its more than 50 years of operation. Such a misalignment can produce more or less severe spurious non-linear color and magnitude terms (Kamper & Wesselink, 1978; Kozhurina-Platais et al., 1995).

van Leeuwen et al. (2000) have been in fact able to measure a color-related offset in the positions derived from different epoch plates. Such an effect appears, fortunately, to be relatively small ($2 \mu\text{m}$ per magnitude in $(B - V)$, amounting approximately to $0.04''$). But most of all, the effect appears almost linear, so that it has been easily corrected out, surely resulting in unaccurate absolute positions for some of the epochs, but leaving the relative measurements (and thus the proper motions determinations) unaffected.

However, given the result found in Figure 5.1, it is necessary to explore the proper motions of the sub-samples assembled here, in search for possible color or magnitude effects. A first, global test is to compare the average proper motions of blue stars belonging to the HB with that of the redder RGB stars and see if there is any significant discrepancy: the two samples appear to behave exactly in the same way (Figure 5.2).

Our specific task is to identify possible instrumental effects that affect the RGB-a in a different way with respect to the RGB-MP (and RGB-MInt). We thus note that the three sub-samples cover very similar ranges in $(B - I)$ color and B magnitude. So we can use this substantial overlap because, if a color or magnitude spurious trend affects the RGB-a stars, it should also affect the RGB-MP stars that lie in the same color range. If no trend is found, however, we can assume that such a color (or magnitude) effect, if present, has a negligible impact on the result found here.

Figures 5.3 and 5.4 show the proper motions μ_x and μ_y for the three sub-populations, plotted against $(B - I)$ and B from our WFI catalog. On each panel, the slope of a linear square fit to the 3σ -clipped data is indicated.

Figure 5.3: The proper motion is plotted versus the $(B - I)$ color for the three sub-population samples. The left panels refer to μ_x while the right panels refer to μ_y , in mas yr^{-1} . The RGB-MP is plotted in the bottom panels, the RGB-MInt in the intermediate panels and the RGB-a in the top panels. A linear fit to the 3σ clipped data is performed, and the resulting slope is indicated on each panel, in units of mas yr^{-1} per magnitude in $(B - I)$.

Figure 5.4: The proper motion is plotted versus the B magnitude for the three sub-population samples. The left panels refer to μ_x while the right panels refer to μ_y , in mas yr^{-1} . The RGB-MP is plotted in the bottom panels, the RGB-MInt in the intermediate panels and the RGB-a in the top panels. A linear fit to the 3σ clipped data is performed, and the resulting slope is indicated on each panel, in units of mas yr^{-1} per magnitude in B .

Sub-Populations	D	P
RGB-a vs MP	0.567	1.6×10^{-14}
RGB-a vs N97	0.455	3.0×10^{-6}
MP vs HB	0.003	0.46
MInt vs Norris et al. (1997)	0.13	0.33
MInt vs MP	0.264	6.5×10^{-11}
MInt vs RGB-a	0.396	5×10^{-6}

Table 5.1: Two-dimensional KS test for the proper motion distributions of the sub-populations discussed. D is the maximum difference in the cumulative distribution, P is the probability that the two populations are drawn from the same parent distribution. The RGB-a and RGB-MInt sample have proper motion distributions that are incompatible with that of the RGB-MP, while the HB and RGB-MP are perfectly compatible with each other.

We can thus safely conclude that the slopes found (that in most cases are still influenced by the clear presence of some outliers), are sufficiently small to have a negligible impact on the main result presented in this Chapter (Figure 5.1), and they basically compatible with zero slope, within the errors.

5.3 Statistical Significance

Once spurious instrumental effects have been excluded, we still need to prove that the observed result is not due to a statistical fluctuation. We start by performing a two-dimensional generalization of the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test (KS – Peacock, 1983; Fasano & Franceschini, 1987), applied to the proper motion distributions of different groups of stars. These include the RGB-MP, RGB-MInt and RGB-a stars, the HB control sample and the metal-rich stars defined by Norris et al. (1997) from their sample, i.e., stars with $[\text{Ca}/\text{H}] \geq -1.2$, mainly a subsample of the RGB-MInt population. The resulting maximum cumulative distances, D , and probabilities, P , that different pairs of these populations are extracted from the same parent distribution are reported in Table 5.1. Figure 5.5 (left panel) shows the cumulative distributions obtained for the three sub-samples, and the RGB-a clearly stands out as having a much different distribution.

The main conclusions from this test are that the RGB-MP and the HB proper motion distributions are fully compatible with each other, confirming the absence of spurious color-term related instrumental effects. The RGB-a and RGB-MInt proper motion distributions are instead not compatible with the RGB-MP. In particular, the probability that the proper motion distribution

Figure 5.5: The left panel shows cumulative distributions (ϕ) in the proper motion plane (see Figure 5.1) for the three sub-populations: RGB-MP (*heavy solid line*), RGB-MInt (*dotted line*) and RGB-a (*dashed line*). Plotted on the X-axis the geometric distance, d , of each star from the RGB-MP proper motion centroid, ($\mu_{RA} = -3.94, \mu_{DEC} = -4.40$) in mas yr^{-1} . Only stars with accurate proper motion measurements and with 99% membership probability (van Leeuwen et al., 2000) have been considered. The right panel shows the distribution of $|\delta\mu|$ for one million of “RGB-a-equivalent” sub-samples, randomly extracted from the RGB-MP population. Note that the observed $|\delta\mu|$ for the RGB-a is more than 10σ away from the mean of the extracted sub-samples.

observed for the RGB-a stars is drawn from the same parent distribution of the RGB-MP population is lower than 10^{-13} .

We obtain a similar answer by performing extensive Monte Carlo simulations: 10^6 sub-samples of the same size of the RGB-a sample have been randomly extracted from the dominant RGB-MP proper motion distribution. For each extracted sample, the total average mean proper motion modulus $|\delta\mu|$ has been computed: in no case it turned out to be larger than, or equal to, that observed for the RGB-a stars. Moreover, *all* of the extracted sub-samples have $|\delta\mu| \leq 0.4 \text{ mas yr}^{-1}$, i.e., always much lower than what actually observed for the RGB-a (Figure 5.5, right panel).

5.4 Results and Discussion

The above tests put the statistical significance of the result shown in Figure 5.1 beyond any possible doubt: *the RGB-a stars have a proper motion distribution*

Sub-Pop	v_{rad}	σ_v	N
MP	234.2	14.5	186
MInt	231.1	13.0	76
RGB-a	235.6	9.8	10

Table 5.2: Mean Radial velocities for the three sub-populations in ω Cen. Radial velocities are from Mayor et al. (1997), for RGB-a stars a few additional stars have been observed by Pancino et al. (2002).

that is not compatible with that of the bulk population of ω Cen.

On the other hand, the membership of the RGB-a stars to the ω Cen system is proven by the radial velocities. Table 5.2 lists the mean radial velocities for each sub-sample defined in Section 5.1. Though radial velocities have been measured only for ten RGB-a stars, their mean velocity turns out to be fully consistent with that measured for the other sub-populations. This proves that all the considered sub-populations are locked in the same gravitational potential.

Assuming a distance of 5360 pc for the cluster (Thompson et al., 2001), the absolute differential proper motion of the RGB-a population corresponds to a total mean tangential velocity of $v_t \simeq 19.8 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ with respect to the main system, in excellent agreement with the velocity dispersion measured in the core of ω Centauri (Mayor et al., 1997; van Leeuwen et al., 2000). By combining this estimate with the difference in the radial velocity between the RGB-a and MP stars ($\Delta v_r = 1.4 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ – see Table 5.2), we obtain a total mean velocity $v_{tot} \sim 20 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, still significantly lower than the half-mass escape velocity for ω Cen ($v_{esc} = 44 \text{ km s}^{-1}$), as recently estimated by Gnedin et al. (2002). The observed bulk motion of the RGB-a stars is fully consistent with being driven by the potential well of the whole cluster. We can thus conclude that *the RGB-a population is a coherently moving group of stars, gravitationally bound to the ω Cen system.*

This strongly suggest that the RGB-a sub-population had an (at least partially) independent origin with respect to the bulk of the cluster population (RGB-MP and/or RGB-Mint stars). This conclusion is also supported by other observational results. For example, the preliminary spatial distribution analysis performed in Chapter 3 shows that the spatial distribution of the RGB-a stars is elongated perpendicularly to the major axis of the dominant MP population of ω Centauri. This is confirmed by the detailed analysis in Chapter 6, where other evidence concerning the structure of the RGB-a is

presented. Furthermore, the abundance analysis performed in Chapter 4 shows that the RGB-a stars are less α -enhanced than the other sub-populations in ω Cen, suggesting that the interstellar medium from which they formed could have been polluted by SNIa ejecta, as opposed to *all* the other cluster stars (see Chapters 2 and Chapter 4, and references therein).

In the simplest conceivable scenario, the RGB-a stars originated as an independent stellar system, now trapped and disrupting in the potential well of ω Cen. Since the chance of capturing a completely independent object orbiting in the halo of the Galaxy is highly unlikely, it is reasonable to presume that the accreted system was a former satellite of ω Cen. This fact would be in agreement with the hypothesis that ω Cen is in fact the relic of a larger galaxy, partially disrupted by the Galactic tidal field (as suggested by Freeman, 1993; Lee et al., 1999; Dinescu, Girard & van Altena, 1999; Majewski et al., 2000). If this is the case, we are witnessing the process of hierarchical merging, simultaneously occurring on two very different scales: the ω Cen system is merging into the Milky Way and the RGB-a system is merging into ω Cen. High resolution Cold Dark Matter (CDM) models (Moore et al., 1998) predict that hierarchical clustering processes do occur down to the dwarf-galaxy scale ($M \sim 10^7 M_\odot$) even at the present day. Apparently, we have found an *in vivo* example, suggesting that hierarchical merging occurs also on sub-galactic scales ($M \sim 10^{4-5} M_\odot$).

Without a detailed knowledge of the structural parameters for the RGB-a system, no quantitative conclusion can be made concerning the timescales involved in the accretion of the RGB-a by ω Cen. However, as an approximate criterium, we can assume that an accreted self-gravitating stellar system can resist the tidal field stress of the main accreting system if its density is larger than the average density of the host system at its orbital radius (Oh, Lin, & Aarseth, 1995; Burkert, 1997). From the data at our disposal (Chapters 3 and 6), we can roughly estimate that the RGB-a population has a central density comparable to that of the MP population and a *core radius* significantly smaller ($r_c^{RGB-a} \sim 0.5r_c^{MP}$) than that of the main MP population. Then, according to equation 18 by Gerhard (2000), the RGB-a system is expected to dissolve under the tidal strain of ω Cen if its orbital radius is lower than $\sim 1r_c^{MP}$, i.e. the “dangerous” zone for the accreted RGB-a should be limited to the *core* of ω Cen.

Chapter 6

Spatial distribution

In this Chapter we present a detailed analysis of the spatial distribution of the stellar populations ω Cen. Preliminary evidence for a different spatial distribution of the three RGB sub-populations defined in Chapter 3 has already been given in Section 3.4. From a more detailed, two-dimensional statistical analysis, we confirm here that the metal-rich populations (RGB-MInt and RGB-a) have a spatial distribution which is significantly different from the metal-poor (RGB-MP) dominant population. In particular: *(i)* the different sub-populations have different centroids and *(ii)* the metal-poor population is elongated along the E-W direction, while the metal-rich populations are oriented along the orthogonal direction, i.e., N-S. The evidence presented here can partially explain the weird spatial metallicity segregation found by Jurcsik (1998), and further supports the hypothesis that different sub-populations in ω Cen might have had different origins.

6.1 Surface density distributions

To analyse in detail the structural properties of the three RGB sub-populations defined in Chapter 3 (see Figures 3.6 and 3.7), we have used the three photometric samples, with $B < 16$, defined in Chapter 3: the RGB-MP containing 2630 stars, the RGB-MInt containing 816 stars and the RGB-a containing 128 stars.

We computed the surface density distributions of each sub-population, using a fixed kernel estimator algorithm (Silverman, 1986; Merritt, Meylan & Mayor, 1997; Seleznev, 1998), with a kernel half-width of 500 pixels¹ and a grid of 100 pixel cells. The resulting surface density plots are shown in Figure 6.1, where the isodensity contour lines shown are normalized to the

¹In what follows, it is useful to bear in mind that the WFI scale is 0.238 arcseconds per pixel. Thus, 100 pixels correspond approximately to 24 arcseconds.

Figure 6.1: Isodensity contour lines for the three RGB samples defined in the text: the RGB-MP (upper panel), the RGB-MInt (middle panel) and the RGB-a (lower panel). The contour lines are normalized to their peak density and are plotted in steps of 10% of the peak density. In all panels the axes show the distance from the cluster center (700 ± 20 pix, 1900 ± 20 pix), in arcminutes.

Population	<i>D</i>	<i>P</i>
RGB-a vs. RGB-MP	0.171	0.012
RGB-MInt vs. RGB-MP	0.068	0.039
RGB-MInt vs. RGB-a	0.117	0.225

Table 6.1: Results of the two-dimensional generalization of the K-S test for the three sub-populations. The first column shows the populations that are actually compared, the second shows the maximum difference in the cumulative distributions D , while the third column shows the derived probability P that the two populations are drawn from the same parent distribution.

maximum density of each distribution, in steps of 10%. From now on, we will refer to each isodensity level using the fraction of the peak value, i.e., 0.3 for the isodensity level corresponding to 30% of the peak value. The peak density values are: 48.3 stars arcmin⁻² for the RGB-MP, 14.6 stars arcmin⁻² for the RGB-MInt and 2.3 stars arcmin⁻² for the RGB-a.

A first, qualitative comparison of the three distributions shown in Figure 6.1 reveals the following general facts:

- The RGB-MP population is clearly elongated along the E-W direction, reflecting the well known elliptical shape of the whole system. The main peak position is consistent with the cluster centroid estimated by Pancino et al. (2000).
- Both the RGB-a and the RGB-MInt populations have perturbed isodensity contour lines, showing structures similar to bubbles, shells and/or tails. While in the case of the RGB-a the complexity increases in the outer parts, where it is almost certainly due to low number statistics, in the case of the RGB-MInt we find complex structures in the central parts, where data points are more numerous.
- The RGB-MInt population is clearly elongated along the N-S direction in the inner parts, while in the external parts it seems to become elongated in the E-W direction. The main peak lies south of the RGB-MP peak, with a possible secondary peak north of it. This secondary feature gives an evident asymmetric shape to the distribution, that was already noted in Chapter 3.
- The RGB-a population is also elongated along the N-S direction in its inner parts; its main peak lies north of the RGB-MP peak.

Population	$r_{e,90\%}$	$R_{90\%}$	$r_{e,60\%}$	$R_{60\%}$
RGB-MP	213.8 ± 6.5	1.00	578.9 ± 13.5	1.00
RGB-MInt	169.3 ± 15.9	0.79	601.7 ± 7.6	1.04
RGB-a	66.2 ± 5.5	0.31	323.1 ± 5.0	0.56

Table 6.2: The equivalent radius, in pixels, of the ellipses used to approximate the 90% isodensity contour lines (close to the peak) is shown in column 1 ($r_{e,90\%}$) and its ratio with the radius of the RGB-MP population in column 2 ($R_{90\%}$). Columns 3 and 4 show the corresponding values ($r_{e,60\%}$ and $R_{60\%}$) for the ellipses used to approximate the 60% isodensity contour level (close to half maximum).

A simple monodimensional Kolmogorov-Smirnov test (K-S, see e.g., Press et al., 1997) as a function of a radial coordinate is not sufficient to properly assess the significance of these features. We thus used a two-dimensional generalization of the K-S statistical test, which was proposed and investigated with Monte-Carlo experiments by Fasano & Franceschini (1987), as a variant of an earlier idea by Peacock (1983). This test, similarly to the usual K-S test, quantifies the probability P that two (two-dimensional) distributions are extracted from the same parent distribution, using a more sophisticated definition of the maximum difference D in the cumulative distributions.

The results are summarized in Table 6.1. The very low probabilities obtained in the comparison of the RGB-MP population with both the RGB-MInt and the RGB-a ensures us that their spatial distributions are significantly different, i.e., they cannot be drawn from the same parent distribution. On the other hand, the probability obtained in the comparison between the RGB-MInt and the RGB-a populations confirms that they are not significantly different from each other.

We can also notice from Figure 6.1 that the RGB-a population appears *more* concentrated than the RGB-MP one, while we cannot say much about the RGB-MInt population, which has a complicated shape in its inner isodensity contour lines. A more quantitative evaluation confirms this impression: Table 6.2 reports the equivalent radii² of the three sub-populations, calculated with the ellipse parameters derived in Section 6.2, for the 0.9 and 0.6 isodensity contour lines. The RGB-a equivalent radii are ~ 2 -3 times smaller than the RGB-MP correspondent radii.

²The equivalent radius for an ellipse of semi-axes a and b is defined as $r_e = \sqrt{ab}$, i.e., the radius of a circle with the same area.

Figure 6.2: Example of the approximation of the 0.9 isodensity contour line with an ellipse, for the RGB-MP. *Top Panel:* The black dots represent the points in the 20 pixels grid that are closer to 90% of the peak value; the solid ellipse is the best fit. *Bottom Panel* Same as above, but this time with the 50 pixel grid: the final ellipse fit is slightly different.

Figure 6.3: Ellipse parameters notation: O is the ellipse center; X and Y are the axes of the usual cartesian reference frame, while ψ and r are the angular and radial coordinates in the polar coordinate system; a and b are the ellipse semi-major and semi-minor axes, respectively; φ is the major axis inclination with respect to the X axis.

6.2 Ellipticity

To describe in a more quantitative way the shape and structure of the sub-populations defined in Chapter 3, we fitted ellipses to the isodensity contours of each sample. The spatial distributions were derived as in Section 6.1, with the same kernel, but using higher resolution grids of 20 and 50 pixel cells. We used the finer grid (20 pix) for the internal regions that are more densely populated, i.e., within the 0.6 isodensity level, and the coarser grid (50 pix) for the outer regions. As in Section 6.1, we defined densities in units of maximum (peak) density for each distribution, and we chose isodensity levels going from 90% to 10% of the peak density, in steps of 10%. Ellipses were fitted to each isodensity line, defined by those grid nodes that bracket the chosen density value (see Figure 6.2). The best-fit ellipses are hereafter designated with the same notation used for the isodensity contours in Figure 6.1, i.e., 0.9 for the 90% ellipse and so on.

Kholopov (1953) suggested that the best way to approximate equal density lines with ellipses in globular clusters is to use polar coordinates (r, ψ) . This method has the advantage that the deviations of points from the ellipse along the radial direction are close to the deviations in the direction perpendicular to the ellipse. In polar coordinates, the ellipses have the following form:

Population	$X_C(\text{pix})$	$Y_C(\text{pix})$	$d(\text{pix})$	$d(\prime\prime)$
RGB-tot	689±8	1906±12	—	—
RGB-MP	701±9	1954±17	49±24	12±6
RGB-MInt	651±10	1671±16	238±24	57±6
RGB-a	761±9	2194±8	297±19	71±5
ω Cen	700±20	1900±20	12±32	3±8

Table 6.3: The density peaks of the whole RGB sample and of the three sub-samples (in pixels), represented by the centers of the 80% isodensity level fits. The distance of each population from the RGB total sample is calculated, both in pixels and in arcseconds. The last row reports the corresponding distance between the present RGB global sample and the cluster centroid determined by Pancino et al. (2000).

$$\frac{1}{r^2} = A + B \cdot \sin 2\psi + C \cdot \cos 2\psi \quad (6.1)$$

The relations of the coefficients A , B and C with the usual ellipse parameters (Figure 6.3) are

$$A = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{a^2} + \frac{1}{b^2} \right)$$

$$B = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{a^2} - \frac{1}{b^2} \right) \cdot \sin 2\varphi$$

$$C = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{a^2} - \frac{1}{b^2} \right) \cdot \cos 2\varphi$$

As demonstrated by earlier studies (Geyer, Nelles & Hopp, 1983), the “a priori” adoption of the cluster center position can produce errors (i.e., an overestimation) on the ellipticity estimate. This point is even more important in our particular case, since we suspect that the centroids of the three sub-populations differ from each other. Therefore, we determined the coordinates of each ellipse center as the mean coordinates of the input points on each isodensity line. The ellipse coefficients A , B and C were determined by least square approximation with singular value decomposition (Press et al., 1997). An example of the result of the fitting procedure is shown in Figure 6.2.

6.2.1 Ellipse centers

Following the procedure described above, we determined the ellipse centers for each of the three sub-populations defined in Chapter 3, and for each isodensity level. The same procedure has been applied, for sake of comparison, also to the total RGB sample defined as the union of the three sub-samples. The results are listed in Table 6.3: the RGB-MInt and RGB-a centers are significantly

Figure 6.4: Displacement of the ellipse centers for the three-sub-populations. Ellipses are denominated along the abscissae in fractions of the peak value, as described in the text. The shaded area represents the cluster center position determined by Pancino et al. (2000), ($X_C = 700 \pm 20$ pix, $Y_C = 1900 \pm 20$ pix). The three sub-populations are marked with different symbols: *filled dots* for the RGB-MP, *filled squares* for the RGB-MInt and *filled triangles* for the RGB-a. The *top panel* shows the displacements in the E-W direction, i.e., along the X CCD axis, while the *bottom panel* shows the displacements along the N-S direction, i.e., the Y CCD axis. The errorbars are smaller than the symbols.

different from the RGB-MP center. We can also compare with the center position found by Pancino et al. (2000), which is $(700 \pm 20, 1900 \pm 20)$ in the WFI pixel system. As we can see, the center of the global RGB sample is perfectly compatible with that estimate.

A look at the center position trend with the isodensity level (Figure 6.4) shows that the RGB-MP, dominating the cluster population, has a quite stable center position and coincides reasonably well with the center of ω Cen measured by Pancino et al. (2000), except for its two inner isodensity levels. The RGB-MInt center is slightly displaced to the east ($\sim 10''$) and significantly to the south ($\sim 1'$), at least for the inner fits. This reflects the behaviour seen in Figure 6.1: in the central parts the main peak of the population is clearly S-E of the RGB-MP population, while the behaviour in the external parts becomes smoother. The RGB-a center is instead slightly displaced to the west

Population	grid	ellipse	$(b/a) \pm \delta(b/a)$	$\varphi \pm \delta\varphi$
RGB-tot	20	0.9	0.92 ± 0.01	49.2 ± 5.7
	20	0.8	0.93 ± 0.01	26.3 ± 4.9
	20	0.7	0.93 ± 0.02	17.5 ± 3.5
	20	0.6	0.93 ± 0.01	19.5 ± 2.9
	50	0.5	0.93 ± 0.02	18.0 ± 4.3
	50	0.4	0.93 ± 0.02	20.9 ± 4.7
	50	0.3	0.92 ± 0.02	31.9 ± 3.3
	50	0.2	0.89 ± 0.01	32.0 ± 2.7
	50	0.1	0.84 ± 0.01	3.7 ± 1.7
	50	0.05	0.84 ± 0.03	6.0 ± 1.2
RGB-MP	20	0.9	0.82 ± 0.05	-10.4 ± 3.1
	20	0.8	0.80 ± 0.12	3.8 ± 2.4
	20	0.7	0.79 ± 0.05	7.0 ± 1.7
	20	0.6	0.81 ± 0.04	7.0 ± 1.4
	50	0.5	0.84 ± 0.03	12.4 ± 2.6
	50	0.4	0.85 ± 0.02	15.8 ± 2.7
	50	0.3	0.88 ± 0.02	22.7 ± 3.2
	50	0.2	0.90 ± 0.01	41.9 ± 2.8
	50	0.1	0.85 ± 0.04	8.6 ± 2.2
	50	0.05	0.85 ± 0.02	10.9 ± 1.6
RGB-MInt	20	0.9	0.85 ± 0.16	-8.0 ± 8.9
	20	0.8	0.73 ± 0.10	-6.1 ± 2.4
	20	0.6	0.75 ± 0.02	100.2 ± 0.8
	50	0.5	0.77 ± 0.03	100.8 ± 1.6
	50	0.4	0.87 ± 0.03	102.2 ± 2.8
	50	0.3	0.90 ± 0.02	33.0 ± 6.4
	50	0.2	0.88 ± 0.02	24.3 ± 3.8
	50	0.1	0.83 ± 0.06	6.3 ± 2.2
RGB-a	20	0.9	0.66 ± 0.11	47.2 ± 10.7
	20	0.8	0.86 ± 0.12	97.9 ± 7.2
	20	0.7	0.81 ± 0.04	112.7 ± 4.7
	20	0.6	0.83 ± 0.03	108.7 ± 2.9

Table 6.4: Axial ratio and orientation for the best-fit ellipses for the whole RGB sample and for each sub-sample. Each best-fit ellipse is designated with the fraction of the peak density for each population, as described in the text. The axial ratio (b/a) and the inclination angle φ (i.e., the angle in degrees, counted from west to north) are shown.

($\sim 10''$), and significantly to the north ($\sim 1'$), at least for the few isodensity contour lines that we were able to fit with ellipses. Again, this reflects what seen in Figure 6.1. We recall here that the literature estimates of ω Cen's core radius go from a maximum of $r_c = 2.58'$ (Trager, King & Djorgovski, 1995) to a minimum of $r_c = 1.4'$ (van Leeuwen et al., 2000), so the observed displacements are comparable in size to the core radius of ω Cen.

6.2.2 Flattening and orientation

As shown in Table 6.4, the three sub-populations axial ratios have similar behaviours, within the errorbars. They do not show dramatic trends moving away from the center, with both the RGB-MP and the RGB-MInt becoming slowly rounder away from their density peaks. For the RGB-a, due to the low number of objects in the external parts, only the inner isodensity levels could be fitted. The weighted averages of the axial ratios shown in Table 6.4 are: $\langle b/a \rangle = 0.81 \pm 0.01$ for the RGB-MP, $\langle b/a \rangle = 0.81 \pm 0.06$ for the RGB-MInt and $\langle b/a \rangle = 0.78 \pm 0.11$ for the RGB-a.

To compare our results with previous work, we performed the same measurements on the entire RGB sample, resulting from the union of the three sub-samples defined in Chapter 3. In particular, Figure 6.5 shows the comparison with Geyer, Nelles & Hopp (1983, see their Table 4): the overall agreement is reasonably good, with a marginal discrepancy in the region between $2'.5$ and $4'.5$ from the cluster center. Moreover, our average axial ratio and ellipticity ($\varepsilon = 1 - b/a$) for the whole RGB sample, $\langle b/a \rangle = 0.89 \pm 0.04$ and $\langle \varepsilon \rangle = 0.11 \pm 0.04$, compare well with previous results like $\langle b/a \rangle = 0.83 \pm 0.03$ (White & Shawl, 1987), $\langle \varepsilon \rangle = 0.12 \pm 0.04$ (Geyer, Nelles & Hopp, 1983), or $\langle \varepsilon \rangle = 0.077$ (van Leeuwen et al., 2000).

Finally, while the flattenings of the three sub-populations appear rather similar, the orientations of the best-fit ellipses are instead quite different (see Table 6.4). The RGB-MP major axis is always close to the E-W direction, with $\langle \varphi \rangle \sim -4^\circ \pm 10$, and its inclination seems to increase slowly with the distance from the cluster center, although at these low flattenings the uncertainty on the inclination angle can be substantially higher than the formal errors quoted in Table 6.4 (Geyer, Nelles & Hopp, 1983). The RGB-MInt shows instead a complex structure in the central parts (Figure 6.1), with a possible double peak. But its 0.6–0.4 isodensity levels (the most reliable ones) are always inclined along the N-S direction, with $\langle \varphi \rangle \sim 100^\circ$, while the outer parts suddenly drop to $\langle \varphi \rangle \sim 25^\circ$, much closer to the E-W direction. Finally, the

Figure 6.5: Axial ratio for the whole RGB population (black dots), compared with the measures by Geyer et al. (1983), which is represented by a shaded area (see both their Table 4 and our Table 6.4).

RGB-a is oriented along the N-S direction, although ellipses could be fit only to the inner parts, with $\langle \varphi \rangle$ close to 90° – 100° , except for the innermost fit. Again, these quantitative estimates closely reflect what seen in Figure 6.1.

6.3 Metallicity segregation

Recently Jurcsik (1998), using a compilation of good-quality spectroscopic data from the literature, has shown that the bright giants ($V \leq 12.75$) in ω Cen, belonging to the two metallicity groups with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \leq -1.75$ and $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \geq -1.25$, have a weird spatial distribution. Each of the two groups occupies one half of the cluster: no star of one group is found on the other side and the two centroids are separated by $6.2'$ (see her Figure 1). The separation line runs approximately perpendicular to the apparent minor axis of the cluster, which is roughly oriented towards the Galactic center: the most metal rich giants are on the southern half, that faces the Galaxy.

Ikuta & Arimoto (2000) questioned this effect. They used the same compilation of data and they showed that no spatial segregation of stars with different metallicity is evident. However, we would like to note here that, as clearly stated by Jurcsik (1998), the effect is only visible if one applies the specified selections, i.e., *only for bright stars of the two extreme metallicity groups*. The effect was instead partially confirmed by Hilker & Richtler (2000), who measured abundances of stars in ω Cen with Strömngren metallicity indices. Their Figure 15 shows a clear segregation of the most metal-rich stars in the

southern half of the cluster, but they could not confirm the segregation of the most metal-poor stars.

The metal-rich group in Jurcsik (1998), with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \geq -1.25$, is mainly a sub-sample of our RGB-MInt population, which has a pronounced peak just $\sim 1'$ south of the cluster center (see Figure 6.1 and Table 6.3), a value that is roughly compatible with Jurcsik estimate ($\sim 3'$). We thus easily explain the observed segregation of her metal-rich group, since when one draws randomly a sample of metal-rich stars, there is a higher probability to find them close to the main peak of the density distribution, i.e., in the southern half of the cluster.

Unfortunately, Jurcsik (1998) metal-poor group, with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \leq -1.75$, is instead a sub-sample of our RGB-MP, or more precisely it represents the lowest metallicity tail of the RGB-MP, which we cannot properly isolate from our photometry alone. If the effect she found will be confirmed in the future, it could mean that an additional, metal-poor sub-population exists in ω Cen, with its own distinct properties (see Chapter 8). Otherwise, the spatial segregation of that group of stars could also be a purely statistical fluctuation, explaining why Hilker & Richtler (2000) were not able to confirm it. More data on abundances of a significant sample of stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \leq -1.75$ are needed to completely explain this second half of the puzzle (see Chapter 9).

6.4 Summary

Using the sub-samples defined in Chapter 3, we have shown that the three RGB sub-populations are significantly different in their spatial distribution and structural properties. In particular:

- Both the RGB-MInt and the RGB-a main density peaks are shifted by $\sim 1'$ with respect to the cluster center.
- Both the RGB-a and the RGB-MInt populations are elongated on a direction that is perpendicular to the elongation of the RGB-MP population.
- The RGB-a population is significantly more concentrated than the RGB-MP population. No firm conclusion can be reached for the RGB-MInt, due to the complex isodensity contour line's shapes in its central parts.
- Both the RGB-MInt and the RGB-a show complex and perturbed isodensity contour lines, resembling bubbles, shells and tails. While for

the outer isodensity contours this can be due to statistical undersampling (especially for the RGB-a), in the inner parts these features are probably real.

- Finally, we were able to explain the metal-rich part of the weird spatial metallicity segregation, found by Jurcsik (1998) and confirmed by Hilker & Richtler (2000), thanks to the peculiar surface density distribution of the RGB-MInt and, in particular, to its center displacement with respect to the RGB-MP center.

These findings point towards a different dynamical origin for the RGB-a and RGB-MInt, with respect to the RGB-MP and they will be discussed in the framework of the accepted theories on the formation and evolution of ω Cen, in Chapter 9.

Chapter 7

Using the WFI photometric Catalog to calibrate the RGB-Tip method

In this Chapter we present an interesting side application of the huge photometric database presented in Chapter 3: the empirical calibration of an excellent distance indicator. The absolute I magnitude of the Tip of the Red Giant Branch (M_I^{TRGB}) is in fact one of the most promising Standard Candles actually used in astrophysics as a fundamental pillar for the Cosmological Distance Scale. With the aim of improving the observational basis of its calibration, we have obtained an accurate estimate of the (M_I^{TRGB}) for ω Cen, using the huge optical photometric catalog presented in Chapter 3 and the direct distance estimate for ω Cen, recently obtained by Thompson et al. (2001), from the study of a detached eclipsing binary. The derived value $M_I^{TRGB} = -4.04 \pm 0.12$ provides, at present, the most accurate empirical zero-point for the calibration of the $M_I^{TRGB} - [\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ relation, at $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -1.7$.

Part of the work presented in this Chapter has been published in Bellazzini, Ferraro & Pancino (2001). We are presently working on the extension of the RGB-Tip calibration to the J and K IR bands (see Ferraro et al., 2000), using the large IR photometric database presented in Chapter 3.

7.1 Introduction

While the use of the luminosity of the Tip of the Red Giant Branch (TRGB) as a standard candle dates back to 1930 (see Madore & Freedman, 1995, and references therein), the development of the method as a safe and viable technique is relatively recent (Lee et al., 1993). In a few years it has become a widely adopted technique, finding fruitful application also within the *HST Key*

Figure 7.1: $(V - I)_0^{TRGB}$ as a function of $[Fe/H]$ for the six clusters studied by Da Costa & Armandroff (1990). All data are taken from Da Costa & Armandroff (1990). The curve represents the best fits to the data, the corresponding equation is also reported. The *rms* scatter is 0.04 mag.

project on the Extragalactic Distance Scale Ferrarese et al. (see 2000a,b, and references therein). The underlying physical processes are clearly understood and well rooted in the theory of stellar evolution (Madore & Freedman, 1995).

The method is particularly useful to estimate distances to those stellar systems that do not contain Cepheids, such as early type galaxies, and it can be applied to galaxies as far as ~ 12 Mpc with the current instrumentation. The key observable quantity is the magnitude of the bright end (the tip) of the RGB, that corresponds to a sharp cut-off in the RGB Luminosity Function (LF), measured in the Cousin's *I* passband¹. In this passband the magnitude of the tip shows a very weak (if any) dependence on metallicity (Da Costa & Armandroff, 1990). The feature can be identified by applying the Sobel's filter, an edge-detection algorithm, to the LF of the upper RGB (see Sakai, Madore, & Freedman, 1996, for a standard application²). The possible biases have been well characterized and quantified by means of numerical simulations by Madore & Freedman (1995).

¹Hereafter, when we will refer to the *I* passband, we will always mean the *Cousin's I* passband, unless we specify otherwise.

²From now on, we will refer to their method for the detection of the RGB Tip as to the *standard analysis*.

In this context, we are performing an extensive study of the RGB population in GGC. In particular, we have derived an accurate calibration of the RGB photometric properties as a function of metallicity, both in the optical and in the IR (Ferraro et al., 1999a, 2000). The final aim of this program is to use stellar populations in GGCs as *calibrators* for the RGB-Tip method, taking advantage of the large samples that can be easily assembled with the new generation of array detectors and cameras. In this Chapter we present (i) a very robust empirical calibration of M_I^{TRGB} at $[Fe/H] \sim -1.7$, derived by applying the *standard analysis* to a very large sample of RGB stars in the globular cluster ω Cen (NGC 5139), and based on a direct distance estimate recently obtained by Thompson et al. (2001) for a detached eclipsing binary in this cluster, and (ii) a new *empirical* calibration of the $M_I^{TRGB} - [Fe/H]$ relation based on a large, homogeneous IR database of RGB stars in GGC, recently published by Ferraro et al. (2000).

The aim of this paper is to provide a first, robust pillar for a well rooted empirical calibration of M_I^{TRGB} as a standard candle, extending over a wide range in metallicity. This will constitute the basis for a secure application of the RGB Tip method as an extragalactic distance indicator.

7.2 A new $M_I^{TRGB} - [Fe/H]$ relation

The most widely adopted calibration of the absolute I magnitude of the RGB Tip ($M_I^{TRGB} = M_{bol}^{TRGB} - BC_I$) was derived by Lee et al. (1993) from the following relations, which give the bolometric magnitude of the tip (M_{bol}^{TRGB}) as a function of metallicity:

$$M_{bol}^{TRGB} = -0.19[Fe/H] - 3.81 \quad (7.1)$$

and the I bolometric correction (BC_I) as a function of the intrinsic color $(V - I)_0$:

$$BC_I = 0.881 - 0.243(V - I)_0 \quad (7.2)$$

both obtained by Da Costa & Armandroff (1990). Using accurate V and I photometry of a small number of RGB stars³ in eight selected globular clusters in the metallicity range $-2.2 \leq [Fe/H] \leq -0.7$, Da Costa & Armandroff (1990) estimated the apparent I magnitude of the RGB Tip (I^{TRGB}) as the

³From 20 to 110 stars per cluster were observed by Da Costa & Armandroff (1990) in the upper ~ 4 mag of each RGB.

magnitude of the brightest and reddest giant in their samples. They converted I^{TRGB} to absolute magnitudes by adopting the RR Lyrae distance scale $M_V(\text{RRLy}) = 0.17[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] + 0.82$, from Lee et al. (1993), and finally to M_{bol} using Equation 7.2. Note that, in this context, the most relevant observational fact presented by Da Costa & Armandroff (1990) is that $M_I^{TRGB} = -4.0 \pm 0.1$, in the sampled range of metallicity.

The above calibrations suffer from two major sources of uncertainty:

- The evolution of stars along the RGB becomes faster as their luminosity increases along the path toward the RGB Tip. Thus, most of the cluster light has to be observed to correctly sample the fastest evolutionary phases (Renzini & Fusi Pecci, 1988). Madore & Freedman (1995) stated that acceptable detections of the RGB Tip can be obtained if more than 50 stars are sampled within 1 mag from the tip and that fine estimates can be obtained only sampling more than 100 stars in that range. The Da Costa & Armandroff (1990) samples are much poorer than this, therefore their I^{TRGB} estimates may be affected by the systematics associated with small number statistics.
- The RR Lyrae distance scale is quite uncertain. While there is now some agreement on the slope of the $M_V(\text{RRLy}) - [\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ relation, the actual zero points is still hardly debated (see Cacciari, 1999, for a recent review).

The most recent calibration of the $M_{bol}^{TRGB} - [Fe/H]$ relation has been obtained by Ferraro et al. (2000), from homogeneous near-infrared photometry of a large sample of RGB stars in nine GGC. Several hundred giants were observed in the upper ~ 4 mag of each RGB. Moreover, the data-set presented by Ferraro et al. (2000) extends to a much higher metallicity with respect to Da Costa & Armandroff (1990), covering the range $-2.2 \leq [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \leq -0.2$. The RGB Tip was identified by using the brightest non-variable RGB star in the K band. Ferraro et al. (2000) adopted the new distance scale presented by Ferraro et al. (1999a) which, although still based on the HB, was obtained with a new semi-empirical approach (see Ferraro et al., 1999a, for details). Ferraro et al. (2000) provided M_{bol}^{TRGB} as a function of $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ in two metallicity scales: (i) the Carretta & Gratton (1997) scale and (ii) the *global* metallicity ($[\text{M}/\text{H}]$) scale, which takes into account also the α -elements abundances. To obtain a more direct comparison with the calibration by Lee et al. (1993), we used the data from Ferraro et al. (2000) to derive M_{bol}^{TRGB} as a function of $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ in the Zinn & West (1984) metallicity scale, and obtained:

$$M_{bol}^{TRGB} = -0.12[Fe/H] - 3.76 \quad (7.3)$$

The larger samples used by Ferraro et al. (2000), the wider metallicity range covered and the minor impact of the extinction and bolometric corrections on infrared luminosities, suggest that Equation 7.3 has to be preferred to Equation 7.1. Note, however, that the final $M_I^{TRGB} - [Fe/H]$ relations derived by the two independent calibrations of M_{bol}^{TRGB} are in agreement within the uncertainties (see Section 7.3 and Figure 7.4).

In order to derive the M_I^{TRGB} from the new empirical calibration, we need to combine Equation 7.3 with Equation 7.2, following the relation $M_I^{TRGB} = M_{bol}^{TRGB} - BC_I$. The actual BC_I depends implicitly on metallicity, since BC_I depends on the $(V - I)$ color of the RGB Tip (Equation 7.2) which, in turn, depends on metallicity. To make such a dependence explicit, we plot in Figure 7.1 $(V - I)_0^{TRGB}$ as a function of $[Fe/H]$ for the six clusters studied by Da Costa & Armandroff (1990). The data are best fitted by a second order polynomial which is also reported in Figure 7.1. We adopt this relation to eliminate the dependency of M_I^{TRGB} on $(V - I)$ color and we finally obtain the following relation:

$$M_I^{TRGB} = 0.14[Fe/H]^2 + 0.48[Fe/H] - 3.66 \quad (7.4)$$

which provides the calibration of M_I^{TRGB} as a function of metallicity only, in the Zinn & West (1984) scale.

Equations 7.3 and 7.4 represent a substantial improvement with respect to previous work, since they are based on the largest IR RGB samples in GGCs available in the literature. Note that Ferraro et al. (2000) sampled a significant fraction of the cluster light (up to $\sim 80\%$). However even in this large data-set the number of RGB stars in the upper magnitude from the RGB Tip is < 50 in all cases, and the brightest star detection is possibly prone to low number statistics effects. This is due, in most cases, to intrinsic poorness of the cluster population, since the majority of GGCs simply *do not contain a sufficient number of RGB stars* to adequately sample the upper RGB. Thus extensive observations of the most massive GGCs are urged in order to properly calibrate the above relations. In the following on the use of the huge photometric database presented in Chapter 3 to set strong empirical constraints on the RGB Tip absolute magnitude of ω Cen.

7.3 The determination of the RGB-Tip in ω Cen

ω Cen is the most luminous GC in the Milky Way system, therefore even the fastest evolutionary phases are well populated and it is possible to observe a quite large sample of RGB stars, fulfilling the prescriptions of Madore & Freedman (1995). The absolute photometric calibration of the WFI B and I photometry is accurate to within ± 0.02 mag. The observed field extends over an area enclosing 90% of the cluster light. Thus, virtually *almost all the bright stars of ω Cen are included in the adopted database*. Considering that ω Cen is the most luminous globular cluster of the whole Galaxy, this photometric database is the largest sample that can be obtained in the Galactic globular cluster system.

Moreover, as discussed in Chapter 2, ω Cen was the first globular in which a detached eclipsing binary system, *OGLEGC17*, was discovered (Kaluzny et al., 1996). This enabled Thompson et al. (2001) to obtain a direct distance estimate, independent of any other distance scale. The distance of detached, eclipsing double line spectroscopic binaries can in fact be obtained by coupling the physical parameters of the system with the relations between color and surface brightness by Barnes & Evans (1976). This method is basically *geometrical*, since the distance is obtained by comparison between the linear and angular size of the binary members (see Lacy (1977); Kruszewski & Semeniuk (1999)).

The final distance obtained by Thompson et al. (2001) is $d = 5385 \pm 300$ pc, which corresponds to $(m - M)_0 = 13.65 \pm 0.11$, if we assume their adopted extinction value, $E(B - V) = 0.13 \pm 0.02$. Their result is in good agreement with previous estimates. According to Thompson et al. (2001), the error bar on the distance modulus can be significantly reduced as soon as better light and velocity curves will be obtained for *OGLEGC17*. Thus, a significant improvement of the quoted measure of the distance modulus has to be expected in the near future. A further independent distance estimate, based on a geometrical method, could soon be provided also by the comparison of the linear and the angular velocity dispersion from the large database of proper motions by van Leeuwen et al. (2000), once supported by detailed dynamical modeling.

In deriving M_I^{TRGB} another fundamental ingredient can still be greatly refined and improved in the near future: the *reddening*. For instance, Mateo et al. (1995) report that the $(V - I)_0$ color at minimum light of RRab variables

Figure 7.2: $(I, B - I)$ CMD of the brightest 3 mag of the RGB of ω Cen, from Pancino et al. (2000)

is universal and independent of metallicity. Thus, reliable $E(V - I)$ estimates can be obtained from the *observed* $(V - I)$ at minimum light and large samples would greatly improve the accuracy. For ω Cen, in particular, a V and I survey of RR Lyrae can potentially provide a reddening estimate with an uncertainty of ± 0.01 mag or lower, since this populous cluster contains more than 70 RRab (Rey et al., 2000).

In conclusion, ω Cen seems to fit all the requirements to obtain an excellent calibration of M_I^{TRGB} and still leaves considerable room for future improvements.

A possible caveat may be associated with the wide metallicity distribution observed in this cluster, discussed in Chapter 4. However, it has been shown that the largely dominant population is metal poor (Norris, Freeman & Mighell, 1996; Suntzeff & Kraft, 1996). The peak of such population occurs at $[Fe/H] \sim -1.7$ (Suntzeff & Kraft, 1996) and we will adopt this as the characteristic metallicity of the cluster.

7.3.1 M_I of the RGB-Tip in ω Cen

Figure 7.2 shows the $I, (B - I)$ CMD of the brightest 3 magnitudes in the RGB of ω Cen: 1777 stars are reported in this diagram, most of them being

RGB stars. The contribution of AGB stars is negligible for $I < 11$, and the photometric errors are lower than 0.02 mag in both passbands, over the whole magnitude range plotted in the diagram. The contamination by foreground sources is negligible in this region of the CMD and the crowding is not a serious concern for such bright stars in this nearby and relatively loose cluster. The RGB sample contains 185 stars in the upper magnitude bin, which is almost twice of what recommended by Madore & Freedman (1995) for an optimal detection of the RGB Tip.

The edge-detector filter is applied on a smoothed version of the LF of the RGB, following the *standard analysis* as described by Sakai, Madore, & Freedman (1996, see their appendix). In Figure 7.3 (panel a)) the RGB LF for $I < 11$ is reported. A sharp cut-off is clearly evident at $I \sim 9.8$. The same LF is shown in Figure 7.3 (panel b)) as a smoothed histogram, while the edge-detector filter response to the smoothed LF is reported in panel c). The main peak in the filter response indicates the cut-off point: the RGB Tip is clearly and unambiguously detected at $I = 9.84 \pm 0.1$, the associated uncertainty is the Half Width at Half Maximum (HWHM) of the peak.

Moreover, the large sample of giants observed in this cluster allows us to adopt a more refined approach to the quantification of the uncertainty, by applying a *bootstrap* technique (see Babu & Feigelson (1996), and references therein). To do this, we randomly extracted a subsample containing 80% of the stars from the global sample of all RGB stars with $I < 11$, we repeated the measure of I^{TRGB} on the extracted subsample with the same technique as above and recorded the final result. Panel d) in Figure 7.3 shows the distribution of 10,428 such estimates on randomly extracted subsamples: the mean of the distribution is $\langle I \rangle = 9.835$ and the standard deviation is $\sigma = 0.04$ mag. The estimate of I^{TRGB} turns out to be remarkably robust to statistical fluctuations, with 83% of the estimates falling within $\pm 1\sigma$ from the mean. We adopt the bootstrapped σ as the uncertainty on our estimate of the apparent I magnitude of the tip. The final result is: $I^{TRGB} = 9.84 \pm 0.04$.

It is now straightforward to provide M_I^{TRGB} of ω Cen as a function of distance modulus and reddening:

$$M_I^{TRGB} = 9.84(\pm 0.04) - K \cdot E(B - V) - (m - M)_0 \quad (7.5)$$

where $K = A_I/E(B - V)$, A_I is the amount of extinction in the I passband, $E(B - V)$ is the reddening and $(m - M)_0$ is the true distance modulus. Since the data-set samples virtually the whole cluster population

Figure 7.3: The LF for the RGB stars with $I < 11$ is shown as a histogram in *panel (a)* and as a smoothed histogram in *panel (b)*. The arrow in *panel (a)* indicates the cut off of the LF corresponding to the RGB Tip. The smoothed histogram is multiplied by an arbitrary constant to facilitate comparison with *panel (a)*. The response of the edge-detection algorithm is shown in *panel (c)*, while the distribution of the bootstrapped estimates is shown in *panel (d)*. The location of I^{TRGB} is unambiguously identified by the peaks in *panels (c)* and *(d)* at $I = 9.84 \pm 0.1$. The associated uncertainty is the Half Width at Half Maximum (HWHM) of the peak.

in this range of magnitudes, it is unlikely that the I^{TRGB} estimate will be significantly improved by new observations. On the other hand, all other terms of Equation 7.5 can be subject to substantial improvements in their estimates, as discussed in Section 7.3. Here we adopt the distance and reddening by Thompson et al. (2001) and the reddening laws by Dean, Warren & Cousins (1978)⁴, with the same assumptions of Da Costa & Armandroff (1990), i.e., $A_I \simeq 1.76E(B - V)$. We obtain:

$$M_I^{TRGB} = -4.04 \pm 0.12 \quad (7.6)$$

where *all* the sources of uncertainty have been taken into account. The main contributor to the error budget remains the estimate of the distance modulus.

7.4 Comparison with other calibrations

It is worth checking how the existing empirical and theoretical calibrations compare with the above estimate of M_I^{TRGB} , at the relevant metallicity $[Fe/H] \sim -1.7$. In Figure 7.4 our estimate of M_I^{TRGB} in ω Cen is reported as a *big black dot* in the M_I^{TRGB} vs. $[Fe/H]$ plane. The horizontal error bar represents the range in metallicity covered by the dominant population of the cluster (see Figure 11 in Suntzeff & Kraft, 1996).

The empirical calibrations discussed in Section 7.2 are also plotted: the *heavy solid curve* is the new calibration based on the large IR database by Ferraro et al. (2000, Equation 4), while the Lee et al. (1993) calibration (Equation 1 and 2 from Da Costa & Armandroff, 1990) has been converted to a function of metallicity, following the procedure described in Section 7.2, and it is plotted as a *dotted-dashed curve*. The horizontal *long dashed line* represents the recent result by Ferrarese et al. (2000a) who calibrated the RGB Tip as a secondary indicator by using Cepheid distances in a small set of nearby galaxies where both Cepheids and the RGB Tip have been detected. They found $M_I^{TRGB} = -4.06 \pm 0.07$ (random) ± 0.13 (systematic), in very good agreement with our estimate, despite their larger uncertainty. In Figure 7.4, we plotted also the region delimited by the two empirical calibrations discussed above as a *shaded area*, in order to point out the region of the plane where most of the empirical estimates lie.

⁴As far as we know Dean, Warren & Cousins (1978) are the only ones providing a reddening law for the Cousin's I passband. All other sources we were able to retrieve refer to Johnson's I , a quite different filter with different $A_I/E(B - V)$ values.

Figure 7.4: Comparison between the calibration of M_I^{TRGB} obtained for ω Cen and different $M_I^{TRGB} - [\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ relations. The *big black dot* is our estimate of M_I^{TRGB} in ω Cen, where the horizontal error bar represents the range in metallicity comprising the dominant population of the cluster. Different curves represent different calibrations: the *short dashed curve* shows the calibration by Salaris & Cassisi (1998, Equation 5); the *dotted curve* represents the same calibration with different assumptions for the bolometric correction (eq. 6 in Salaris & Cassisi, 1998); the *dashed-dotted curve* is the empirical calibration by Lee et al. (1993), see their Equations 1 and 2, reported in the $M_I^{TRGB} - [\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ plane as described in their Section 2; the *heavy continuous curve* represents the empirical calibration we have derived from the Ferraro et al. (2000) database (our Equation 7.4); the *long dashed line* reports the calibration of M_I^{TRGB} as a secondary, indicator provided by Ferrarese et al. (2000a). The *shaded area* delimits the region of the plane where most of the empirical relations lie. Note that both the ω Cen measure and the Ferrarese et al. (2000a) calibration fall within this region.

Salaris & Cassisi (1998) provided a theoretical relation of M_I^{TRGB} as a function of the global metallicity $[M/H]$, instead of $[Fe/H]$. We convert their $[M/H]$ to $[Fe/H]$ according to the prescriptions of Salaris, Chieffi, & Straniero (1993) and assuming $[\alpha/Fe]=+0.28$ over the considered metallicity range (see Ferraro et al. (1999a)). Using two different bolometric corrections, Salaris & Cassisi (1998) derived two slightly different relations (their eq. 5 and 6), which are reported in Figure 7.4 as a *short dashed curve* and as a *dotted curve*, respectively.

As can be seen from Figure 7.4, the *theoretical* calibrations are systematically (~ 0.2 mag) brighter than *empirical* ones, as already noted by Salaris & Cassisi (1998) and Ferrarese et al. (2000a). The strong constraint provided by the RGB Tip luminosity in ω Cen seems to favor the empirical calibrations. However, as stated by Castellani, Deglinoenti, & Luridiana (1993) and Ferraro et al. (2000), theoretical relationships should be considered as upper limits for the RGB Tip luminosity, since they refer to the nominal red giant luminosity at the He flash.

7.5 Summary and Conclusions

We have used some of the most recent results from the study of Galactic Globular Clusters to improve the observational basis of the calibration of the RGB Tip method as a powerful distance indicator.

In particular, we have derived a robust estimate of M_I^{TRGB} in ω Cen, based (a) on the application of the standard technique on the very large sample of RGB stars presented in Chapter 3, and (b) on a direct distance estimate from a detached eclipsing binary by Thompson et al. (2001). Our result turns out to be in excellent agreement with previous empirical calibrations. Expected improvements in the distance and reddening estimates may likely reduce the uncertainties of our calibrating point to $\sim \pm 0.06$ mag. Thus, Equation 7.5 shall be considered as a very firm point of the RGB Tip calibration, at $[Fe/H] \sim -1.7$, for the future, as well as an important observational test for stellar evolutionary models. However, even at the present level of accuracy, the M_I^{TRGB} measure derived here is the less uncertain calibrating point for the $M_I^{TRGB} - [Fe/H]$ relation.

A new empirical $M_I^{TRGB} - [Fe/H]$ relation (Equation 7.4) was also derived. It turns out to be in excellent agreement with the derived M_I^{TRGB} of ω Cen as well as with other empirical calibrations. The main advantages of the new

relation derived here with respect to the previous ones (Lee et al., 1993; Da Costa & Armandroff, 1990) are: *(i)* it is based on more solid observational basis, since it has been derived from the largest IR database of RGB stars in Galactic globulars available in the literature (Ferraro et al., 2000), *(ii)* it has been calibrated over a larger range of metal abundances, extending the metallicity limit from $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \leq -0.7$ (Lee et al., 1993; Da Costa & Armandroff, 1990) to $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \leq -0.2$; for this reason, Equation 7.4 has to be considered a much more appropriate tool for applications to external galaxies, which, in general, are significantly more metal-rich than $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] > -0.7$.

Chapter 8

Towards a Determination of Age Differences within ω Cen

In this Chapter we present some preliminary results concerning the determination of the relative ages of the different populations in ω Cen. In particular, thanks to the WFI photometry presented in Chapter 3, we were able to identify sub-structures at the TO and SGB level in the CMD of ω Cen, in the outer regions that are less affected by crowding. On the basis of the CMD, we selected six stars lying on different SGB sub-structures and we observed them with UVES with the aim of deriving accurate chemical abundances and metallicities. The powerful combination of high-quality photometric and spectroscopic data will hopefully enable us to break the so-called age-metallicity degeneracy and measure the age differences among the sub-populations with great accuracy.

8.1 The Complex Structure of the SGB of ω Cen

Claims of an age spread of 3–5 Gyr, among the various sub-populations in ω Cen, have been made by Hughes & Wallerstein (2000) and Hilker & Richtler (2000), based on the TO region morphology of CMD. Such claims have not been confirmed by similar studies by Majewski et al. (2000) or Frinchaboy et al. (2002). This proves how the determination of relative ages can be difficult, especially if it relies on photometric measurements only.

Profiting from the wide field photometry presented in Chapter 3, that covers an area of $33' \times 34'$, we were able to detect the fine details of the SGB structure in ω Cen. As can be appreciated already from Figure 3.2, the SGB region of ω Cen presents some evident sub-structure, at least in the most external parts, e.g., on CCDs number #4, #5, #7 and #8 in the $B, (B - I)$ CMD. Among these, the clearest example appears on CCD #5,

Figure 8.1: A zoomed version of the SGB region of ω Cen, in the region covered by CCD #5 of the WFI photometry presented in Chapter 3 (left panel). Lying $\sim 10'$ S-E of the cluster center, this region is unaffected by severe crowding and a complex structure is visible at the SGB level, where multiple sub-branches can be seen. Stars inside a rectangular region, marked by a thick solid line, have been selected to produce a running histogram (right panel). At least three peaks are identified in the histogram (dotted lines), corresponding to three different sub-branches at the SGB level.

that lies $\sim 10'$ South-East of the center of ω -Cen. Figure 8.1 shows a zoomed section of the CMD in this region, where the multiple sub-branches can be clearly appreciated.

The splitting in multiple components that is evident from Figure 8.1 could never be observed before in any other published ω Cen photometry. However, since it can be seen only in the outer parts of the cluster, it is highly unlikely that the RGB-a counterpart will be found among the sub-branches, since it is quite centrally concentrated (see Chapter 6). It is thus reasonable to expect that the observed sub-structures will represent the SGB counterparts of the RGB-MP and RGB-MInt populations.

The reading of such a detailed sub-structure in terms of relative ages, however, is extremely difficult without a clear knowledge of the global metallicity (including the α -enhancement) of stars belonging to the different sub-branches. This problem is well known in the study of stellar populations, being often called *age-metallicity degeneracy*. In order to illustrate how it affects the derivation of ages, we constructed an example, based on the SGB

Figure 8.2: Example of the age-metallicity degeneracy problem. The zoomed SGB region has been fitted with two sets of isochrones by Bergbusch & Vandenberg (2001). The assumed distance modulus and reddening are, in both cases, $(m - M)_V = 13.97$ (Harris, 1996) and $E(B - V) = 0.11$ (Lub, 2002). In the left panel, isochrones with a metallicity close to the average of ω Cen, $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = 1.51$, have been fitted to the SGB substructure, resulting in ages of ~ 14 and 18 Gyr. In the right panel two different metallicities, close to the RGB-MP and RGB-MInt main peaks, $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -1.71$ and -1.3 , resulting in the same age of ~ 16 Gyr.

photometry of Figure 8.1 that shows how extremely different answers can be obtained *from the same CMD*, if the precise metallicities of the various sub-structures are not known.

This example is presented in Figure 8.2, where different hypothesis on the metallicity of the various sub-structures are made, and ages are derived from isochrone fitting using the models by Bergbusch & Vandenberg (2001). We adopted a distance modulus of $(m - M)_V = 13.97$ (Harris, 1996) and reddening $E(B - V) = 0.11$ (Lub, 2002). In particular, equally reasonable fits to the data are obtained assuming the two following scenarios: *(i)* all the stars in the SGB region have the same metallicity, close to the ω Cen average, $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -1.5$; then, in order to reproduce the complex structure seen in the CMD, we need to assume different ages of 18 and 14 Gyr for the uppermost and lowermost sub-branches (left panel); *(ii)* the stars in the SGB region have two different metallicities, close to the values found for the metal-poor and metal-intermediate peaks in the MDF of ω Cen, $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -1.7$ and -1.3 ; then the complex structure is reproduced by assuming that both sub-branches have

Figure 8.3: The position of the six UVES targets in the $B, (B - I)$ plane, with their WFI names marked.

the same age, 16 Gyr.

So, the age difference varies from 4 Gyr to no difference at all, depending only on the adopted metallicity. One could slightly vary the distance modulus and reddening as well, choosing $(m - M)_V = 14.05$ (Thompson et al., 2001) or $E(B - V) = 0.15$ (Djorgovski, 1993), which would in turn imply slight metallicity and age adjustments to obtain good fits with the data, adding even more free parameters. A precise determination of the metallicity of each of the sub-branches is thus a fundamental ingredient to solve the relative ages problem.

8.2 The UVES Sample of SGB stars

In order to shed light on this problem, we started an exploratory survey, by identifying six stars from those shown in Figures 8.1 and 8.2, in order to sample the two extreme sub-branches visible in the figures, that we will call *Upper Branch* and *Lower Branch*, from now on. Three stars (WFI 507109, WFI 512938 and WFI 507633) were selected in the Upper Branch and three (WFI 503358, WFI 503951 and WFI 512115) in the Lower branch (see Figure 8.3).

The stars were observed on March 18–20, 2002, with UVES at the VLT in Paranal, Chile, using the same setup as for the RGB Runs B and C (see

Observing Logs for the SGB Sample						
WFI	V	$(B - V)_o$	$(V - I)_o$	t_{exp}	S/N	Notes
507109	17.305	0.604	0.663	11228	25/50/40	Upper SGB
512938	17.322	0.599	0.651	10000	30/50/40	Upper SGB
507633	17.393	0.561	0.662	12000	25/45/40	Upper SGB
503358	17.530	0.653	0.654	10800	25/50/40	Lower SGB
503951	17.576	0.649	0.649	11400	25/50/40	Lower SGB
512115	17.638	0.647	0.660	11400	25/45/35	Lower SGB

Table 8.1: The observing logs, along with some fundamental target information. The first column reports the star name according to the WFI catalog presented in Chapter 3.

Chapter 4), giving a resolution of $R \sim 45,000$. Given the faint magnitudes of these stars ($V \sim 17.5$), we could reach a $S/N \sim 50$ per pixel only in the central portion of the spectra ($\sim 4600 - 5800 \text{ \AA}$), while the reddest part ($\sim 5800 - 7000 \text{ \AA}$) had $S/N \sim 40$ and the bluest part ($\sim 3500 - 4600 \text{ \AA}$) $S/N \sim 25$. To achieve these ratios, we rebinned along the dispersion axis, so each resolution element covers $\sim 2 - 3$ pixels, and we observed each star twice in two different nights to detect eventual radial velocity variations, for a total of approximately 3 hours of effective exposure time. None of the observed stars showed any sign of radial velocity variations, and they are all radial velocity members of ω Cen. The complete observation diary can be found in Table 8.1.

The spectra were extracted with the semi-automatic UVES pipeline (Ballester et al., 2000) described in Chapter 4, but the blue part of the spectra had to be re-extracted manually using the *ccdred* and *echelle* packages within IRAF, that perform similar reduction steps, since the S/N was not high enough for the pipeline to automatically perform the extraction. The spectra were then normalized to the continuum and corrected for telluric absorption with IRAF as described in Chapter 4, using the spectra of HR 5206/HD 120640 (Hoffleit & Jaschek, 1991) observed at least once every night. An example of the spectral quality can be seen in Figure 8.4.

These six subgiants are the first stars ever observed at the SGB of ω Cen with such a high resolution, so they are a goldmine of information and their complete analysis will be performed as soon as possible. A glimpse on the kind of results that we will be able to derive can be found in Section 8.4. For the purpose of this Thesis, we only show the determination of the abundance of iron and α -elements, that are the fundamental ingredients to break the age-metallicity degeneracy described in Section 8.1.

Figure 8.4: A sample of the spectra obtained with UVES is shown. Each spectrum is the sum of two spectra, for a total of 3 hours of exposure time. The S/N in this region is approximately ~ 50 per pixel, where a resolution element covers approximately 2–3 pixels. The six SGB stars are ordered by increasing metallicity, from top to bottom. The region contains a few Ca I and Fe I lines, including one of the few measurable Fe II lines.

Adopted Model Parameters and Abundance Results									
WFI	T_{eff}	$\log g$	v_t	[M/H]	[Fe/H]	[Mg/H]	[Si/H]	[Ca/H]	[Ti/H]
507109	5500	3.5	1.1	-1.8	-2.08	-1.69	-1.77	-1.84	-1.67
512938	5500	3.8	1.2	-1.8	-2.11	-1.72	-1.71	-1.84	-1.70
507633	5700	3.7	1.2	-1.8	-2.12	-1.63	—	-1.90	-1.77
503358	5600	3.7	0.8	-1.3	-1.62	-1.28	-1.41	-1.29	-1.33
503951	5500	3.4	0.8	-1.3	-1.56	-1.25	-1.29	-1.16	-1.17
512115	5600	3.7	0.4	-1.3	-1.04	-0.89	-1.07	-0.72	-0.42

Table 8.2: The adopted model parameters for the SGB stars and the resulting abundances. The first column contains the star name according to the WFI photometry presented in Chapter 3. Columns two to five contain the best model parameters, adopted for the abundance analysis. The last six columns contain the abundance determinations for Fe, Mg, Si, Ca and Ti. The uncertainty on these determinations is of $\sim \pm 0.15$ dex.

8.2.1 Abundance Analysis

The abundance analysis for the SGB stars was performed with a similar method to that described in Chapter 4 for the RGB stars. First estimates of the model parameters T_{eff} and $\log g$ were derived from the WFI photometry described in Chapter 3 and the fundamental relations presented in Chapter 4, using a distance modulus of $(m - M)_V = 13.97$ (Harris, 1996) and a reddening of $E(B - V) = 0.11$ (Lub, 2002). The $E(V - I)$ was derived using the reddening laws by Dean, Warren & Cousins (1978). The color-temperature calibrations were the ones by (Montegriffo et al., 1998) and Alonso, Arribas & Martínez-Roger (1999).

We used the old MARCS models of Edvardsson (1993, private communication), since the new grids by Plez do not extend enough in gravity and temperature to reach the typical values expected for SGB stars. The linelist and atomic data were selected from the VALD (Kupka et al., 1999), and we used only lines of Fe I, Fe II, Mg I, Si I, Ca I and Ti I, since the main goal of this preliminary analysis was the precise determination of the *global* metallicity. The lines selection and abundance calculation procedure was slightly more sophisticated than the one used for the RGB surveys, and consisted of the following steps:

- We used the abundance calculation code to *predict* the equivalent width of each of the $\sim 110,000$ VALD lines of all of the elements in the range $4000 - 7000\text{\AA}$, using the photometric T_{eff} and $\log g$ plus some reasonable estimates of v_t , [M/H] and of the abundances of each element involved;

- We selected a list of Fe, Mg, Si, Ca and Ti lines having predicted EW larger than 15 mÅ, and that were sufficiently isolated, i.e., not closer than their FWHM to other lines larger than 10% of their EW. We measured the EW of the surviving lines on the SGB spectra with DAOSPEC;
- We searched for the best model as described in Chapter 4, exploring a wide range of T_{eff} , $\log g$, v_t and [M/H];
- We used the best model to compute accurate abundances of Fe, Mg, Si, Ca and Ti. Lines that were systematically discrepant were rejected, and the best model was searched for, once again. This procedure was iterated a few times;
- We then used the refined model parameters and elements abundances to predict the EW of the $\sim 110,000$ VALD lines, and repeated the whole procedure a few times.

The adopted model parameters and the resulting abundances are presented in Table 8.2. They are based on ~ 300 Fe lines, 8 Mg lines, a few Si lines, 25 Ca lines and ~ 50 Ti lines, so the random errors are always quite small, of the order of a few hundredths of a dex. The uncertainty on abundances deriving from the choice of the model parameters is instead of $\sim \pm 0.15$ dex, and completely dominates the final uncertainty (see Chapter 4).

As can be seen, there are no stars belonging to the RGB-a SGB counterpart (SGB-a) in the surveyed sample. As said above, this was to be expected: it is quite unlikely that these stars are found outside the central regions of ω Cen, where the population is most concentrated (see Chapter 6). The three stars belonging to the Lower Branch are more metal-rich than the three stars belonging to the Upper Branch (see Figure 8.3). Two of them (WFI 503358 and WFI 503951) show metallicities very close to that of the RGB-MP, as shown in Table 8.2, while the third (WFI 512115) has a metallicity which is more typical of the RGB-MInt. The reality of this difference can be appreciated from Figure 8.4. Moreover, as computed by averaging the results in Table 8.2, the α -enhancement of all stars turns out to be $[\alpha/Fe]=+0.3$.

8.3 A Surprising Result

Apart from the expected absence of SGB-a stars, the most unexpected result is the presence of three stars with metallicities of $[Fe/H]=-2.12$, -2.11 and -2.08 ,

Figure 8.5: A comparison between the spectrum of WFI 507633 and star 206810 in NGC 6397 (top panel), taken from the UVES archive (already published by Gratton et al., 2001). The two stars have similar atmosphere parameters (see text), and their spectra are virtually identical: their difference (bottom panel) shows no residual except from noise.

all lying on the Upper Branch (see Table 8.2 and Figure 8.6). As discussed in detail in Chapter 2, there is only marginal evidence for the existence of such metal-poor stars in ω Cen. If such a metal-poor population exists, it should be a minority of the total cluster population. According to the photometric metallicity distributions found by Hilker & Richtler (2000) or Frinchaboy et al. (2002), it should account for no more than a few % of the total population. A slightly larger percentage is implied by the MS bimodal distribution found by Anderson (2002). Here we chose three stars in the upper part of the SGB and all of them turned out to be at $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -2.1$, in some contrast with the above findings.

To assess the robustness of our abundance measurements, we started a set of tests, that is still under way. Among these, we re-analyzed some UVES archive spectra of three sub-giants (stars 206810, 669 and 793) in NGC 6397 (already published by Gratton et al., 2001), that have very similar temperatures, gravities and metallicities to the most metal-poor SGB stars in our sample. Adopting their same parameters ($T_{eff} = 5500^{\circ}\text{K}$, $\log g = 3.4$ and $v_t = 1.3$) we obtained quite similar abundances. For star 206810, Gratton et al. (2001) obtained $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -2.10$ and $[\alpha/\text{Fe}] = +0.48$, while we obtained $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -1.96$ and $[\alpha/\text{Fe}] = +0.31$. For star 669 they obtained $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -2.01$

Figure 8.6: The position and abundance determination for the six SGB UVES targets is indicated (left panel) on the CMD for CCD #5. α -enhanced (Bergbusch & Vandenberg, 2001) isochrones are fitted to the three main SGB sub-branches (right panel) identified in Figure 8.1, using the metallicities obtained from the abundance analysis of the UVES spectra. A distance modulus of $(m - M)_V = 13.97$ (Harris, 1996) and reddening of $E(B - V) = 0.11$ (Lub, 2002) are adopted. The solid isochrone has an age of 18 Gyr and a metallicity of $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -2.14$; the long dashed line has an age of 18 Gyr as well and $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -1.61$; the short dashed line has instead an age of 12 Gyr and $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -1.01$

and $[\alpha/\text{Fe}] = +0.34$, while we obtained $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -1.96$ and $[\alpha/\text{Fe}] = +0.34$. Finally, for star 793 they obtained $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -2.04$ and $[\alpha/\text{Fe}] < +0.34$, while we obtained $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -2.04$ and $[\alpha/\text{Fe}] = +0.25$.

A comparison of the spectra of NGC 6397 and ω Cen confirms the validity of the abundance analysis. Figure 8.5 compares the spectra of WFI 507633 and star 206810 in NGC 6397. The parameters of these stars are very similar, and in fact the calcium and iron lines are virtually identical (top panel), as confirmed by subtracting one spectrum from the other (bottom panel).

It seems thus likely that a (perhaps) substantial sub-population with low metallicity ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -2.1$) exists in ω Cen, raising a set of new questions that need to be answered, as for example (i) why previous RGB survey did not pick up larger numbers of these metal-poor stars? (ii) could they be a spatially segregated population, that can be seen only at 10' South-East of the cluster Center? We hope to provide definitive answers with the FLAMES observations scheduled on may 2003, that are described in Chapter 9.

8.3.1 Deriving Ages: a Preliminary Exercise

With the abundances determined in the previous Sections, we can attempt a first, preliminary estimate of the relative ages among the three SGB sub-populations found. Figure 8.6 shows the result of such an attempt, although we would like to point out that this is just the first step of a delicate and complex measurement process, involving the use of models with finer metallicity and age grids, and exploring the whole space of distance and reddening estimates for ω Cen.

The left panel of Figure 8.6 shows the position of the targets in the CMD. The iron abundances of the six targets are also indicated. The average α -enhancement is $[\alpha/\text{Fe}] = +0.3$ for all stars, so we used α -enhanced isochrones by Bergbusch & Vandenberg (2001) with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -2.14, -1.61$ and -1.01 and fitted them to the SGB morphology (right panel). We adopted $(m - M)_V = 13.97$ (Harris, 1996) and $E(B - V) = 0.11$ (Lub, 2002).

The best fit was obtained with an age of 18 Gyr for both the $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -2.14$ and the $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -1.61$, implying an age difference of no more than 1 Gyr between the two populations, given the coarseness of the model grid in age. The $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -1.01$ was instead fitted with an age of 12 Gyr, although the fit with 14 Gyr (not shown) provided a reasonable fit as well, implying that most probably 13 Gyr would have been the best fit. This implies an age difference of 4–5 Gyr between the RGB-MP and the RGB-MInt population.

The interesting thing that can be appreciated from the right panel of Figure 8.6 is that we chose our targets on the lower branch exactly in the position where the two isochrones cross each other due to the age difference. Thus, if we are interpreting the data correctly, this choice explains why we found two stars with a typical RGB-MP metallicity and one star with a typical RGB-MInt metallicity so close to each other.

8.4 Exploiting the Potentiality of the SGB Spectra

The spectra presented here are the first high-resolution spectra ever obtained in the SGB of ω Cen. In this Thesis they are used for a very specific goal, but they contain much more information that just awaits for being extracted.

A glimpse of the treasure of information contained in this dataset can be appreciated in Figure 8.7. Only the three stars belonging to the lower SGB (i.e., the three most metal rich ones) are plotted in the regions containing the 3880 Å CN blue band (left panel) and the 4305 Å CH G-Band (right panel).

Figure 8.7: The spectra of the three most metal-rich SGB stars are shown in the region of the 3880 Å CN blue band (left panel) and of the 4305 Å CH G-Band. The three stars have very similar T_{eff} , $\log g$, v_t and metallicity, but they show a very different behaviour as far as these molecular bands are concerned. In particular, while stars WFI 503951 and WFI 512115 show an impressive CN absorption band, they are completely lacking any absorption in the CH band. Conversely, star WFI 503358 shows no trace of a CN absorption at all, while some absorption can be seen in the CH band, although the CH G-Band is intrinsically fainter and the effect is more difficult to be appreciated.

In, particular, the two uppermost stars (WFI 503358 and WFI 503951) can be considered as twins, since they basically have very similar T_{eff} , $\log g$, v_t and $[Fe/H]$, but while the former shows practically *no trace* of the CN band, the latter shows an impressively strong CN absorption. The situation is mirrored by the CH G-band, although this band is much weaker intrinsically and so the effect is difficult to appreciate by eye, without a proper measurement of the band strength index. However, while WFI 503951 possessed a deep CN band, there is *no trace* of absorption in its CH band. The opposite is true for WFI 503358, that has no absorption in the CN band but shows some absorption in the CH band.

This is a beautiful esemplification of the CH-CN anti-correlation that was described in Chapter 2. In particular, according to isochrones (see also Figure 8.6), these three stars could be well before the first dredge-up point, that happens at the very base of the RGB for these low mass stars. If this is the case, we would have found a sign of anti-correlations at a level in which they cannot be explained with pure internal mixing episodes, and thus require pollution by a previous generation of AGB stars to be explained. To further

explore this possibility, accurate measurements of Mg, Na, O, and Al would be required. While O is quite difficult to measure in these warm sub-giants, Mg, Na and Al are all present in these spectra and will soon be measured.

Chapter 9

Conclusions and Future Prospects

Here we discuss the main results presented in previous Chapters, in the framework of the current theories of the formation and evolution of ω Cen. Of course many questions still remain open and the Chapter is closed with a description of the future projects that we are carrying on in the context of the Bologna Key Project on ω Cen.

9.1 Summary of the Thesis Results

As discussed in Section 1.1, this Thesis work has been mainly concentrated on the identification and the study of the spectro-photometric properties of the anomalous metal-rich population (RGB-a) in ω Cen (see Chapter 3 and Lee et al., 1999; Pancino et al., 2000). Several of the RGB-a chemical, structural and dynamical properties have been determined here for the first time, and can be summarized as follows:

- The identification of the anomalous RGB-a population has been presented for the first time (Chapter 3);
- The RGB-a, containing $\sim 5\%$ of the RGB stars in ω Cen, is more centrally concentrated than the bulk of the cluster population (Chapter 3);
- The RGB-a spatial distribution is not compatible with that of the main cluster population, i.e., the RGB-MP (Chapters 3 and 6);
- The RGB-a main density peak is almost one core radius away (N-W) from the main cluster peak (Chapter 6);
- The RGB-a is more flattened on average ($\langle \varepsilon \rangle \simeq 0.22$) than the whole cluster ($\langle \varepsilon \rangle \simeq 0.12$) (Chapter 6);

- The RGB-a is elongated along the N-S direction, i.e., perpendicularly to the RGB-MP and global cluster elongation (Chapters 3 and 6);
- The RGB-a shows a bulk residual proper motion of $\sim 0.8 \text{ mas yr}^{-1}$ with respect to the cluster average proper motion, but it is still gravitationally locked in ω Cen's potential well (Chapter 5);
- The RGB-a average metallicity is $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -0.62 \pm 0.06$, on the basis of high-resolution, high S/N UVES data for 12 RGB-a stars (Chapter 4);
- The RGB-a stars show a lower α -enhancement with respect to the other populations in ω Cen (Chapter 4);
- The RGB-a stars show the same, very high and very unusual overabundance of s -process elements as the other sub-populations of ω Cen (Chapter 4);

Moreover, some new observational evidence concerning the metal-poor and metal-intermediate RGB sub-populations (RGB-MP and RGB-MInt) has also been collected. In particular, while the RGB-MP, being the dominant population, shares the main properties of ω Cen as a whole, the RGB-MInt appears as an intermediate group between the RGB-a and the RGB-MP when its structural and kinematical properties are considered:

- The RGB-MInt, containing $\sim 25\%$ of the RGB stars in ω Cen, is probably slightly more concentrated than the bulk of the cluster population, but its very complex spatial structure prevents us to be more quantitative on this point (Chapter 3);
- The RGB-MInt spatial distribution is not compatible with that of the main cluster population (RGB-MP), but on the other hand, it turns out to be marginally compatible with the RGB-a spatial density distribution (Chapters 3 and 6);
- The RGB-MInt show a very complex spatial structure, with a possible double peak and its main density peak lies almost one core radius away (S-E) from the main cluster peak (Chapter 6);
- The RGB-MInt is elongated along the N-S direction as the RGB-a, i.e., perpendicularly to the RGB-MP and global cluster elongation (Chapters 3 and 6);

- The RGB-MInt also shows marginal evidence of a bulk residual proper motion with respect to the cluster average proper motion (Chapter 5);

9.2 Implications for the Current Theories on ω Cen

In Chapter 2 we review most of the many peculiar properties of ω Cen. Here we summarize and review the currently most accepted explanations for its formation and evolution, which are all based upon non-negligible pieces of observational evidence. For each proposed scenario, we discuss the impact and implications of the new results presented in this Thesis, summarizing both the supporting evidence and the unanswered questions.

9.2.1 The Self Enrichment Scenario

One of the most popular scenario proposes that ω Cen has been somehow able to retain the ejecta of previous generations of stars and to self-enrich during its star formation history (Morgan & Lake, 1989; Parmentier et al., 1999). This is mainly supported by previous results concerning the metallicity distribution (Section 2.5 and Suntzeff & Kraft, 1996; Norris, Freeman & Mighell, 1996) and the detailed chemical composition of its giants (Section 2.6 and Norris & Da Costa, 1995a; Smith et al., 2000). Moreover, in a standard dissipative self-enrichment scenario, we would expect the more metal-rich (and younger) populations (the RGB-MInt and RGB-a) to be more centrally concentrated than the metal-poor, dominant population (the RGB-MP). This is almost always the case for the dwarf galaxies of the local group, with only a few exceptions (Harbeck et al., 2001), and it is exactly what we observe for ω Cen.

In particular, the fundamental piece of evidence in favour of this scenario is the constancy of the α -enhancement with metallicity ($[\alpha/\text{Fe}] \sim +0.3$) for all stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \leq -0.8$ (Norris & Da Costa, 1995a; Smith et al., 2000). This requires that the major responsables for the enrichment of these stars are SNe type II: as discussed in Chapter 2 already, only a small fraction ($\sim 3\%$) of the SNe type II ejecta needed to be retained to explain the reached abundances.

The continuity of properties between the RGB-MP and the RGB-MInt giants, concerning the α -elements and the s -process elements abundances and the light elements anti-correlations described in Section 2.6, have also been invoked to support the idea that these two sub-populations evolved in a common system. Moreover, ω Cen is the only galactic component to show such a high abundance of s -process elements: the other GGC and the field stars in

that metallicity range have solar heavy elements ratios (but see Section 9.2.2 for other systems that share this characteristic with ω Cen). However, the lower α -elements abundance of the RGB-a stars found in Chapter 4 (and possibly even of the RGB-MP stars, see Section 4.3), and the indication of a break in the slope of the $[s/\text{Fe}]$ versus $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ relation (Smith, 2002) are somewhat contradicting this idea of continuous properties among the various sub-populations of ω Cen.

Concerning the RGB-MP and the RGB-MInt populations, the conclusions based on the α -elements and on the flat trends in $[\text{Eu}/\text{Fe}]$ and $[\text{Cu}/\text{Fe}]$ (see Section 2.6), have been taken as evidence that no significant contribution by SNe type Ia have enriched these two populations. This has been explained either with a star formation process short enough to end before the onset of SNe type Ia, or by assuming that SNe type Ia winds efficiently removed most of their own products (Recchi, Matteucci, & D’Ercole, 2001). This is reasonable since usually SNe type Ia explode in less dense medium, that has been already swept-up by previous stellar generations.

The RGB-a as the Last Burst of Star Formation

If we assume that the more centrally concentrated RGB-a population (defined in Chapter 3) is the natural product of such a dissipative self-enrichment process, then we need to assume that it was enriched by SNe type Ia ejecta, given its lower α -enhancement (Chapter 4). We also must make the hypothesis that the RGB-a is the youngest stellar population inside ω Cen, possibly the last burst of star formation inside the cluster. In fact, we would have detected the “knee” of the $[\alpha/\text{Fe}]$ relation, a very valuable constraint to the chemical evolution of the whole stellar system (McWilliam, 1997). The canonical interpretation of such feature is that it marks the onset of the SNe type Ia pollution. While the timescale of this enrichment process are generally believed to be short (≤ 1 Gyr), they are still quite uncertain, since they depend on several factors (Matteucci & Recchi, 2001).

However, this interpretation of the RGB-a adds more complication to the self-enrichment scenario. We run in fact into the difficulty of explaining how ω Cen was able to retain even part of the energetic SNe type Ia ejecta (see Gnedin et al., 2002, for a discussion on this point). Specific and detailed calculations on this point have not been produced yet, but according to the above reasoning (Recchi, Matteucci, & D’Ercole, 2001), a dense interstellar medium could have been the key ingredient to retain the SNe Ia gas. This

opens a whole lot of new questions that for the moment have no quantitative answers: (i) How dense should the interstellar gas be to retain efficiently enough the SNe Ia winds? (ii) How would it have affected the retention of the SNe II products? (iii) How could it have survived the interaction with the Galactic disk long enough to allow the formation of the RGB-a?

The Enrichment Timescales Puzzle

Another complication arises when one tries to reconcile the enrichment timescales of the various chemical contributors in ω Cen. We know that the RGB-MP and RGB-MInt have been enriched simultaneously by SNe II and AGB low mass stars up to $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -0.8$ (Section 2.6). We have seen that, while the enrichment timescales of SNe II are quite fast (≤ 1 Gyr), the ones of the AGB stars of $1 \div 3 M_{\odot}$ are of at least $1 \div 2$ Gyr, and possibly even longer (~ 5 Gyr). While an attempt to solve this contradiction has been made by Ventura et al. (2001), invoking direct AGB pollution on the stellar atmospheres *when it was still forming*, the problem remains open. The discovery of the RGB-a and of its low α -enhancement does not add any further complication to the timescales problem, since the pollution timescales of SNe Ia depend heavily on the star formation rate of the system under consideration (Matteucci & Recchi, 2001).

Concluding, it appears that the main sources of chemical enrichment for the different sub-populations in ω Cen have been identified, although some work remains to be done to completely characterize the RGB-a. There is no doubt that part of the ejecta of SNe type II, low mass AGB stars and even SNe type Ia have somehow been incorporated in the gas from which these stars have formed (or even during their formation process). But there are some problems in putting all of the pieces together in one single isolated system, especially when the timescales of the various processes are considered.

Moreover, it is still quite difficult to accommodate the different structural and kinematical properties of the different sub-populations, like their elongation and orientation, their main density peaks offsets (Chapter 6) and their different rotation, proper motions and velocity dispersion, (Freeman, 1985; Norris et al., 1997; Ferraro, Bellazzini, & Pancino, 2002a), in a standard dissipative self-enrichment scenario, so a more sophisticated approach may be needed.

Figure 9.1: Different stellar systems are plotted in the $(M_V, \mu_V(0))$ – left panel – and the $(\log r_c, \mu_V(0))$ plane – right panel. The dwarf spheroidals and dwarf ellipticals (Mateo, 1998) are plotted as *small triangles* while the GGC (Harris, 1996) are plotted as small *empty circles*. The region where the Ultra-compact Dwarf Galaxies (UCD) lie is marked with a dotted line (Fellhauer & Kroupa, 2002). G 1, the largest GC in M 31 (Meylan, 2002) is marked as an *empty star*, while M 54 and ω Cen are marked as an *asterisk* and a *large filled polygon*, respectively. The nucleus of NGC 205 is plotted as an *empty square*, while NGC 205 as a whole is in the dwarf galaxies sequence.

9.2.2 An Accreted Dwarf Galaxy?

The idea that ω Cen was once (part of) a larger stellar system, accreted and partially disrupted by the Milky Way, has been proposed by many authors (see the most recent works by Dinescu, Girard & van Altena, 1999; Lee et al., 1999; Majewski et al., 2000; Hughes & Wallerstein, 2000; Hilker & Richtler, 2000). Evidence supporting this idea comes from the fact that most dwarf galaxies in the local group have complex star formation histories, containing more than one stellar sub-population (Harbeck et al., 2001; Tolstoy et al., 2003) and they also have many structural properties that are comparable to those of ω Cen (see Chapter 2).

The case of the disrupting Sagittarius dSph poses an inspiring comparison, for some of its chemical abundance patterns (see below) and for the fact that it has a large globular cluster, M 54, associated with its main density peak. It also seems to be associated with three more GGC: Terzan 7, Terzan 8 and Arp 2 (Da Costa & Armandroff, 1995). This lead to the well known hypothesis that M 54 is the nucleus of the Sagittarius¹ (Bassino & Muzzio, 1995; Sarajedini & Layden, 1995; Layden & Sarajedini, 2000).

According to Dinescu, Girard & van Altena (1999), ω Cen could not survive as a gas rich, star-forming system in its present orbit for a long time. So the hypothesis has been made (Dinescu, Girard & van Altena, 1999) that ω Cen was in the past a larger entity, decayed to its present orbit through dynamical friction. This implies that the past mass of ω Cen was much larger, otherwise dynamical friction would not have affected the orbit so much (Zhao, 2002). In this case, the two other GGC that share ω Cen anomalous orbital parameters, NGC 6779 and NGC 362, could be somehow associated to it (Dinescu, Girard & van Altena, 1999). Indeed, traces of a retrograde stream of stars in the local neighborhood, compatible with the orbit of ω Cen, have been found by Dinescu (2002) (see Chapter 2).

A Nucleated Dwarf Elliptical?

More support to the general idea that ω Cen was formerly a larger system, more specifically a nucleated dwarf elliptical, comes from the comparison of the structural properties of GGC, dwarf galaxies and ω Cen. In Figure 9.1, we have plotted the position of different stellar systems on two projections of the

¹In particular, it is interesting to note that Terzan 7 has a metallicity of $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -0.62$ (Harris, 1996), quite similar to that of the RGB-a, while M 54 has $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -1.59$, very close to the RGB-MP, and to the average metallicity of ω Cen.

Fundamental Plane (Djorgovski & Davis, 1987), the $(M_V, \mu_V(0))$ plane and the $(\log r_c, \mu_V(0))$ plane. As can be seen, ω Centauri (*large filled polygon*) appears very close to the GGC sequence (*small empty dots*) and well out of the dwarf galaxies sequence (*small black triangles*). However, the *nucleus* of NGC 205 (*empty square*), a nucleated dwarf elliptical that otherwise lies on the “normal” dwarf galaxies sequence, lies very close to the GGC sequence if plotted alone (see Meylan, 2002; Freeman & Bland-Hawthorn, 2002). Although based on only one nucleus, this evidence supports the idea that the nuclei of nucleated dwarf ellipticals could be very similar to the most massive GC, and that ω Cen has quite different kinematical properties from the dSph.

Thus it appears that, if really ω Cen was (part of) a dwarf galaxy, most probably it was a nucleated dwarf elliptical, and not a dSph. This is supported by recent high-resolution spectroscopic analysis of a few dSph (Shetrone et al., 2003; Smecker-Hane & McWilliam, 2003). In particular, the *s*-process elements, in the dSph studied so far, are largely underabundant with respect to solar (Shetrone et al., 2003) with the only exception of the disrupting Sagittarius (Smecker-Hane, McWilliam & Ibata, 1998; Smecker-Hane & McWilliam, 2003), which however is atypical as a dSph, most probably the remnant of a nucleated dwarf elliptical (see above). Also, none of the dSph surveyed so far with high-resolution spectroscopy show any sign of anti-correlations among Mg, Al, Na and O (not even the Sagittarius), while most GGC do, ω Cen included. Finally, very metal-poor stars are observed in all dSph, and their metallicity distributions appear to have a metal-poor tail, while in ω Cen there is a sharp cut-off around $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -1.9$, with only marginal evidence for a small metal-poor population at lower abundance (Jurcsik, 1998; Frinchaboy et al., 2002; Anderson, 2002, see also Chapter 8).

9.2.3 The Merging Scenario

To account for the observed correlations between the chemical and dynamical properties of ω Cen, both Freeman (1985) and Norris et al. (1997) concluded that some kind of merging event between stellar systems must have been invoked (see Chapter 2). Indeed, many twin and double clusters, merging clusters and very flattened clusters are observed in the Large Magellanic Cloud (LMC — Bhatia & Hatzidimitriou, 1988; Leon, Bergond & Vallenari, 1999) and many hypothesis have been suggested to explain their existence and formation mechanisms (see Gurzadyan, 2000; Theis, 2002, for further discussions).

The merging of unequal mass globulars has also been studied theoretically

by, e.g., Makino, Akiyama & Sugimoto (1991), who found that the merger result is a flattened cluster, in which the originally more massive globular system retains the lion's share of the angular momentum. Norris et al. (1997) noted that in fact, in ω Cen, it is the most massive component (the metal-poor one) that rotates, and the unusually high ellipticity of ω Cen is compatible with the flattened shapes resulting from the merger of two globular clusters (Makino, Akiyama & Sugimoto, 1991).

However, in the present potential well of the Milky Way, the merging of two already formed globular clusters appears quite unlikely (Norris, Freeman & Mighell, 1996; Smith et al., 2000; Thurl & Johnston, 2002), given the high relative velocities of the encounters, unless the two (or more) GC formed together, as it is supposed to happen for the double and twin clusters in the LMC (Bhatia & Hatzidimitriou, 1988; Leon, Bergond & Vallenari, 1999; Gurzadyan, 2000; Theis, 2002). The chance of an interaction, resulting in a merger event, would be substantially higher in a lower potential system, like a dwarf galaxy (Thurl & Johnston, 2002). Also, as already pointed out by Norris, Freeman & Mighell (1996) and Suntzeff & Kraft (1996), the simple merging of two or more single metallicity clusters cannot account for the broad metallicity distribution of the RGB.

Unfortunately, while there is no doubt on the fact that some self-enrichment must be included in a successful formation and evolution theory for ω Cen (Section 9.2.1), we are dealing with a complex set of observational facts, containing sometimes conflicting evidence. In fact, some of the observational facts collected so far (Norris et al., 1997; Jurcsik, 1998; Lee et al., 1999; Pancino et al., 2000; Ferraro, Pancino, & Bellazzini, 2002b), along with the new results presented in this Thesis (Chapters 3, 5 and 6), point towards a merging and/or accretion event in the past history of ω Cen. However unlikely this may appear, we have no other way to explain the structural and kinematical properties of the various cluster sub-populations.

The RGB-a (and RGB-MInt?) as an Accreted Component

Let us first discuss the relative orientation of the three RGB sub-populations found in Chapters 3 and 6. It is now well established that the elongated shape of the whole cluster (dominated by the RGB-MP population) is mainly due to rotation (Harding, 1965; Merritt, Meylan & Mayor, 1997; Meylan & Mayor, 1986), which is consistent with the picture of a dynamically young and not completely relaxed cluster (Section 2.4). Thus, it becomes tempting to

explain the elongations of the RGB-MInt and RGB-a populations in terms of rotational velocity, too, but in this case it would be necessary to assume that these two populations rotate around a *perpendicular axis* with respect to the RGB-MP.

An inspiring comparison is posed by the recent work by Sarzi et al. (2000), who examine an example of galaxy that has undergone a major merging or accretion event in its past. The signature of such an event is the simultaneous presence of (1) an orthogonally elongated bulge with respect to the disk, and of (2) two rotation curves, perpendicular to each other, one for the host galaxy and another for the accreted component. Now, we have shown in this Thesis that the first signature could indeed be present in ω Cen: we have (at least) two components with orthogonal elongations. The work of Norris et al. (1997) shows that the second signature is partially present in ω Cen. In this respect, the bulk proper motion for the RGB-a found in Chapter 5 suggests that the RGB-a could be an *accreted population*, captured by the main body of ω Cen. We thus should expect the RGB-a to have a different centre with respect to the main cluster population, and it is exactly what we found in Chapter 6.

Moreover, if a merging/accretion event has really taken place in the past history of ω Cen, how long ago do we expect it to have happened? We already know that ω Cen has a very long relaxation time, comparable to its age. We also know that the RGB-a is $\sim 2-3$ times more concentrated than the RGB-MP (Chapter 6), and it lies almost one core radius away from the centre of ω Cen. Thus, the density contrast between the RGB-a and its surrounding environment suggests that it could have survived as a self-gravitating system for many Gyr² (see also Chapter 5). It is however puzzling that the (few) radial velocities measured for the RGB-a so far are not so different from the cluster average³.

The Merger Within a Fragment Scenario

So, a self-consistent set of observational facts, supporting the occurrence of an accretion or merger event in the cluster past history, is beginning to take shape.

²An interesting discussion on the survival of globular clusters within dwarf elliptical galaxies has been presented by Lotz et al. (2001).

³In this respect, we would like to note that the simultaneous presence of a bulk proper motion with respect to the whole cluster, and absence of a correspondent bulk radial velocity motion, could simply be indicative of a transverse global motion, i.e., approximately perpendicular to the line of sight. In other words, it would mean that the RGB-a “orbit” inside ω Cen is seen face-on, although the probability of such a configuration is not very high. This is similar to the suggestion by van den Bosch et al. (1999), concerning the puzzling result on the RGB-MInt velocity dispersions by Norris et al. (1997)

We would like to note here that this fact is not necessarily in contradiction with the occurrence of some self-enrichment, nor with the hypothesis that ω Cen is the remaining nucleus of a larger body (a dwarf galaxy), accreted and partially disrupted by the Milky Way.

An interesting scenario, that could accommodate all of the observational evidence collected so far, was discussed by, e.g., Freeman (1985), Norris et al. (1997) and Smith et al. (2000): the so-called *merger within a fragment scenario*, descending from the general framework proposed by Searle (1977). In this framework, a conglomerate of star-forming sub-systems or regions could evolve within a large cloud and a common potential well (a fragment), each section evolving with slightly different timescales, and slightly different chemical properties.

Later, a dwarf galaxy with its own globular cluster system could form, and a few globular clusters (like the ones traced by the RGB-a, or even the RGB-MInt) could spiral towards the system centre, while the remaining clusters could be stripped by the interaction with the Milky Way, along with most of the dwarf galaxy halo. Recent calculations by Bromm & Clarke (2002) support this line of reasoning (see also Fellhauer & Kroupa, 2002), together with the example of the Sagittarius dwarf galaxy discussed above. Although still qualitative, this idea deserves to be further explored since it appears the most promising to explain ω Cen's puzzling properties.

9.3 Open Questions and Future Prospects

In the framework of the global project on ω Cen, the future observational campaigns are oriented towards three main directions:

- To obtain a complete screening of the abundance patterns (from the light elements, to iron, the α -elements and the *s*-process elements, for all of the RGB sub-populations in ω Cen and for a large sample of a few hundred stars;
- To search for tracers of the anomalous population in other evolutionary phases, like the HB (the HB-a) and the SGB (the SGB-a), and to investigate if the faint stars below the HB could belong to this population;
- To finally settle the problem of the relative ages determination for the various sub-populations in ω Cen.

Figure 9.2: The proposed targets for the FLAMES survey. A selection of RGB stars is shown (small triangles) in the top panel, while a coverage of the SGB-TO region is shown in the bottom panel. The collection of all the FLAMES observations will enable us to derive the complete chemical fingerprint of the different sub-populations in ω Cen, to measure accurate age differences for the different sub-populations, and to investigate the correlations between chemical and dynamical properties with an unprecedented dataset.

In doing this, we will take advantage of the present generation of ESO telescopes and instruments. From this point of view, we are in a particularly favorable position, since the Bologna Observatory is member of the Ital-FLAMES consortium (a consortium of four Italian observatories: Bologna, Trieste, Palermo and Catania) which participated to the construction of the FLAMES facility. The Fibre Large Array Multi Element Spectrograph (FLAMES) is a system that feeds with fibre links two spectrographs simultaneously, GIRAFFE and UVES, located on the Nasmyth platforms of VLT-UT2. GIRAFFE is a multi-object echelle spectrograph covering the entire visible range (370-900 nm) at intermediate ($R=7,500-12,500$) and high ($R=15,000-25,000$) resolution. FLAMES will therefore allow intermediate-high resolution spectroscopy for objects brighter than $V=22$ with a multiplex capability of 8 to 130 fibers over a large field of view (about 25 arcmin in diameter).

The use of this facility will allow us to make a significant step towards the final characterization of the different sub-populations in ω Cen, both from the dynamical and chemical point of view. In Figure 9.2 we show a preliminary selection of candidates for the RGB (*Left Panel*) and the SGB-TO (*Right Panel*) FLAMES surveys.

We plan to use part of the Consortium guaranteed time to perform simultaneous observations with UVES and GIRAFFE. By maintaining an overlap of 5-10 stars between the high resolution ($R \sim 40,000$) and the medium resolution ($R \sim 20,000$) samples, we can check the performance of the spectral synthesis method used and avoid using blended or unreliable lines in the lower resolution spectra. An important byproduct of this massive spectroscopic survey is the production of an unprecedented catalog of radial velocity estimates. We will achieve a precision of 0.15 km sec^{-1} , that will enable us to explore the correlation between chemical and dynamical properties in the cluster stars.

To properly derive relative ages for all the sub-populations, we need of course to sample even the most rare components, like the RGB-a. For this reason, we need to obtain very high-quality photometric data for the central parts of ω Cen as well. While the WFI photometry (as shown in Chapter 8) allowed to put into evidence the splitting of the SGB sequences in the external parts of the cluster, only extremely good seeing conditions from the ground (FORS at the VLT) or space observations with the HST will enable us to disentangle the SGB structure of the crowded center of ω Cen.

Bibliography

- Alcaino, G. & Liller, W. 1987, AJ, 94, 1585
- Alonso, A., Arribas, S., & Martínez-Roger, C. 1999, A&AS, 140, 261
- Andersen, J. 1999, Transactions of the IAU, Vol. XXIVA, p.36 (1999) , 24, A36
- Anderson, J. 1997, Ph.D. Thesis, University of California, Berkeley
- Anderson, J. 2002, ASP Conf. Ser. 265: Omega Centauri, A Unique Window into Astrophysics, 87
- Ashurov, A. E. & van Leeuwen, F. 2002, ASP Conf. Ser. 265: Omega Centauri, A Unique Window into Astrophysics, 51
- Babu, G. J. & Feigelson, E. D. 1996, Astrostatistics by G.J. Babu and E.D. Feigelson. London: Chapman and Hall, 1996.,
- Bailyn, C. D., Sarajedini, A., Cohn, H., Lugger, P. M., & Grindlay, J. E. 1992, AJ, 103, 1564
- Ballester, P., Modigliani, A., Boitquin, O., Cristiani, S., Hanuschik, R., Kaufer, A., Wolf, S. 2000, The ESO Messenger, 101, 31
- Barnes, T. G. & Evans, D. S. 1976, MNRAS, 174, 489
- Bassino, L. P. & Muzzio, J. C. 1995, The Observatory, 115, 256
- Bell, R. A., Cannon, R. D., Harris, G. L. H., & Hesser, J. E. 1981, ApJ, 249, 637
- Bellazzini, M., Ferraro, F. R. & Pancino, E. 2001, ApJ, 556, 635
- Bergbusch, P. A. & Vandenberg, D. A. 2001, ApJ, 556, 322
- Bessell, M. S. & Norris, J. 1976, ApJ, 208, 369
- Bessell, M. S. 1979, PASP, 91, 589

- Bhatia, R. K. & Hatzidimitriou, D. 1988, MNRAS, 230, 215
- Bielski, A. 1975, J. Quant. Spectrosc. Radiat. Transfer, 15, 463
- Biemont, E. & Grevesse, N. 1973, A&A, 27, 163
- Bromm, V. & Clarke, C. J. 2002, ApJL, 566, L1
- Brown, J. A., Wallerstein, G., Cunha, K., & Smith, V. V. 1991, A&A, 249, L13
- Brown, J. A. & Wallerstein, G. 1993, AJ, 106, 133
- Buonanno, R., Buscema, G., Corsi, C. E., Ferraro, I., & Iannicola, G. 1983, A&A, 126, 278
- Buonanno, R., Corsi, C. E., & Fusi Pecci, F. 1985, A&A, 145, 97
- Buonanno, R. & Iannicola, G. 1989, PASP, 101, 294
- Buonanno, R., Corsi, C., Bellazzini, M., Ferraro, F. R., & Pecci, F. F. 1997, AJ, 113, 706
- Burkert, A. 1997, ApJL, 474, L99
- Burstein, D. & Heiles, C. 1982, AJ, 87, 1165
- Busso, M., Gallino, R. & Wasserburg, G. J. 1999, ARA&A, 37, 239
- Busso, M., Gallino, R., Lambert, D. L., Travaglio, C., & Smith, V. V. 2001, ApJ, 557, 802
- Butler, D., Dickens, R. J., & Epps, E. 1978, ApJ, 225, 148
- Cacciari, C. 1999, ASP Conf. Ser. 167: Harmonizing Cosmic Distance Scales in a Post-HIPPARCOS Era, 140
- Cannon, R. D. 1980, A&A, 81, 379
- Cannon, R. D. & Stewart, N. J. 1981, MNRAS, 195, 15
- Cannon, R. D. & Stobie, R. S. 1973, MNRAS, 162, 207
- Cannon, R. D., Croke, B. F. W., Bell, R. A., Hesser, J. E., & Stathakis, R. A. 1998, MNRAS, 298, 601
- Cardelli, J. A., Clayton, G. C., & Mathis, J. S. 1989, ApJ, 345, 245

- Carretta, E. & Gratton, R. G. 1997, *A&AS*, 121, 95
- Castellani, V., Chieffi, A., & Straniero, O. 1990, *ApJS*, 74, 463
- Castellani, V., Deglinoenti, S., & Luridiana, V. 1993, *A&A*, 272, 442
- Cayrel, R. 1988, *IAU Symp. 132: The Impact of Very High S/N Spectroscopy on Stellar Physics*, 132, 345
- Cohen, J. G. 1981, *ApJ*, 247, 869
- Cohen, J. G. 1999, *AJ*, 117, 2434
- Combes, F., Leon, S., & Meylan, G. 1999, *A&A*, 352, 149
- Cottrell, P. L. & Da Costa, G. S. 1981, *ApJL*, 245, L79
- Cunha, K., Smith, V. V., Suntzeff, N. B., Norris, J. E., Da Costa, G. S., & Plez, B. 2002, *AJ*, 124, 379
- Da Costa, G. S. & Armandroff, T. E. 1990, *AJ*, 100, 162
- Da Costa, G. S. & Armandroff, T. E. 1995, *AJ*, 109, 2533
- Da Costa, G. S. 1998, *IAU Symp. 189: Fundamental Stellar Properties*, 189, 193
- Davoust, E. & Prugniel, P. 1990, *A&A*, 230, 67
- Dean, J. F., Warren, P. R., & Cousins, A. W. J. 1978, *MNRAS*, 183, 569
- de Marchi, G. 1999, *AJ*, 117, 303
- Denissenkov, P. A., Weiss, A., & Wagenhuber, J. 1997, *A&A*, 320, 115
- D’Cruz, N. L., Dorman, B., Rood, R. T., & O’Connell, R. W. 1996, *ApJ*, 466, 359
- D’Cruz, N. L. et al. 2000, *ApJ*, 530, 352
- D’Cruz, N. L., Rood, R. T., O’Connell, R. W., Dickens, R. J., Hatzidimitriou, D., Dorman, B., Landsman, W. B., & Whitney, J. H. 2002, *ASP Conf. Ser. 265: Omega Centauri, A Unique Window into Astrophysics*, 235
- Dickens, R. J. & Caldwell, S. P. 1988, *MNRAS*, 233, 677
- Dickens, R. J. & Woolley, R. v. d. R. 1967, *Royal Greenwich Observatory Bulletin*, 128, 255

- Dickens, R. J. & Bell, R. A. 1976, *ApJ*, 207, 506
- Dinescu, D. I., Girard, T. M., & van Altena, W. F. 1999, *AJ*, 117, 1792
- Dinescu, D. I., van Altena, W. F., Girard, T. M., & López, C. E. 1999, *AJ*, 117, 277
- Dinescu, D. I. 2002, *ASP Conf. Ser.* 265: *Omega Centauri, A Unique Window into Astrophysics*, 365
- Djorgovski, S. & Davis, M. 1987, *ApJ*, 313, 59
- Djorgovski, S. 1993, *ASP Conf. Ser.* 50: *Structure and Dynamics of Globular Clusters*, 373
- Djorgovski, S. & Meylan, G. 1993, *ASP Conf. Ser.* 50: *Structure and Dynamics of Globular Clusters*, 325
- Edvardsson, B., Andersen, J., Gustafsson, B., Lambert, D. L., Nissen, P. E., & Tomkin, J. 1993, *A&A*, 275, 101
- Elson, R. A. W., Gilmore, G. F., Santiago, B. X., & Casertano, S. 1995, *AJ*, 110, 682
- Lloyd Evans, T. 1983, *MNRAS*, 204, 975
- Fasano, G. & Franceschini, A. 1987, *MNRAS*, 225, 155
- Fellhauer, M. & Kroupa, P. 2002, *Ap&SS*, 281, 355
- Ferrarese, L. et al. 2000, *ApJS*, 128, 431
- Ferrarese, L. et al. 2000, *ApJ*, 529, 745
- Ferraro, F. R., Paltrinieri, B., Fusi Pecci, F., Cacciari, C., Dorman, B., & Rood, R. T. 1997, *ApJL*, 484, L145
- Ferraro, F. R., Paltrinieri, B., Pecci, F. F., Rood, R. T., & Dorman, B. 1998, *ApJ*, 500, 311
- Ferraro, F. R., Messineo, M., Fusi Pecci, F., de Palo, M. A., Straniero, O., Chieffi, A., & Limongi, M. 1999, *AJ*, 118, 1738
- Ferraro, F. R., Paltrinieri, B., Rood, R. T., & Dorman, B. 1999, *ApJ*, 522, 983
- Ferraro, F.R., Montegriffo, P., Origlia, L., & Fusi Pecci, F., 2000, *AJ*, 119, 1282

- Ferraro, F. R., Bellazzini, M., & Pancino, E. 2002, *ApJL*, 573, L95
- Ferraro, F. R., Pancino, E., & Bellazzini, M. 2002, *ASP Conf. Ser.* 265: *Omega Centauri, A Unique Window into Astrophysics*, 407
- François, P., Spite, M., & Spite, F. 1988, *A&A*, 191, 267
- Freeman, K. C. 1985, *IAU Symp.* 113: *Dynamics of Star Clusters*, 113, 33
- Freeman, K. C. 1993, *ASP Conf. Ser.* 48: *The Globular Cluster-Galaxy Connection*, 608
- Freeman, K. C. & Rodgers, A. W. 1975, *ApJL*, 201, L71
- Freeman, K. & Bland-Hawthorn, J. 2002, *ARA&A*, 40, 487
- Frenk, C. S. & Fall, S. M. 1982, *MNRAS*, 199, 565
- Frinchaboy, P. M. et al. 2002, *ASP Conf. Ser.* 265: *Omega Centauri, A Unique Window into Astrophysics*, 143
- Fusi Pecci, F., Ferraro, F. R., Bellazzini, M., Djorgovski, S., Piotto, G., & Buonanno, R. 1993, *AJ*, 105, 1145
- Fusi Pecci, F. et al. 1996, *AJ*, 112, 1461
- Gallino, R., Arlandini, C., Busso, M., Lugaro, M., Travaglio, C., Straniero, O., Chieffi, A., & Limongi, M. 1998, *ApJ*, 497, 388
- Geyer, E. H., Nelles, B., & Hopp, U. 1983, *A&A*, 125, 359
- Gerhard, O. 2000, *ASP Conf. Ser.* 211: *Massive Stellar Clusters*, 12
- Gnedin, O. Y., Zhao, H., Pringle, J. E., Fall, S. M., Livio, M., & Meylan, G. 2002, *ApJL*, 568, L23
- Gratton, R. G. 1982, *A&A*, 115, 336
- Gratton, R. G. 1989, *A&A*, 208, 171
- Gratton, R. G. 1999, *Ap&SS*, 265, 157
- Gratton, R. G. et al. 2001, *A&A*, 369, 87
- Gurzadyan, G. A. 2000, *New Astronomy*, 5, 349
- Harding, G. A. 1965, *Royal Greenwich Observatory Bulletin*, 99, 65

- Harbeck, D. et al. 2001, AJ, 122, 3092
- Harris, W. E. 1996, AJ, 112, 1487
- Hartwick, F. D. A. 1976, ApJ, 209, 418
- Hesser, J. E., Hartwick, F. D. A., & McClure, R. D. 1977, ApJS, 33, 471
- Hilker, M. & Richtler, T. 2000, A&A, 362, 895
- Hoffleit, D. & Jaschek, C. —. 1991, New Haven, Conn.: Yale University Observatory, —c1991, 5th rev.ed., edited by Hoffleit, Dorrit; Jaschek, Carlos —v(coll.),
- Hughes, J. & Wallerstein, G. 2000, AJ, 119, 1225
- Icke, V. & Alcaïno, G. 1988, A&A, 204, 115
- Ikuta, C. & Arimoto, N. 2000, A&A, 358, 535
- Irwin, M. & Hatzidimitriou, D. 1995, MNRAS, 277, 1354
- Johnson, H. R., Bernat, A. P., & Krupp, B. M. 1980, ApJS, 42, 501
- Jurcsik, J. 1998, ApJL, 506, L113
- Kaluzny, J., Kubiak, M., Szymanski, M., Udalski, A., Krzeminski, W., & Mateo, M. 1996, A&AS, 120, 139
- Kaluzny, J., Kubiak, M., Szymanski, M., Udalski, A., Krzeminski, W., Mateo, M., & Stanek, K. 1997, A&AS, 122, 471
- Kamper, K. W. & Wesselink, A. J. 1978, AJ, 83, 1653
- Kholopov, P. N., 1953, Publ. Astron. Sterneberg Inst. 23, 250
- King, I. R. & Anderson, J. 2002, ASP Conf. Ser. 265: Omega Centauri, A Unique Window into Astrophysics, 21
- Kozhurina-Platais, V., Girard, T. M., Platais, I., van Altena, W. F., Ianna, P. A., & Cannon, R. D. 1995, AJ, 109, 672
- Kraft, R. P. 1994, PASP, 106, 553
- Kruszewski, A. & Semeniuk, I. 1999, Acta Astronomica, 49, 561
- Kupka, F., Piskunov, N., Ryabchikova, T. A., Stempels, H. C., & Weiss, W. W. 1999, A&AS, 138, 119

- Lacy, C. H. 1977, ApJ, 213, 458
- Lambert, D. L., Smith, V. V., Busso, M., Gallino, R., & Straniero, O. 1995, ApJ, 450, 302
- Landolt, A. U. 1992, AJ, 104, 340
- Layden, A. C. & Sarajedini, A. 2000, AJ, 119, 1760
- Lee, M.G., Freedman, W.L, & Madore, B.F., 1993, ApJ, 417, 553
- Lee, Y.-W., Joo, J.-M., Sohn, Y.-J., Rey, S.-C., Lee, H.-C., & Walker, A. R. 1999, Nature, 402, 55
- Leon, S., Bergond, G., & Vallenari, A. 1999, A&A, 344, 450
- Leon, S., Meylan, G., & Combes, F. 2000, A&A, 359, 907
- Lindsay, E. M., 1956, Vistas in Astron., 2, 1057
- Lotz, J. M., Telford, R., Ferguson, H. C., Miller, B. W., Stiavelli, M., & Mack, J. 2001, ApJ, 552, 572
- Lub, J. 2002, ASP Conf. Ser. 265: Omega Centauri, A Unique Window into Astrophysics, 95
- Lyngå, G. 1996, A&AS, 115, 297
- Madore, B. F. & Freedman, W. L. 1995, AJ, 109, 1645
- Makino, J., Akiyama, K., & Sugimoto, D. 1991, Ap&SS, 185, 63
- Mallia, E. A. & Pagel, B. E. J. 1981, MNRAS, 194, 421
- Majewski, S. R., Patterson, R. J., Dinescu, D. I., Johnson, W. Y., Ostheimer, J. C., Kunkel, W. E., & Palma, C. 2000, The Galactic Halo : From Globular Cluster to Field Stars, 619
- Mandushev, G., Spasova, N., & Staneva, A. 1991, A&A, 252, 94
- Martin, W. C. 1938, Annalen van de Sterrewacht te Leiden, 17, 1
- Mateo, M., Udalski, A., Szymanski, M., Kaluzny, J., Kubiak, M., & Krzeminski, W. 1995, AJ, 109, 588
- Mateo, M. L. 1998, ARA&A, 36, 435

- Matteucci, F., Raiteri, C. M., Busson, M., Gallino, R., & Gratton, R. 1993, *A&A*, 272, 421
- Matteucci, F. & Recchi, S. 2001, *ApJ*, 558, 351
- Mayor, M. et al. 1997, *AJ*, 114, 1087
- Meléndez, J. & Barbuy, B. 1999, *ApJS*, 124, 527
- Merritt, D., Meylan, G., & Mayor, M. 1997, *AJ*, 114, 1074
- Meylan, G. & Mayor, M. 1986, *A&A*, 166, 122
- Meylan, G. 1987, *A&A*, 184, 144
- Meylan, G., Mayor, M., Duquenois, A., & Dubath, P. 1995, *A&A*, 303, 761
- Meylan, G. 2002, *ASP Conf. Ser. 265: Omega Centauri, A Unique Window into Astrophysics*, 3
- McWilliam, A., Preston, G. W., Sneden, C., & Searle, L. 1995, *AJ*, 109, 2757
- McWilliam, A. 1997, *ARA&A*, 35, 503
- Moehler, S., Napiwotzki, R., Sweigart, A. V., Landsman, W. B., & Dreizler, S. 2002, *ASP Conf. Ser. 265: Omega Centauri, A Unique Window into Astrophysics*, 247
- Montegriffo, P., Ferraro, F. R., Fusi Pecci, F., & Origlia, L. 1995, *MNRAS*, 276, 739
- Montegriffo, P., Ferraro, F. R., Origlia, L., & Fusi Pecci, F. 1998, *MNRAS*, 297, 872
- Moore, B. 1996, *ApJL*, 461, L13
- Moore, B., Governato, F., Quinn, T., Stadel, J., & Lake, G. 1998, *ApJL*, 499, L5
- Morgan, S. & Lake, G. 1989, *ApJ*, 339, 171
- Murray, C. A., Candy, M. P., & Jones, D. H. P. 1965, *Royal Greenwich Observatory Bulletin*, 100, 81
- Nave, G., Johansson, S., Learner, R. C. M., Thorne, A. P., & Brault, J. W. 1994, *ApJS*, 94, 221

- Noble, R. G., Buttress, J., Griffiths, W. K., Dickens, R. J., & Penny, A. J. 1991, MNRAS, 250, 314
- Norris, J. 1974, ApJ, 194, 109
- Norris, J. & Bessell, M. S. 1978, ApJL, 225, L49
- Norris, J. & Freeman, K. C. 1983, ApJ, 266, 130
- Norris, J. E., Da Costa, G. S., & Tingay, S. J. 1995, ApJS, 99, 637
- Norris, J. E. & Da Costa, G. S. 1995, ApJ, 447, 680
- Norris, J. E. & Da Costa, G. S. 1995, ApJL, 441, L81
- Norris, J. E., Da Costa, G. S., & Tingay, S. J. 1995, ApJS, 99, 637
- Norris, J. E., Freeman, K. C., & Mighell, K. J. 1996, ApJ, 462, 241
- Norris, J. E., Freeman, K. C., Mayor, M., & Seitzer, P. 1997, ApJL, 487, L187
- Oh, K. S., Lin, D. N. C., & Aarseth, S. J. 1995, ApJ, 442, 142
- Origlia, L., Moorwood, A. F. M., & Oliva, E. 1993, A&A, 280, 536
- Origlia, L., Ferraro, F. R., Fusi Pecci, F., & Oliva, E. 1997, A&A, 321, 859
- Origlia, L., Rich, R. M., & Castro, S. 2002, AJ, 123, 1559
- Origlia, L., Ferraro, F. R., Fusi Pecci, F., & Rood, R. T. 2002, ApJ, 571, 458
- Origlia, L., Ferraro, F. R., Bellazzini, M. & Pancino, E., 2003, accepted for publication in ApJ
- Pagel, B. E. J. 1992, IAU Symp. 149: The Stellar Populations of Galaxies, 149, 133
- Paltoglou, G. & Norris, J. E. 1989, ApJ, 336, 185
- Parmentier, G., Jehin, E., Magain, P., Neuforge, C., Noels, A., & Thoul, A. A. 1999, A&A, 352, 138
- Pancino, E., Ferraro, F.R., Bellazzini, M., Piotto, G. & Zoccali M. 2000, ApJL, 534, L83
- Pancino, E. 2002, ASP Conf. Ser. 265: Omega Centauri, A Unique Window into Astrophysics, 313

- Pancino, E., Pasquini, L., Hill, V., Ferraro, F. R., & Bellazzini, M. 2002, *ApJL*, 568, L101
- Pancino, E., Seleznev, A., Ferraro, F. R., Bellazzini, M. & Piotto, G. 2003, submitted to *MNRAS*
- Peacock, J. A. 1983, *MNRAS*, 202, 615
- Persson, S. E., Cohen, J. G., Matthews, K., Frogel, J. A., & Aaronson, M. 1980, *ApJ*, 235, 452
- Persson, S. E., Murphy, D. C., Krzeminski, W., Roth, M., & Rieke, M. J. 1998, *AJ*, 116, 2475
- Peterson, C. J. 1993, *ASP Conf. Ser.* 50: Structure and Dynamics of Globular Clusters, 337
- Piotto, G., Zoccali, M., King, I. R., Djorgovski, S. G., Sosin, C., Rich, R. M., & Meylan, G. 1999, *AJ*, 118, 1727
- Plez, B. 1992, *A&AS*, 94, 527
- Press W.H., Teukolsky S.A., Vetterling W.T., Flannery B.P., 1997, *Numerical Recipes of Fortran 77. The art of Scientific Computing.* 2nd Ed., Cambridge University Press, New York
- Pryor, C. & Meylan, G. 1993, *ASP Conf. Ser.* 50: Structure and Dynamics of Globular Clusters, 357
- Pulone, L., de Marchi, G., Paresce, F., & Allard, F. 1998, *ApJL*, 492, L41
- Recchi, S., Matteucci, F., & D'Ercole, A. 2001, *MNRAS*, 322, 800
- Renzini, A. & Fusi Pecci, F. 1988, *ARA&A*, 26, 199
- Rey, S., Lee, Y., Joo, J., Walker, A., & Baird, S. 2000, *AJ*, 119, 1824
- Richer, H. B., Fahlman, G. G., Buonanno, R., Fusi Pecci, F., Searle, L., & Thompson, I. B. 1991, *ApJ*, 381, 147
- Rood, R. T. 1973, *ApJ*, 184, 815
- Sakai, S., Madore, B. F., & Freedman, W. L. 1996, *ApJ*, 461, 713
- Salaris, M., & Cassisi, S., 1998, *MNRAS*, 298, 166
- Salaris, M., Chieffi, A., & Straniero, O. 1993, *ApJ*, 414, 580

- Sarajedini, A. & Layden, A. C. 1995, *AJ*, 109, 1086
- Searle, L. & Sargent, W. L. W. 1972, *ApJ*, 173, 25
- Searle, L. 1977, in *The Evolution of Galaxies and Stellar Populations*, ed. B. M. Tinsley & R. B. Larson
- Seitzer, P. O. 1983, Ph.D. Thesis, University of Virginia
- Seleznev, A. F. 1998, *Astronomy Reports*, 42, 153
- Schlegel, D. J., Finkbeiner, D. P., & Davis, M. 1998, *ApJ*, 500, 525
- Shetrone, M., Venn, K. A., Tolstoy, E., Primas, F., Hill, V., & Kaufer, A. 2003, *AJ*, 125, 684
- Silverman, B. W. 1986, *Monographs on Statistics and Applied Probability*, London: Chapman and Hall, 1986,
- Smecker-Hane, T., McWilliam, A., & Ibata, R. 1998, *Bulletin of the American Astronomical Society*, 30, 916
- Smecker-Hane, T., & McWilliam, A., 2003, submitted to *ApJ* ([astro-ph/0205411](#))
- Smith, G. H. & Tout, C. A. 1992, *MNRAS*, 256, 449
- Smith, V. V., Cunha, K., & Lambert, D. L. 1995, *AJ*, 110, 2827
- Smith, V. V., Suntzeff, N. B., Cunha, K., Gallino, R., Busso, M., Lambert, D. L., & Straniero, O. 2000, *AJ*, 119, 1239
- Smith, V. V. 2002, *ASP Conf. Ser.* 265: *Omega Centauri, A Unique Window into Astrophysics*, 109
- Snedden, C., Gratton, R. G., & Crocker, D. A. 1991, *A&A*, 246, 354
- Snedden, C. 1999, *APA&A*, 265, 145
- Spite, M. 1967, *Annales d'Astrophysique*, 30, 685
- Stetson, P. B. 1993, *ASP Conf. Ser.* 48: *The Globular Cluster-Galaxy Connection*, 14
- Stetson, P. B. 1994, *PASP*, 106, 250

- Straniero, O., Chieffi, A., Limongi, M., Busso, M., Gallino, R., & Arlandini, C. 1997, *ApJ*, 478, 332
- Suntzeff, N. 1993, *ASP Conf. Ser.* 48: *The Globular Cluster-Galaxy Connection*, 167
- Suntzeff, N. B. & Kraft, R. P. 1996, *AJ*, 111, 1913
- Sweigart, A. V. & Mengel, J. G. 1979, *ApJ*, 229, 624
- Sweigart, A. V., Brown, T. M., Lanz, T., Landsman, W. B., & Hubeny, I. 2002, *ASP Conf. Ser.* 265: *Omega Centauri, A Unique Window into Astrophysics*, 261
- Theis, C. 2002, *Ap&SS*, 281, 97
- Thompson, I.B., Kaluzny, J., Pych, W., Burley G., Krzeminski, W., Paczynski, B., Persson, S.E. & Preston, G.W. 2001, *AJ*, 121, 3089
- Thurl, C. & Johnston, K. V. 2002, *ASP Conf. Ser.* 265: *Omega Centauri, A Unique Window into Astrophysics*, 337
- Tolstoy, E., Venn, K. A., Shetrone, M., Primas, F., Hill, V., Kaufer, A., & Szeifert, T. 2003, *AJ*, 125, 707
- Trager, S. C., King, I. R., & Djorgovski, S. 1995, *AJ*, 109, 218
- Truran, J. W., Cowan, J. J., Pilachowski, C. A., & Sneden, C. 2002, *PASP*, 114, 1293
- van Leeuwen, F., Le Poole, R. S., Reijns, R. A., Freeman, K. C., & de Zeeuw, P. T. 2000, *A&A*, 360, 472
- van Leeuwen, F., Hughes, J. D., & Piotto, G. 2002, *ASP Conf. Ser.* 265: *Omega Centauri, A Unique Window into Astrophysics*,
- van den Bosch, F. C., Lewis, G. F., Lake, G., & Stadel, J. 1999, *ApJ*, 515, 50
- Vanture, A. D., Wallerstein, G., & Brown, J. A. 1994, *PASP*, 106, 835
- Vanture, A. D., Wallerstein, G., & Suntzeff, N. B. 2002, *ApJ*, 569, 984
- Ventura, P., D'Antona, F., Mazzitelli, I., & Gratton, R. 2001, *ApJL*, 550, L65
- Webbink, R. F. 1985, *IAU Symp.* 113: *Dynamics of Star Clusters*, 113, 541
- White, R. E. & Shawl, S. J. 1987, *ApJ*, 317, 246

- Whitney, J. H. et al. 1994, AJ, 108, 1350
- Whitney, J. H. Rood, R. T., O'Connell, R. W., D'Cruz, N. L., Dorman, B., Landsman, W. B., Bohlin, R. C., Roberts, M. S., Smith, A. M., Stecher, T. P. 1998, ApJ, 495, 284
- Woolley, R. R. 1966, Royal Observatory Annals, 2, 1
- Woosley, S. E. & Weaver, T. A. 1995, ApJS, 101, 181
- Zhao, H. S. 2002, ASP Conf. Ser. 265: Omega Centauri, A Unique Window into Astrophysics, 391
- Zinn, R. & West, M. J. 1984, APJS, 55, 45